

**Risk Management Framework - an Analysis of Risk Management Process
in SME's of the UK Construction Industry**

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DECLARATION

I declare that the work in this thesis was carried out in accordance with the regulations of the University of the West of Scotland and is original except where indicated by specific reference in the text. No part of the thesis has been submitted as part of any other academic award. The thesis has not been presented to any other education institution in the United Kingdom or overseas. Any views expressed in the thesis are those of the author and in no way represent those of the University.

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ABBREVIATIONS

AHP:	Analytical Hierarchy process
ASSE:	American Society of Safety Engineers
CHAS:	Contractor Health and Safety
CIOB:	Chartered Institute of Building
COBRA:	Co-Benefit Risk Assessment
FMEA:	Failure Mode Effective Analysis
ICE:	Institute of Civil Engineer
IPRA:	International Project Risk Assessment
ICRAM-1:	International Construction Risk Assessment Model
NPV:	Net Present Value
OECD:	Orgaization of Ecomnomic Co-operation and Development
PMBOK:	Project Management Body of Knowledge
RAM:	Risk Assessor Model
RICS:	Royal Institute of Chartered Surveyors
RM:	Risk Management
RMF:	Risk Management Framework
RMP:	Risk Management Process
TGP:	Three Gorges Project
WBS:	Work Breakdown Structure

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ABSTRACT

It is crucial to counter the multifaceted threats associated within construction project lifecycle, in particular for SME's in the UK construction industry, not only to secure work but also to make a profit. This research seeks to identify and evaluate these risks and their effective mitigation measures and to develop a risk management framework for the SME's in the UK construction industry, which the investors/ developers/ contractors can adopt when contracting construction work or during the project lifecycle. Furthermore, the current status of risk management and organizational culture is also evaluated.

Two surveys were conducted, and thirty-two critical risks were identified, categorized into six hierarchical risk levels subcategories, and evaluated and ranked their criticality. For the top 10 the identified risks, practical mitigation measures have also been proposed. The survey respondents have perceived almost all mitigation measures as effective.

Findings after the extraction of results were, that there are no active Risk Management Frameworks for the SME's in the UK construction industry. Considering all the factors identified which include the expertise, knowledge, resources and need, an easy to understand risk management framework is proposed which has 5 step procedures which is beneficial at any stage of the project cycle, and does not require special qualifications or knowledge to adopt and implement. All the guidelines are provided in the appendix for successful implementation of risk management framework.

Based on the findings and results from the questionnaire surveys and literature review, a qualitative risk management framework was finally proposed with its complete implementation guidelines provided, which will benefit the risk management of SME's in the UK construction industry.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

In the 20th century, where every year is bringing rapid developments, and risks are approaching, the obligatory for survival and achieving is knowing the environment and being susceptible of decision-making in a right and appropriate one. In case of not distinguishing both internal and external risk factors of the project, the managerial decision-making mistakes occur. Moreover, time and cost assessment forecasts go towards an adverse event. Risk management can identify risk-generating factors. Furthermore, risk management can command or eradicate such risk factors through computation and select suitable strategies. Zadeh (2010) illustrates that inspire of the predominant significance of risk management as one of the subfields of project management; regrettably, less concern has been given to risk management. In very few organizations, employers or contractors are appeared to be having a proper insight into risk management.

The risk is integral and hard to remove altogether. The risk is a condition of threat achieving the desired results, performance, quality and the budget of the construction project. Numerous projects collapse to accomplish their performance is the desired result due to the cost and time overruns (Zadeh, 2010). Uncontrollable and unmitigated risks are the source of project failure. However, risk cannot be eliminated completely, but it can be mitigated and restrained through the proper implementation of appropriate tools and techniques.

Construction is a high risk involving industry with not the best of the track record of managing with risk. The risk is a constitutional part of any construction project or any of the myriad categorization falling within the generality of the built environment. The involvement of the construction industry, as a result, have been facing the undesired outcomes of failure in the form of unplanned delays in project completion, with a cost exceeding the budget and sometimes failed to meet quality standards and operational requirements. So, effective risk management of construction associated risks remains a significant challenge to industry practitioners. With the increased uncertainties and complexities in identifying and assessing

risk in construction projects and the lack of information about risk assessment techniques due to deficiency of owner participation in risk sharing with the contractor, the need for risk analysis and management approach is increasing.

1.2 Research Background

The most consistent employment opportunities in a developed economy are through SME's, in any sector, which is an example of a health SME's structure and its essential contribution to the rising GDP (Chapman, 1994). They create the largest chunk of employment and generate the highest service volume by introducing innovation and welcoming entrepreneurs (Lee, 2012).

The construction industry is known to be the most energetic, risky and challenging industry and the associated activities, procedures, surrounding and culture is risk-prone (Chapman, C. 2008). SME's are in need of managing their risks more efficiently to boost their performance and raising the standard of the construction industry. They are known to be performing informal risk management procedures which are mostly unsuccessful, as they are working in most of the construction projects ongoing in a country (Rostami, 2015). Finance and technology are two things which restrict an SME to acquire cost-effective and time-efficient techniques (Welsh, White, 1981).

Research and surveys in the UK construction industry indicate the vulnerable knowledge of risk management within organizations (Smith, Lyons, 2004). Construction professionals have less training and knowledge about the techniques and disability to critically analyze the obtained results to practice an efficient risk management process for an organization (Kim, 2000; Frimpong, 2003).

Analyst Rostami (2015) found out that SME's most vigilant task is to adopt an appropriate type of tool or technique which suits their working style or a construction project. Organizational cultural resistance plays a vital role which minimizes their exposure to risk management procedures and its benefits. This is similar to what Chileshe, N and Kikwasi (2013) found out that the two most eminent challenges' of professionals in managing risks are less knowledge and presence of mind, which are in no position to mitigate the identified or unidentified risks. Therefore, it is almost unachievable to reduce the risk of SME's without the experience of risk assessment tools and techniques used in the construction industry.

1.3 Rationale

There were 2.1 million jobs in the construction industry in 2015, 6.2% of the total job opportunities in the UK (Rostami, 2016). There has been a steady increase in jobs in the construction industry in last ten years (despite falling in 2009 and 2010). In comparison to 2005, there is a decrease of 0.8% in construction jobs as figures were 7.0% in 2005 and in 2015 its 6.2% (Rhodes, 2015).

Gross value added (GVA) is the best unit to measure the contribution of any industry to UK economy. It only accounts for the 'added value', and excludes costs incurred in the production process (Rhodes, C. 2016). The total value of construction outcome in 2014 alone was £103 billion, 6.5% of the total economy. 2014 was the best years as industrial output rose by 9.5%, the enormous increase since last in 1990 (Smith, 2014).

The Federation of Small Businesses (FSB) manifesto reported that over 99% of the 3.7 million businesses in the UK are SMEs. Out of these 90% are micro, which means they have less than 10 employees. Out of 180,000 construction firms in the UK, 96% are assumed to have less than 8 employees (Jaunzens, 2021). More than 86% of employees work within SMEs in construction and are accountable of 75% of the turnover. SMEs wipeout about 40% of the energy used within the construction industry. They also make a part of UK gross national product with whooping figures of over 40%.

More than large organizations, SMEs are more exposed to risk, as they have fewer resources, finances, negligible risk management strategy and methodology to encounter internal and external threats (Verbano, 2019). It has been only a few years since research has started to implements risk management process in SME's; due to this reason, there are numerous areas which are still understudied.

This trouble is also intensified by SMEs' limited resources which make both implementation and practice of risk management more complicated (Wang, 2007). The take-up and method of risk management techniques involve a hefty level of investment which in some cases, is unaffordable for SMEs. So, in a nutshell, there are a lot of areas where SME's still needs work for example professional training and knowledge of risk management process, a dedicated person to deal with risk management, a certain amount of finance dedicated to this purpose and most important the change in the culture of accepting risk as an eminent

constituent of a construction project, where Raftery (2003) remarks that no construction job is big or small.

1.4 Scope

To ascertain the implementation of the risk management process by SME's in the UK construction industry for more equitable quantified risk analysis and recommend a risk management framework to improve SME's risk management practices in the UK construction industry. The questionnaire surveys are designed for the easy understanding of significant stakeholders in the construction industry affiliated with FMB(Federation of Master Builders), CIOB(Chartered Institute of Builders) and CHAS(Contractors Health and Safety Assessment Scheme), and later incorporating the results obtained to develop a risk management framework for the better implementation and procedure awareness of this risk management in the construction industry.

1.5 Objectives

- To analyze the current scenario of key risk management process and practices in the UK construction industry
- To evaluate the impact of risk management process on the overall performance of SMEs in the UK Construction industry..
- To explore the critical risk factors with indicators of cost, performance and time.
- To recommend a Risk Management Framework for SME's to mitigate the impact of risk.

1.6 Research Question

“How effective are Risk Management practices which are adapted in the SME's of the UK Construction Industry, and how a practical risk management framework be recommended to mitigate risks in SME's”

1.7 Methodology

To fulfil the above objectives, both secondary/ and primary data collection methods are used. The secondary data of a literature review mainly came from documentary sources published information from relevant institutions in the UK as well as from world organizations such as the IRM, IOR, IIRMS, ICE, IMF, the World Bank, academic Journals and relevant reference

books. The secondary data is mainly relying on relevant published sources from research journals, books, articles and report published in the UK Construction industry. The Primary data for the research is gathered through face-to-face interviews and questionnaire sent over to SME's carried out in London, Greater London, and Midlands. (See chapter 5). From all this research and its analysis based on the data collections, a UK Risk Management Framework for SME's detailing the relationship of critical risk factors and their significance to the projects success and survival of on a company in the construction sector for a more extended period is generated.

1.8 Summary

This research effort is considered a part of a comprehensive research in Risk Management Framework and Risk Management Process that is aimed at re-evaluating SME's construction risk management process and facilitating the abolition of the existing gap between theory and practice to improve SME's risk management practices in the UK. This research also seeks to identify and evaluate these risks and their effective mitigation measures and to develop a risk management framework for the SME's in the UK construction industry, which the investors or developers or contractors can adopt when contracting construction work during the project lifecycle. Furthermore, the current status of risk management and organizational culture is also evaluated. This introductory chapter has setup the basis of research considering all the objectives identified to be achieved in following chapters.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

Probability occurrence of an adverse event, and uncertainty is known as RISK. Its definition changes from industry to industry, but the central theme of an adverse event remains the same. A lot of different authors have explained risk in different scenarios.

Risk has multiple interpretations for various persons, and risk deviates according to point of view, perceptions, and experiences. From a technological point of view, architects, engineers, and contractors generally view risk, while developers and owners view it from the economic and financial side. Health and safety practitioners also recognize a major effect of risk (Zacharias, 2004). Risk in general, has been viewed as an experiential term of challenging measurements (Zacharias, 2007).

Present investigations of risk have a propensity towards focus on the two basic qualities of risk, close to risk and a test (Flanagan, 1993).

Accompanying by three segments the authors described the term risk as following:

1. Risk opportunity: What could happen to the hindrance or to the project?
2. Vulnerability of occasion: possibility of happening of the occasion (Raftery, 2003).
3. The likely misfortune/pick up: Significance of the event of opportunity that can be calculated as misfortune or benefit.

According to the given attributes, for the most part and numerous experts have determined risk in the accompanying condition (Al-Bahar,1990; Raftery, 2003).

Likelihood of an occasion Potential x (Uncertainty) misfortune magnitude /pick up = Risk

They clarify a risk as the manner by which a thing or circumstance can cause damage and openness as 'the degree to which the feasible beneficiary of the monetary commitment can be managed by the risk. The punishment is taken to indicate injury, harm, loss of execution, and funds, in spite of the fact that weakness enters the ideas of recurrence and likelihood (Haneef, 2012).

"Risk" is characterized as the opportunity of an unfavourable occasion contingent upon the conditions (Butler, 1982).

Risk has been clarified as the potential for undesirable or negative outcomes of an occasion or activity (Rowe, 1977). Additionally, it is characterized as a mix of risks and openness (Chicken and Posner, 1998). Current writing clarifies about risk have a tendency towards fixation on the two basic attributes of risk, as a challenge and risk “(Norman, Flanagan, 1993), the likelihood of event of something influencing project’s destinations; such an impact can be negative or positive (AS/NZS, 2004). The blend of recurrence or possibility of a predefined opportunity or risk to occur and the components of the results in the event of occurrence.

2.2 Definition of Risk

Risk has many definitions, the most commonly accepted and used definition relates the risk to the negative events, or a possibility of occurrence of a negative event. Risk is everywhere, it is present in every activity or sector. Every sector has different techniques of quantifying risks, but its basics remain same which are its probability and occurrence.

2.2.1 Risk Management Fundamentals

A combination of risk definitions has been used in projects construction, and not any particular standard definition or techniques accessible to portray the premise on which risk evaluation is set up. As indicated by (RAMP 1998), the risk is oftentimes featured in the construction industry as the presence of genuine or potential possibilities or risks influencing projects“ goals while appointing, working, or charging the undertaking. As indicated by (Crandall, Al-Bahar,1990) the meaning of risk as it is an openness to likelihood of occurring mishaps well or horribly, which decides the project’s objective as an outcome of uncertainty (Al-Bahar, Crandall, 1990). As indicated by (Gibson, Walewski, 2003), as referenced by Ioannou and Dias (1995), two types are characterized by risk:

1. Unadulterated risk exist when monetary disaster chances are higher than monetary benefit
2. Theoretically, risk incorporates two additions and misfortunes

Conclusive investigation by CII on risk construction (Diekmann, 1998) uses exemplary activities to distinct the ideas of certainty, uncertainty/vulnerability, risk and all are well-spoken to the writing (Smith, 2001; ASCE, 1979; CIRA, 1994; Kangari, 1995; Hastak, Shaked, 2000; PMI, 2001) estimated as back to back methodologies of risk management: 1) by identification, 2) then to evaluate, 3) further assessment/examination of the effect and 4) the response of management. Being stress with respect to construction risks has made various endeavors improve risk management strategies. For example, the Institute of Actuaries in the United Kingdom and Institute of Civil Engineers planned to work on a project named as “Risk Analysis and Management of Projects (RAMP,1998)”. The mentioned method involves the application of concurred risk to identify and alleviate risks as well as undertaking panels system via fixation of risks occur during the whole lifecycle at the project. After legitimate strategic arrangement during the project lifecycle, clients are desirable to pursue after just as investigating arranged stretches.

Probability investigation construction is recorded as equal as risk appraisal of customer (Al-Bahar,Crandall, 1990; Liftson, Shaifer, 1992). Occasions need such techniques far reaching, fundamentally unrelated, and temporarily self-ruling. In any case, construction incorporates numerous elements, and choosing similitude, dependence, and causality are habitually hard. Consequently, abstract scientific strategies that depend on past encounters and information on firms and individuals can measure uncertainty/vulnerability impact and risk construction (Bajaj, 1997). Risks could be effectively managed in one of the different techniques.

As per the working of Lyons & Skitmore (2020), the executives found out work risky to arrange and use during the periods of project life cycle is more than its work during end or applied stages. In contradiction of the assessment, the application of risk management is enormous during the project’s calculated period.

2.3 Procedure of Risk Management

Undertaking risk has been resolved as an unsure position or condition that if there should be an occurrence of experiencing has positive or negative effects on project, similar to scope, time, cost, or quality (i.e. reason for the task considering time is to convey it dependent on planned arranging when the goal of the task with respect to cost is to convey it dependent on allowed cost). An undertaking risk (see appendix B-1) may come from at least one grounds and have at least one impacts in the event of finding. For instance, the explanation may be the

requirement for arising a natural grant to play out a movement or the absence of specialists for planning the undertaking. Risk happens when the area whose commitment is to give the grant delays over the thing is made prior to giving the license or the absence of a lot of planners for the action. On the off chance that any of these risks happen, a few results will influence the task timetable, execution, or cost. Risks could arise as a result of an undertaking focused or association arranged climate, which may bring about project risk. For example, different simultaneous activities, absence of incorporated administration frameworks, helpless task the board practices, or dependence on outside gatherings wild.

As per The European Standard On Risk Management (AS/NZS, 2004), the risk management cycle set out in the Standard is represented in Figure 2.1.

2.1: General Risk Assessment Framework (AZS, 2004)

There has been extensive study involved in understanding the different definitions of risk from numerous authors, in **table 2.1**; there are few of them mentioned

Table 2.1: Risk Definition as per Literature

Author	Title
Guikema and Imbeah (2009)	Used the Sophisticated Programmatic Risk Identification and Control model to handle construction projects
Batson (2009)	Risk Assessment Recognition Approaches for Preparation and Implementation of Building
Liu and Low (2009)	Creating a Risk

	Management Organizational Learning-Based Model in Chinese Construction Companies
Zhao & Duan (2008)	An Integrated Model of Risk Assessment for Building Projects Hlaing et al. (2008) Singapore Construction Contractors' Perceptions on Recognition of Construction Risk
Hui and Yong (2008)	Model Identification of Risk Management System Nasirzadeh et al, (2008) Construction Risk Management Integration of System Dynamics and Fuzzy Logic Modelling
Haghnevis & Sajedi (2008)	A Project Management Risk Model for Developing Countries Shokravi et al. (2008) Risk Assessment and Tunneling Analysis Via FMEA (see appendix B-5)
Tang et al. (2007)	Risk Management within the Chinese industry
Lam et al. (2007)	Modeling Risk Allocation call In Construction Contracts (see appendix B-2)
Liu et al. (2007)	Key problems and challenges of risk management and insurance in China's industry
Z. Zhang, and Wang (2007)	Understanding the key risks in production comes in China
Sheykh et al, (2007)	Practical Study of Risk Management; Power Plant Project Aliahmadi et al. (2007) Management of Risks In Supply Chain Projects
Afify and Hassanein (2007)	Contractor Risk Control Practices: A Case Study of Power Station Ventures in Egypt Lyons and Skitmore (2004) In the Queensland Engineering Construction Sector, Project Risk Management: A Survey
Walewski and Gibson	Risk Management for the Multinational

(2003)	Project;
	Procedures, processes, and vital factors
Khajeh and Hadi (2003)	Risk Management Implementation

Implementation of Risk Management

Management of risk is a central bit of strategic management of any organization. It is the cycle whereby firms deliberately address the risks relating to their activities with the objective of achieving upheld advantage inside each construction and across the plan, things being what they are. The point of convergence of good risk management is to identify first and treatment of these risks. It will probably expand the estimation of the overall large number of activities of the organization. It marshals the perception of the conceivable likely increase and downside of every single one of those factors which can impact the organization. It assembles the probability of achievement and reduces both the likelihood of dissatisfaction and the weakness of achieving its overall objections. Management of risk should be constant and making measure that runs all through the organizational framework and its utilization. It should address methodically all the risks incorporating the relationships past, present, and future. It ought to be facilitated into the organizational lifestyle with a reasonable methodology and a program drove by the most senior organization. It should make an understanding of the procedure into key and operational targets, consigning obligation all through the relationship with each boss and delegate liable for regulating risk as a part of their duties portrayal. It maintains obligation, execution assessment, and prize, as needs be progressing operational capability at all levels.

Factors external and internal

The risks were defying bythe organization, and its undertakings can result from external and inward components to the organization. The diagram overleaf summarizes occurrences of key risks in these regions and shows that some specific risks can have external and inside drivers and thusly cover the two regions. They can be arranged further into sorts of risk, for instance, key, financial, operational, risk, etc.

Figure 2.2: Organizational Risks (Zadeh, 2017)

It is an important part of risk management protection and value addition to the firm and obviously to its stakeholders as it is a big support for the organizational objective achievement by giving a framework to an organization that enables future construction to happen in a dependable and controlled manner, improving dynamic, orchestrating, and prioritization by the broad and coordinated understanding of the business activity, precariousness, and errand opportunity/risk, adding to more capable use/assignment of capital and resources inside the firm, decreasing unusualness in the unnecessary zones of the business, making sure about and redesigning assets and companions picture, making and supporting people and the organizational data base, progressing operational profitability. The rule fragments of the risk management cycle are described under:

Build up the Context

Identification of risk is typically the focal piece of risk management, however as per the outline, it isn't the initial segment of the risk management cycle. It is basic to know what in the undertaking is at risk of danger to recognize a risk. The standard technique's underlying

job is to defined limits for the setting of the risk appraisal, which can be partitioned into two segments. Distinct and imaginative.

Descriptive Philosophy

To ensure that immeasurably significant risks/dangers are seized, it is fundamental to comprehend the company's targets inside which risks will be tended to. This is the distinct part of the setting investigation.

For an organization that is a bit of a greater endeavour, a practice may be typical but good enough to find out a connection between the parent cycle and destination. Keep it assured that there is no existence of huge speculations possibly ignorance of certain destinations, it is principal to explore the arrangement between goals at different levels in the association.

Creative/ Inventive

The following segment of the setting investigation is creative or innovative rather than descript. Risk distinguishing proof normally is unfruitful if an endeavour is made to thoroughly consider an organization completely. It would be significantly more financially knowledgeable to isolate it into certain parts for identification of risk/hazard. These parts are portrayed as basic segments in the Standard.

Key segments are an assortment of subjects that must be respected individually inside the risk identification cycle. By and large, every point is marginally more modest than the idea of the organization, empowering those completing the risk awareness to focus on their thought reflections and get into more understanding than they would in the event that they endeavoured to deal with the whole organization in one round. An amazing arranged gathering of key parts will spur imaginative thoughts, and ensure that all basic issues are considered before those responsible for awareness of risk..

2.3.1 Identifying Threats/ Risks

First phas0065 of the risk management method in order to identify the threats for further procedure. Critical analysis of the situation or project is required to determine the risk involved fully, as risks that are not specified are likely to become threats in the future (Ahmet, O. 2003). There are several risk identification instruments and procedures used in the construction industry, namely: brainstorming, Delphi technique, previous project record,

work breakdown structure (P.M. Book, 2001). Work break down (WBS) is an efficient technique that reduces a risk event's chances, which may be missed.

The following methods can make risk identification:

Brainstorming:

Among the most accepted processes. Widely, it is used for the creation of ideas, all related entities involved with the initiative unite in one location is often favourable for risk recognition. There has been a facilitator who instructs the participants on different issues and only after the considerations is penned down. The mediator checks the items before closing them, and excludes the unwanted stuff.

Delphi Technique:

This method is like conceptualizing, yet members don't have any acquaintance with one another, and they are absent together. They will recognize the variables without speaking with different member the empowering influence, as in conceptualizing, measures the distinguished elements.

Interviewing/Expert Opinion:

Experts or staff with enough involvement with an undertaking can be an incredible assistance in maintaining a strategic distance from/taking care of relatable issues again and again. All the members or the pertinent people in the undertaking can be met to distinguish factors influencing risk.

Experience from Past:

Experience derived from past undertaking a comparative extent, the thought possibly shaped to recognize the variables. When looking at the qualities of undertakings will give a genuine image of the normal components.

Checklists/Agendas:

These are convenient however clear slanted variables' arrangements of variables thought as possible venture's risk Recognized agenda containing risks rundown in undertakings endeavoured previously as well as methodology of risks gives a crown start in identification of risk.

2.3.1.1 Description of Risk

Description of risk intends to assign the perceived risks in a coordinated organization, for example, by using a table/plan. The risk depiction table detail can be used to consider the depiction and assessment of risks. Accepting an inside and out arranged structure is basic to ensure an organized risk conspicuous verification, depiction, and assessment measure. By considering the outcome and probability of all of the risks set out in the table, it should be anything besides hard to arrange the essential risks should have been dismembered in more detail. Conspicuous verification of the dangers stressed over business activities and dynamic may be organized as fundamental, operational and tactical. It is essential to get control over risk management at the sensible period of errands and for the span of the life of a specific endeavor.

1. Name of Risk	
2. Scope of Risk	Qualitative description of the events, their size, type, number and dependencies
3. Nature of Risk	Eg. strategic, operational, financial, knowledge or compliance
4. Stakeholders	Stakeholders and their expectations
5. Quantification of Risk	Significance and Probability
6. Risk Tolerance/ Appetite	Loss potential and financial impact of risk Value at risk Probability and size of potential losses/gains Objective(s) for control of the risk and desired level of performance
7. Risk Treatment & Control Mechanisms	Primary means by which the risk is currently managed Levels of confidence in existing control Identification of protocols for monitoring and review
8. Potential Action for Improvement	Recommendations to reduce risk
9. Strategy and Policy Developments	Identification of function responsible for developing strategy and policy

Figure 2.3: Description of Risk (Norman, 2017)

2.3.1.2 Reporting of Risk

Various levels inside a company need additional data from the cycle of risk management. The Board of Directors ought to: most basic risks/dangers included, mindful/aware of the potential consequences for investor estimation of the distinction to foreseen execution ranges, ensure legitimate degrees of mindfulness/awareness all through the organization, ought to

know about how the organization will adapt to an emergency, know the noteworthiness of partner trust in the organization, realize how to speak with the speculation network where pertinent, have a thought regarding the cycle of risk management is working viably, Issue a reasonable risk management strategy itemizing the risk/danger management theory and duties Business Units ought to, risk awareness which is their obligation, the potential effects these may have on different locales, and the impact different territories may have on them, have implementation/execution markers which supervise the unequivocal business and monetary exercises, progress towards destinations, and recognize advancements which require mediation (e.g., gauges and financial plans), have arrangements which impart contrasts in spending plans and gauges at the right recurrence to permit the move to be made, report reliably and speedily to upper administration of any possible new risks/dangers or disappointments of current control measures.

People ought to comprehend their duty regarding singular risks, see how they can consistently improve the response of risk management, comprehend that risk management and its awareness are a basic piece organizational life cycle.

2.3.1.3 External/Outer Reporting

An organization needs to report its stakeholders, consistently setting out its approaches of risk management and unwavering quality in accomplishing its objectives. Stakeholders see organizations to give proof of useful administration of the association's non-monetary presentation in such regions as network issues, basic freedoms, work practices, wellbeing and security, and the climate.

Reporting of Risk, correspondence, and great corporate administration necessitate that organizations receive a precise way to deal with risk management which shields the interests of their partners, guarantees that the Board of Directors delivers its obligations to coordinate system, construct worth, and screen the project's exhibition, guarantees that administration controls are in position and are point by point satisfactorily. The game plans for the essential detailing of risk management ought to be featured and be accessible to the partners.

The official or authority reporting should address the control techniques upper administration obligations regarding the risk management cycle the cycles used to feature risks and how the risk management frameworks manage them, the essential control frameworks set up to counter huge risks, the checking and survey framework is set up. Any important lacks

uncovered by the framework or the framework itself ought to be accounted for along with the means taken to manage them.

2.3.2 Assessment of Risk

Developing/producing and understanding the risk is risk assessment. It helps the analyst if the uncertainty needs treatment and the appropriate strategy to treat the most cost-effective way. It involves the sources of risk generation, their positive and negative effect, and the probability of their occurrence (Al-Bahar, 1990). The IRM (2013) report suggests that risk analysis aids identify uncertainty and provides many options to facilitate final cost.

Risk assessment is comprised of two kinds of assessment techniques: qualitative and quantitative.

Figure 2.4: Types of *Risk Assessment Techniques*

They both are dependent upon the data raised by risk identification, whereas the qualitative assessment depends upon the judgment of experienced professionals, risk ranking, comparison, and information (El-Gafy, 2007). Quantitative techniques (see appendix B-6, B-9, B-11) include the variable and their mathematical calculations to determine the severity of risk (Ahmet, 2003). Few widely practiced qualitative and quantitative risk assessment techniques are detailed below.

2.3.2.1 Quantitative Measures:

Analysis of Sensitivity:

For the identification of the components of threatened project, having high impact on the result. Risk model designed and after that sensitivity analysis is experimented in correspondence of the sensitivity of the model to the model's vital elements on outcome of

the project. By changing the measures of one variable at one time changes in the project outcome or the impact of the changes has been clearly seen (see appendix B-10).

Analysis of Scenario:

If the changing risks coincide then analysis of scenario unveils the effect of various scenarios of the project. The decision which will be in the favour of risk of security or can cover maximum risks or calamities addition with minimum chances of loss in future that would be taken and that will be the right choice to choose.

Simulation of Monte Carlo /Probabilistic Analysis:

It is a process or model shows different uncertainty tiers' impact on the achievable objectives. Simulation of Monte Carlo is usually castoff for this analysis of risk. Impact of uncertainties on project cost & time can be viewed out by this. It chooses random figure for every factor in the distribution of probability also gives calculation for numerous times. Three stages of estimation are captured by this system nearby, highly bad and the best one and thus the risk management is calculated (see appendix B-7).

Trees Decision:

The decision tree diagram does this analysis. Trees of decision trees are favourable for the formulation of problem and option evaluation we use graphical model in this analysis and the effects of the decisions on the project are checked after that.

2.3.2.2 Subjective/Qualitative Techniques:

Subjective techniques for risk appraisal depend on engaging scales and are utilized for specifying the probability and effect of risk. These relatively straightforward procedures apply when a risk audit is asked in little and medium-size projects. Additionally, this technique is by and large utilized in the event of insufficient, restricted, or inaccessible mathematical information and restricted assets of time and cost. They are recorded as follows:

Effect of Appraisal and Risk Probability:

The probability of unfavourable occasion's happening is estimated by using this strategy. Furthermore, with respect to the constructive outcomes on situations the risk control-on an

undertaking extension is assessed. Unfriendly impacts also come about because of risks. For this appraisal, probability and impact must be nitty gritty and traditionally fitted to a particular project. Therefore a suggestion is that far away from of scale must be outlined, and its level depends on the tendency of venture, measures, as well as destinations. 'Improbable to practically certain' this scope is recognized by PMI (Project Management Institute) and it is an excellent scope provided; notwithstanding, coordinating mathematical evaluation is allowable. The effect scale differs from 'low' to 'high.'

Probability/likelihood Effect of Risk Rating Lattice:

For the reason of quantitative examination Probability & effect is used. Accordingly, calculated results derived by using different measures are organized via other different techniques available for counting in the writing. The scope, rating and shading is permitted to explain the importance of every risk. High probability effect of risk is supposed as high risk and it needs to be cover at main priority. Conversely, Low scoring denotes a low level of risk and it is not dangerous enough and can be sorted out as per require mentor timely.

Categorisation of Risk and Assessment of Risk Urgency:

Risk categorisation is a method of arranging project chances. As indicated by their sources, to select regions of the task that are generally presented to those risks. Instruments that can be utilized in this technique are work breakdown structure (WBS) or risk breakdown structure (RBS), and their job is to detail successful risk response. WBS separates complex exercises into little, sensible units and makes a connected, various levelled arrangement of free exercises. RBS sorts risks/dangers and shows their conditions.

2.3.3 Risk Response Development

In this phase, the analysts plan to the identified and quantified potential risks which can affect negatively on the project life cycle. Furthermore, the risks are prioritised, and action is taken against them by nominating the actual owner of the risk. The institute of risk management (2010) demonstrates in their report is that treatment of risk includes as significant element, risk control/alleviation, yet stretches out further to, for instance, risk avoidance, risk transfer/move, risk financing, and so on risk response/reaction advancement stage incorporates the huge risk chooses control/relief, however it is additionally cut back to avoidance of risk, transfer of risk, retention of risk and risk minimization. Dependable

proprietors of risk are allotted for its relief and dealing with the adequacy (Hillson, 2001). Its components are characterized underneath.

Avoidance of Risk:

Risk can be countered by eliminating the base of the risk of executing the undertaking an unmistakable way while as yet proposing to achieve project destinations. Change project management intend to destroy risk, to isolate project destinations from the impact of risk, or to mix the target venture which is exposed to bad luck, e.g. broadening timetable & degree diminishing.

Transfer/Transmission of Risk:

Transfer/Transmission of risk requests to discover any other gathering who happily acknowledge the obligation for its management, as well as must be this much bearing for the obligation of the risk and allow that to happen. Moving a risk does not mean it is ended over but it exist and can be openly seen by other gatherings any time in future. Moving risk is supposed to be an important approach in a venture to deal with monetary risks.

Reduction/Mitigation of Risk:

Mitigation of risk cut down the impact of a negative risk/danger event and probability to a suitable edge. By taking prior act to dilute likelihood or risk impact is mostly most effective to repair the damage rather than to maintain it after the occurrence of event or damage.

Risk/Hazard Exploit:

The methodology kills the vulnerability connected with a specific potential gain risk by making the open door occurs. Eliminate the vulnerability related with a specific potential gain risk. Risk instance, an alternative is depicted that happens in an event, would positively touch the undertaking results.

Risk/Danger Share:

Allocate risk ownership of an opportunity to another gathering that is best ready to build its likelihood of event and increment the potential advantages on the off chance that it occurs. Moving risks/dangers and sharing open doors are moreover in that an outsider is utilized,

those to whom the risks are moved interpretation of the obligation and those to whom openings are assigned ought to likewise be permitted to partake in the possible advantages.

Enhancement of Risk:

This technique plans to adjust the "size" of the positive risk. The open door is compounded by expanding its likelihood and effect, subsequently expanding the advantages picked up from the task. It was endeavouring to help or harden the reason for the opportunity and proactively focusing on and animate its sett off conditions.

Acceptance of Risk:

Lastly, it is difficult to annihilate all risks or make the most of all chances. We can record them and impart the attentiveness that they are available and recognized. Given procedure viewed when it is outrageous expected to give a reaction towards risk by other methodology, possibly a reaction isn't vindicated by brightness of risk. At a stage where the venture group and the undertaking administrator decide to admit a risk, all accord to address the risk whenever it occurs.

Emergency course of action:

It represents a fallback plan which is utilized whenever a negative incident takes place. Possibilities of appending are always catered and then reserved strike to deal unidentified risks or in the method of expenses to manage new risks.

2.3.4 Risk Response Control

The conclusion in the ending of the procedure comprises of implementation of strategy, monitoring uncertain events, deploying the counter plans and re-identifying the new potential risk. The complete risk management procedure requires risk reporting and monitoring, to make sure that risk which was effectively-identified, then critically analysed have an efficient control and response structure to mitigate them (Salman, 2005).

2.4 Benefits of Risk Management Process

There are no doubts about the advantages of formal risk management procedures which define the ways to deal the risks, and boost confidence and consistency in decision making which directly benefits the project timely completion and cost overrun. It also permits the

project estimators on different levels of the projects to allow contingency and accurate calculations to deal with uncertainty, which becomes an easy job for auditors and finance controllers. The risk management strategy proposed by researcher Smith, (2011) is as follow:

Figure 2.5 : Risk Management Strategy (Smith, 2011)

2.5 Risk Definition

The involving of risk changes when time goes on, and the implications topple when they are at the specific socio-social and recorded condition which we are situated in. (Deborah, Lupton, 1999) Risk is weakness to the hypothesis of monetary or monetary misfortune or gain, actual harm or injury, or postponement, because of the vulnerability connected with drawing in a specific game-plan (Cooper, Chapman, 1987). As per Cornelius Keating, the risk isn't the current issue which ought to be promptly managed, however it is accepted as future issues that can be invalidated or moderated. Risk is seen as a circumstance which may prompt negative outcomes.

It is uncertainty or possibility of having an adverse event in a project or activity. The meaning of risk varies from person to person; it depends on attitude, experience and viewpoint. It is perceived as a technical issue by engineers, contractors and designers, whereas it is a financial issue for clients and developers (Zacharias, 2007). Analyst Iyer, (2005) defined risk as:

- "Event of risk: what might go wrong or in favour of the project?" (Iyer, 2005)
- "Probability of profit/loss: Potential of loss or gain."

Several authors have claimed to calculate the impact of risk with the given equation (Raftery, 2003, Al-Bahar, 1990).

Risk/hazard= Potential or magnitude of loss/gain. x probability of the event (Uncertainty)

2.6 Construction Industry and the Concept of Risk

The construction industry experienced a wide assortment of risks that may happen in the financing, planning, constructing, and overseeing offices of an undertaking. There are different meanings of risk in the construction business. To understand the risk management cycle, it is imperative to comprehend the fundamental considered risk in all viewpoints. The worldwide standard "Undertaking risk management holds the hypothesis of likelihood and outcome and characterizes risk as a blend of the probability of an occasion which is happening and its belongings to project destinations (IEC 2001). Ward and Chapman (2003) have made a more extensive meaning of chance and propose utilizing a broader idea of vulnerability. They contend that risk is considered as risks yet not chances, and when it happens, it influences the project's performance. Edwards (1995) calls attention to that risk negatively affect the project's cost, quality or time as a rule. These definitions have a typical element: they characterize risk as far as questionable occasions and may have a positive or negative effect on a venture's destinations.

As per Ann (2020), risk understandings can be considered as the accompanying, the same as the word 'risk', the result of an unwanted result or disappointment, chances of accomplishing a given result, signifies danger/risk, taking a possibility in an action.

A (2010) contends the term risk can be characterized in the two parts: the likelihood of event of the risk and the greatness of the results if the risk occurred. Also, the relationship is written in the recipe: Risk = outcomes x likelihood. The overall risk pattern is appeared in figure 3.1 underneath. At the point when the likelihood of event is high, the results of risks appear to be low and the other way around. Risks with critical or seriousness items infrequently occur, however chances which are or have low outcomes will in general happen much of the time.

As referenced over, the condition is by all accounts basic; notwithstanding, the main thing is to comprehend and figure the likelihood of event and the seriousness of results and express those utilizing numbers.

2.7 Construction Industry and Significance of Risk Management

Change is natural for construction work. At the point when a dubious occasion happens, it will affect a portion of the destinations, for example, the cost, timetable, and nature of the project. Construction projects frequently have terrible showing because of an absence of sound risk management cycle. (Liu, Renhu, 2005) Many activities neglect to comply with the time constraint or cost and quality targets. Thus, management of risks turns into a fundamental piece of construction management. Risk management expects to distinguish and deal with those potential and unexpected issues that may presumably happen during the task usage. And furthermore, it attempts to recognize whatever number risk occasion as could reasonably be expected limit their effect on the project, deal with the reactions to those occasions that are likely to appear and give possibility assets to cover risk/hazard occasion that arise. The fundamental motivation behind risk management is to improve project performance through systematic/orderly distinguishing identification, evaluation and the project management related risks. The attention on diminishing risks or unfavourable results, which we may call 'disadvantage' risk, misses an imperative piece of the general picture. (Chapman, Ward, 2003) Changes can't be dispensed with, nonetheless, by applying risk management in undertaking construction, partakes can improve construction management. The advantage of risk management can be closed as follows. Project issues are explained, perceived and considered from the beginning, decisions are upheld by exhaustive investigation, the definition and structure of the venture are persistently checked, an away from of explicit risks related with a task, the construction of chronicled information to aid future risk management methods. (An, 2010).

2.7.1 Consultation and Communication

Meeting and correspondence is both a crucial segment of the risk management cycle and a critical helpful result. Effective risk management depends on accomplishing an elevated level of inventive info and including all gatherings with a task to carry out in accomplishing a fruitful result for the undertaking or business measure being tended to. In both the arranging and execution of the risk management cycle, it is noticeable to ensure that all the individuals who require to be included are given sufficient occasion to do as such and are kept educated regarding improvements in the comprehension of risks and the measures taken to manage them.

2.8 Global and Local Construction Industry with Risk Classification

The underlying phase of risk management is risk identification, where potential risks associated with construction projects are perceived. Risk order is an essential piece of risk identification, attempting to coordinate various risks impacting a construction project. An assortment of strategies for arranging chances has been suggested in the writing. A rundown of components was taken out from certain assets by (Perry ,Hayes, 1985) which were filed with respect to their association with suggested three strategies for classifying risk through an incorporated strategy of general frameworks hypothesis concerning work breakdown structure as a structure being as per the following: by means of perceiving type, result, and effect of risk. Chapman, (2001) arranged risks to four subcategories: project, industry, customer, and climate. Out of 58 risks perceived associated with Sino-Foreign construction t joint endeavors, (Shen , 2001) arranged them in 6 gatherings as per risks" nature, for example lawful, market, monetary, the executives, specialized, and strategy and political. Generally speaking, a few strategies exist for classifying chances connected to construction projects, and the ground why a technique is utilized will set up on the destinations of the examination.

Abdou, (1996) arranges risks in three principal gatherings, to be specific construction, construction of money, and construction plan, and definite the risks accepting different authoritative collaborations among different construction parties enrolled being developed, plan and execution of the project.

Kalayjian, (2000) in his investigation about shrouded risks of construction in the third world characterized not many of essentially experienced in the present worldwide construction field into four gatherings which are as per the following:

Political Risk and Country: The exhibition of the country's economy and political security significantly affects home-grown construction action and project. Conspicuous risk scomprise of monetary strategy and legislative money related obligation; worldwide exchanging organizations; accessibility of assets; framework improvement; interior solidness; just as changes in administrative timetable and political administration.

Financial Risk: The monetary practicality of a venture depends on its capital getting sorted out and ability to draw trustworthy assets of financing at coherent terms. Risks contain the owners" intensity of obtaining enough credit; advance; expect the flimsiness of money trade rates.

Environmental and Climate Risk: Building destinations are helpless against the adjustments in the climate and cataclysmic events like snowstorms, storms and tremors. Another risk can be lessening other hazardous squanders and severe ecological enactment.

Construction and Design Risk: Being blessed in construction projects depends on the dynamic intensity of their top level groups. Risks that should be dealt with incorporate a successful group choice cycle; gaining grants and outsider simultaneousness in a convenient way; acquirement of enough work, materials and gear; observing changes in work scope; quality control affirmation; and guaranteeing in general consistence with legally binding commitments.

Scientist (Hassanein, Afify, 2007) in their examination about risk management practices of contractual workers: a contextual analysis of intensity station projects in Egypt referenced a short depiction of seven risk classifications, which are as per the following:

Risks of Owner Obligation: the agenda embraced factors which ought to be announced in the agreement to explain owner's" duties and to the affirmation of these obligations would think of time. It includes: an obvious clarification of duties; time needed for activity with amendment affirmation of obligations are not performed will be confined in agreements.

Risks with respect to interface with different temporary workers: the agenda included explicit things to moderate risks identified with interfaces with different temporary workers.

Liability related Risks: the agenda remembered explicit measures to be contained for the agreements to guarantee the fair designation of liabilities.

Financial Risks: the agenda referenced about some monetary risks which are identified with the projects in this investigation.

Identification of Risk with changes: the agenda tended to explicit arrangements concerning the synchronous advancement of plan and construction stages on the two quick track projects under examination.

Technical Risk/ dangers: the agenda gave relating to comparative principles and codes and on the grounds that the two projects introduced were offered globally, which makes temporary workers from various nations.

Consortium chances: as referenced previously, in certain agreements, contractual workers are asked to make partnership including unfamiliar and nearby contractual workers as a prerequisite of offering capability.

McConnell, (1996) summarized risk classes in a positioning, which request project administrators to be aware of during executing the arranging of the undertaking. In such a manner, the risks illustrated may be evaded.

McConnell, (1996) referenced four principle gatherings of risks: absence of information, prerequisites, the board issues, and conditions. Necessity risks could be normally occurred by lack of a brilliant vision for the general task, absence of accord on the prerequisite, particularly inside the association generally, conditions that are not in fact organized, construction inside a quickly changing climate utilizing an unbending project management strategy, helpless change management measures that don't supply documentation for later reference.

To forestall dependence risk, a project supervisor should know the accompanying issues inter-component conditions inside the product, Inter-group conditions happen during work is part of transversely capacities, sub-contractor connections and conveyance trustworthiness according to plan, individuals' handiness to execute chore capacities at required time.

Risks identifying with the board issues regularly comes from the blend of issues referenced in two last gatherings: helpless generally arranging and errand distinguishing proof inside the project, helpless decidability problem into real undertaking status either due to poor project the executives or obscurity by project colleagues, muddled undertaking proprietorship and dynamic cycles, deceptive responsibilities which lead to unreasonable outcomes; and staff clashes and helpless correspondence.

It significant that innovation is “an indispensable piece of any of these three risk gatherings. Just in the last gathering, being a lack of information, innovation is the real issue, precisely as a result of inadequate preparing. This issue could cause accidental issues, for example, helpless appreciation of methods, instruments and strategies. In addition, the specialists of the projects who are not expert in the issue referred to above may meet with issues concerning inadequate involvement with the field of use scope making associations which wear "the need of the client. While, The (PMI, 2004) arranged risks in four gatherings, which are

authoritative risks, specialized risks, outer risks, and project related risks (abbreviated as TOPE chances).

As indicated by (Tang, 2007), the five most vital project risks are "low quality of work," "untimely disappointment of the office," "security," "deficient or wrong plan," and "monetary risk/danger."

There are numerous categories of risk identified which are distributed in many events (Raftery, 2003). The distribution in categories is according to their attribute and sensitivity. Risk can be classified as short term risks and long terms risks, short term are those which will affect the current productivity of a project, and long term is those who will develop with time and can cause uncertainty in future (Jayasudha, 2016). Types of risk in a project are categorised as follow:

TYPES OF RISK	UNCERTAINTIES
Design risks	Change in Design, Design delays, changes and mistakes in designs, sketchy details, incomplete specifications, and uncertainty due to different site conditions.
Construction risks	Health and safety, quality control, site access, accidents, machinery failure, labour shortage/absent, inadequate equipment, the productivity of equipment, labour strike.
Financial & economical risks	Cash flow inadequacy, payment delays, wrong estimates of price, the extra cost of planning delays, Changes in legislations, abiding laws, fluctuation in trade rate/price.
Political risks	Change of government, Political parties disputes, sectorial conflicts, foreign forces pressure, disputes between the federal and provincial government, growth in authorities.
Legal and regulatory risks	Currency rate uncertainty, Inflation/deflation; Price/cost fluctuation, Import restrictions/taxes, unusual permit and license delays, complicated/unstable tax procedure;
Sub-contractor risks	Reduced workmanship, lack of skilled labour, lack of specialization, unlawful construction methods, subcontractor failure, and subcontractor bankruptcy.
Environmental risks	Ecological damage, air/water pollution, waste management, recycling or material and waste disposal.

Table 2.2: Sub Categories/Types of Risks

2.9 Risk Management Process in the Global Construction Industry

Risk Management has a direct relation to the successful completion of a project. There are several risk management definitions in the project management literature; the most widely accepted risk management process consists of four steps: risk identification, risk assessment, risk response construction, and risk response control (Jayasudha, 2016). The process includes the minimization of adverse events which would affect the completion date or cost overrun mainly (Ehsan, 2015). The risk management process is depicted in the figure below:

Figure 2.5: *Risk Management Process in Construction Industry (Skorupka, 2003)*

2.10 Risk Management Process Applied in the UK Construction Industry

Overall the risk management in the UK construction industry has a mature process and implementation on a large scale. In contrast, SME's are still struggling, relying on qualitative techniques and lessons learned in previous projects (Rostami, 2016). Analyst company Trimetric (2015) has drawn up its annual construction risk index and has discovered that the UK is now fifth least likely in Europe to experience significant disruption and tenth least likely globally. The formal risk management process in the UK construction industry is illustrated in the following figure:

Figure 2.6 : Risk Management Process in the UK Construction Industry (IRM, 2002)

2.11 Barriers of Implement Risk Management Globally

Lue (2017) in their examination about key issues and difficulties of risk management in China's construction industry recognized that the most unmistakable boundary of improvement of risk management is the unsupportive culture inside the business.

There is an overall hesitance for execution of risk management in the China's construction industry because of an absence of involvement acquired from the consequences of the examination. Absence of involvement causes contractual workers not to recognize the significant issues and points of interest of risk management. Changing the way of life of big business could be the way that can improve the basic comprehension of risks. It is fundamental for Chinese contractual workers to concur with the risk management "idea just as execute risk management procedures. The main issue influencing the improvement of risk management in the Chinese construction industry is the experts" conduct. The huge component of a consolidated risk management cycle will be authoritative picking up, being the learning cycle shaped to help Chinese contractual workers in planning their presentation and information towards risk management. The imperative issue for Chinese contractual workers to fabricate their desire is to change present day skill as indicated by their agreement utilizing hierarchical learning.

Hlaing, (2018) in their examination relating impression of Singapore construction contractual workers on construction risk distinguishing proof kept up that among the issues keeping the execution of the risk management cycle, cash is definitely not a considerable requirement for actualizing risk management cycle for the organizations, while deficiency of time flaunting generally significant in the rundown. (MacLeod, Akintoye, 1997; Skitmore, Lyons, 2004) distinguished limitation of time as principle imperative. The exercises of the construction Industry are confined by time since the introduction of construction is essentially utilized without a moment to spare for the production need of the client. The reactions to the models for overseeing risks notice the construction industry has generally restricted the risks.

The risk treatment procedures can be masterminded dependent on risk reduction, risk transfer, risk avoidance and risk retention. In light of their examination, not only one feature is ruling as reactions in investigation for entire variables fall fairly unmistakable as well as essential aside from component absence acknowledged by investigation model for industry, that was appraised most minimal significance. (Price, Baloi, 2003) likewise examined that despite the fact that there are brags in the strategies of risk management and accessibility of the enormous assortment of information on risk management, it looks that experts have not only perceived the estimation of risk management.

They perceived language, usage costs, and instructive obstructions and a dread of progress to be the foremost boundaries of the proficient conformance. Tang (2007) ordered in investigation in the Chinese Construction Industry about Risk Management that the boundaries of risk management in eleven variables, three out of them establish main three obstructions to risk management that is “Absence of combined risk management systems by parties” lack of information/procedures on risk management, and diverse acknowledgement of risk

2.12 Risk Management in Developed Economies

Processes on managing risks are formed and implemented in developed nations so it is applied more efficiently over there. UK is a developed country if we compare it with other situations then it will come to know that the business environment, regulations and laws made risk more often to occur in a project. Following are some details of developed countries practices.

2.12.1 US Construction Industry

A survey was conducted in which the attitude of large U.S. construction firms towards risk was concluded and determined how these contractors perform construction risk management. The survey was constructed for the top 100 large U.S. engineers. The results were then compared with the risk survey carried out by ASCE. The comparison depicted that in past years, the companies have more emphasised of sharing contractual and legal risks with the owners from the beginning. These risks include the change in specifications, third party delays, contractual delays and other risks. The survey also demonstrated that engineers are only assuming the risks associated with the actual quantity of work, which is not in contradiction to ASCE findings.

Moreover, contractors were found to be very cautious about suggesting alternative options to the client. This was significant, as no previous survey has addressed or sought to quantify allocation or importance of this task. (Kangari, 1995).

Another survey was conducted to develop a risk management model for Florida Construction industry, which suggested that effective and efficient handling and the remedy of risk in a formal systematic manner, is a modernistic concept to the construction industry which is rapidly becoming significant (Ahmed, 2011).

2.12.2 Construction Industry by Chinese

Conducted research, as well as this study aims to reveal the status of the risk management practice in the Chinese construction industry. The critical discoveries of this examination incorporate (Tang, 2009): The five most pivotal undertaking risks are bad quality of work, untimely disappointment of the office, security, deficient or inaccurate plan and monetary risk. The most unmistakable risks included are quality control, office disappointments, deficient details and plan mistakes, and monetary risks. Qualitative risk assessments techniques are famous in the industry as its application does not require a specialised person. More importantly, risk management is considered on all projects levels and sizes. The risk is managed with an informal system of risk management, which is not adequate and a threat to the construction industry. There is no agreement on any formal methods of risk identification, assessment, and accepting the liability of risks; they are not documented. Clients tend to avoid risk, and contracts transfer the risks by insuring them. The major risk management strategy can be named as reducing risks process used in the TGP (The Three Gorges Project

known as largest hydropower project in China. This *technique perceives the intelligence of the analyst, how aware he is of risks and events which could affect the construction project.

2.12.3 Australian Construction Industry

A review was directed by the top counselling firm in Queensland construction industry Australia, focusing on senior administration faculty to assess the utilization of risk management methods. Moreover, these outcomes were contrasted and the other four studies directed in created economies which demonstrated that the utilization of risk management is all the more frequently, it is considered from arranging till the closeout of the project, regardless of the size of the organization or the task (Luons, 2004). The regularly utilized risk distinguishing proof procedures are past undertaking record, conceptualizing, and for risk evaluation, subjective techniques are utilized, which are risk decrease and risk protection.

2.13 Risk Management In Developing Economies

Construction industries are facing rapid changes in developing economies as well; they are fully aware that construction industries drive mostly developed economies. Rapid changes give birth to more risk and exposure to new uncertainties, which can be hazardous if not recognised with time by managers which could affect their decision making. Risk management can provide better planning of cost and time. Developing countries like India, Hong Kong, Pakistan and Saudi Arabia are trying to contribute their best in application of risk managing strategies for their ongoing and future projects.

2.13.1 Indian Construction Industry

Risk management is not an old phenomenon in the Indian construction industries. Formal risk management practices are missing, lack of knowledge and expertise is required to formalise the process. The government projects are dealt on a risk rating system which the government has issued for all the public projects to assist rapid decision making. This will encourage engineers to make a strategy to deal with risks and will promote the rust in public-private partnership projects in the infrastructure sector. Moreover, financial institutions like banks and investment companies trust will boost in lending on government projects (Deviparasad, 2011).

2.13.2 Construction Industry of Hong Kong

Hong Kong construction industry is not that old story in recent decades; it has developed and still developing on a massive scale. They have a reputation for building high rise structure with value engineering designs and environment friendly. They lack training and knowledge of risk assessment and are still not emphasising to consider it as a constituent part of a project lifecycle (Shen, 2009). They are relying on their previous data records and making qualitative and subjective decisions.

A survey was conducted, and their findings were not significantly different from what is discussed above. It also concluded that the importance of the risk management process is not neglected. Still, there is a deficiency of professionals and understating of the process which should be taken into consideration seriously (HKTDC, 2011).

2.13.3 Pakistani Construction Industry

The Pakistani construction industry has transformed in the last decade and the pace of construction investment and construction in all the sectors which has made Pakistani construction industry one of its kind (Farooqui, 2018). The growth in private sector in residential and commercial by Bahria Town and Defence Housing Authority has changed the lifestyle and investment point of view of the general public. Whereas infrastructure and special construction sectors are led hand in hand with Chinese involvement through China Pakistan Economic Corridor project, which is going to lead to the construction industry to a new era of revolution for the people and country of Pakistan. Due to this significant growth in construction, construction industry lacks professional development and awareness of risk management procedures. Furthermore, there is no quantitative risk assessment tool adopted by the industry as yet; they are dealing risk with qualitative methods and experiences which is a significant threat at this stage (Farooqui, 2015).

The application of brainstorming and judgements techniques is widely used and seems to be effective in the past decade, but they have not enough depth to support the intense development ear. Due to this high volume of changes in the industry, contracts have become more aware of uncertainty and stakeholders' satisfaction, which is leading to adopting renown tools and formal risk management practices in the industry (Ali, 2007).

2.13.4 Saudi Arabian Construction Industry

Risk assessment is a new concept to the construction contractors in Saudi Arabia. A survey was conducted about the effectiveness of the risk management process between main engineers, and it illustrated that risk allocation. Establishment awareness is getting developed over here in this part of the globe (Salman, 2005). The practice of risk allocation after they are identified is different in this region, as the client accepts no risk liability and all to be transferred to the contractor. The complicated weather conditions make it challenging to keep a sustainable quality which is the most critical risk. The general perception of contracts was to allow them to share the risk with clients or some additional cost is added to cater to the deals all risks insurance.

2.14 Comparison of Risk Management in Construction Industry with Other industries

Construction is not the only industry where there are risks; every industry has their own risk, which are critical to be analysed. A few of the sectors are detailed below.

2.14.1 Transportation

The present perpetually changing business world becomes unpredictable, sporadic and more convoluted each day. Incorporated Europe unites with transport improvement additionally more prominent business, makes longer conveyed removes and empowers more noteworthy exhibitions. Transport organizations can execute their business thoughts, uphold their viable and acquire a gainful situation available. Simultaneously, these organizations, that have a focal job in monetary exercises need to confront new risk ranges and wrestle with the adjustments achieved by a post-down economy. Albeit truly, the business has considered risks as a fundamental insidious that ought to be conveyed or moderated, present day risk management construction give components that aside from recognizable proof of risks setting up potential entanglements additionally distinguish chances that bring openings.

Risk management is credible in transportation strategic approaches (*see figure 1*). Transportation offices set more significant bodies and targets (e.g., the dependable and powerful development of individuals and products), however achievement is dubious. Inner and outer risk occasions can strike the achievement of these targets. In like manner, offices set execution gauges and emerge resource the executives frameworks to means venture choices. Once more, risks can influence the accomplishment of execution and resources. It is

true on transportation offices to detail denotative venture risk management techniques, strategies, and devices.

Figure 2.7: Risk Triangle in Transportation (Flare, 2019)

The conspicuous global transportation offices have adult risk management rehearses and have planned arrangements and techniques to distinguish, survey, oversee, and screen risks. According to transportation risk management in US, from May 29 to June 11, 2011, a group of Federal, State, and public area experts visited Australia, England, Germany, the Netherlands, and Scotland to distinguish risk management rehearses. An outline of the group's decisions incorporates the accompanying:

Risk management benchmarks key authoritative arrangement. Risk based resource management develops project choices.

- An expansive scope of risk management apparatuses can improve exhibitions.
- Participating in risk correspondence systems improve dynamic.
- Mature associations have an express risk management structure.
- Leading associations have a culture of risk management set up.
- Risk management improves information the board and labor force advancement.

2.14.2 Aviation

Different set of business demands and risks are faced by airlines, remoulded marketplace by new entrants, carriers of state-owned, shifting preferences of consumer and new economic

conditions developing on. Whether executives have pertained about possible hacking and security violations, third-party disruptions or supply-chain or, one factor always remains constant: risk of aviation is evolving, the need is to improve the mitigation risks and to an age them by airlines. If we go thorough historic details then we come to know that aviation industry has done extraordinary measures to manage the operations and to cope with the risks including security and safety. Confidence of traveller always hit high but today the aviation industry bit in suffering due to variation in terms of risks in different dimensions.

Figure 2.8: Key Financials Airline Industry (Zach Investment Research, 2014)

What's more, complexity, emerging nature, and risk sources portray that every risk is not formed equally (Delloite. 2015). Therefore, broad-based risk management strategies orthodox, must be followed to derive a profound view of strategy that would be industry-centric, targeted and cost-effective. Implemented accurately, a winning differentiator for airlines can be a well-articulated risk management method, based on (ROI) return on investment with the support of proactive infrastructure. To be useful, this current tactic risk management ought to be the utmost precedence.

Following are the three significantly threatened and unpredictable areas that become a cause to damage the aviation industry. Data breaches and Cyber incidents, the risk from within insider threats, third-party and vendor threats, disruption of supply chain.

Vulnerability of Cyber Breach

The carrier business is rising over with information and regularly interlinking informational collections, including traveller information, which widens from booking to taking care of things to addressing criticism of post-flight as well as functional information, wanders from

airplane devices from climate offices to GPS frameworks. Advanced airplane, which are currently coming in the creation lines, permit transporters to appreciate associated gadgets to pick up effectiveness along the inventory network, from altering flight execution to overseeing drink orders. Not exclusively do airplane motors presently suitable for far off observing and utilization charging models, the biometrics of each traveler before long might be gathered, put away, positioned, investigated, and repackaged to ensured benefit. This information can improve things, proficiency, and business execution. With heaps of information accompanies new travellers, bunches of risks are additionally invited. From reservations to support to flight the board, business flying depends on secure data innovation frameworks.

In this manner, while evaluating future tech projects, carrier industry security experts and chiefs should respect all types of network safety risks that definitely accompany such advancement. From this good point, will be set up to coordinate risk alleviation systems right off the bat in the arranging and direction.

The aircraft business may participate in a scope of acts that incorporate working environment viciousness, infiltration of data, actual security bargain, damage, illegal intimidation, and actual property robbery, summarizing all can bring about security unpredictability (Delloite. 2015).

Easy Entry or Easy Troubles in the Airline Industry

As indicated by financial hypotheses of the aeronautics business, for example, that of Salop (1979), there is a base number of passages that segments the two points of interest (improving the assortment of items) and burdens (creating section costs). For our situation, raising the quantity of passages has various advantages that can pick up the opportunity of substitutable flights being accessible. In any case, as Salop (1979) discovered, it hoists all out section costs. Accordingly, a lower number of sections exists in the aircraft business. Numerous past investigations about accessible financial models, with Salop (1979), summed up the passages quantity in the simple business sectors surpasses the lower level regarding social government assistance for instance, (Whinston, Mankiw, 1986); Kiyono, Suzumura, 1987; Fujiwara, Suzumura 1993; Ghosh, Saha, 2017). Also, Matsumura & Okamura (2006) portrayed the lacking section circumstance happens when the disutility (transportation cost) work is sunken plus fringy creation is an intensifying capacity of the assortment of yields. Another

illustration of the horrible section case is given by Ghosh and Morita (2007). They discussed that the insufficient passage case happens when there are providers of normal items that have high haggling capacity to finish up the assignment of advantages among makers and providers.

A significant piece of doing risk management is planning ideal alternatives on account of mishaps. For instance, if few travellers can't take their flights on account of motor difficulty or for another explanation, they will load up on one more trip at an offered time to a similar objective. Nonetheless, especially for worldwide flights, there are less flights. For instance, a departure from Sydney (Australia) to Narita (Japan). As of September 2008, there are just two carriers that fly the immediate course: Qantas and Japan Airlines. Consequently, if of them is missed or dropped because of some specialized issue, the travellers should hold back to load up a next Qantas or Japan Airlines flight. As there are not many booked flights, travellers see the greater risk of failing to catch their planes and unfit to arrive at their last objective as arranged. This risk is almost identified with the benefit of aircraft since they should remunerate travellers for convenience and dinner costs. The more aircrafts there are on a similar course, the lower is the risk of the present circumstance. Thinking about the present circumstance, numerous carriers entering the business might be alluring as far as risk management. Also, it is delicate to envision critical passage costs when various aircrafts enter.

Recent Trends of Risk Exposure with Innovation

The aeronautics business' future keeps on being redeveloped by new contenders, for instance, super ease traveller flights, and state-possessed flights combined with creating industry structures and conveying financial conditions. Client decisions are changing, socioeconomics are changing, and the business is countering innovation driven production network disturbance. Previously, associations were reliant on endeavours to order unique risk measure into an "venture" audit of risk with separating levels of progress. Risk management firms tend to check the record in the back view reflect, regularly not fruitful to consider disturbance and the likely issues of hard to distinguish chances and new risks that can either harm vital worth or, alternately, present new income openings. Considering the gigantic expenses contributed via carriers to oversee risk (e.g., life series the board & protection), an extra outcome orientated as well as future-wandering methodology towards distinguishing vital risk drivers that acknowledge the extraordinary idea of the business ought to be thought of,

created, and sent. A definition that not just requires distinguishing instruments that plan for shocks yet a center program that gives top initiative a more extensive perspective on past risks that may have been unloaded in the records of an association.

Successful Strategic Risk Management

The top aircrafts will detect those impromptu occasions will rapidly reshape their organizations. They will understand the requirement for executing vital risk management, applying imaginative reasoning, and employing master accomplices at the applicable hierarchical level. To summarize, their essential risk projects will: Adjust vital destinations, ingested, and risk measures, acquire an endeavour viewpoint that goes across the firm, practice administration and regulate that interface into the board, consider that risks are inward and outer and that vulnerable sides and inclinations can obstruct experiences, using reproduction procedures that search for uproar from startling spots, assert dynamic and progressing information gathering, investigation, and representation.

2.14.2.1 Risk Management Practice of Major International Airlines

a) ACE Aviation Holding Inc- Air Canada:

Pro Aviation is holding Inc. Is the chief holding organization, offering transportations promotion different administrations through top controlling organizations or associations with Canada Air, Partnership of : AC Cargo Limited, ACTS Limited, ACGHS Limited, Aeroplan Limited, Touram Limited (Air Canada Vacations) and Jazz Air LP..

Canada Air is one of the utmost help breadwinner in Canadian homegrown as well as worldwide, Europe, North America, Caribbean, Pacific, South America and Central America market during 2016. It shipped 190 objections all through the five landmasses doing non-stop flights, and business arrangements were made for certain provincial aircrafts.

The organization utilizes monetary subsidiaries to deal with its openness to stream fuel value changes, loan fee and unfamiliar trade rates changes. To withdraw its loan cost risk vital in the US and Canadian skimming rate obligation and venture, the organization shows sending loan fee concurrences with developments of close to year and a half. Unfamiliar trade risk eccentricism is overseen by going into unfamiliar trade forward agreements and money trades. In the end of fiscal year, the organization gone through unfamiliar money onward

agreements as well as alternative arrangements having worth of US\$821 during its 2016 buys.

Organizational transient speculations are made sure about with enormous monetary establishments, Canadian governments and significant partnerships and hence don't unveil the organization to gigantic credit risk.

b) AMR Corporation -- Airlines of America

Airlines Inc of America is a parent auxiliary of AMR Corporation. America's essential help is booked traveller administrations followed by cargo and mail administrations. American Airlines flies to 15 objections all through North America, Latin America, Caribbean, Asia and Europe. In the direction of defeat the expense of fuel, the organization go into stream fuel, unrefined petroleum and warming oil supporting agreements with developments of close to two years. In 2016, fuel cost was 28% of all out costs. Toward the end o December 31, 2016, 2015 and 2014 the all out fuel expenses would have been \$6785 million, \$ 5657 million and \$ 5001 million individually. The supporting arrangements set up guaranteed in increases adding up \$64 million (1.13%), \$1149 million(5.10%) and \$99 million (2.43%) aimed at similar particular years.

Unfamiliar trade risk roots from the organization having costs and incomes in unfamiliar cash sections especially, Euro, British Pound, Japanese Yen, Canadian Dollar and different Latin American monetary standards with variances in swapping scale influence the USD estimation for such costs& incomes.

Loan fee risk is a risk to the organizations transient ventures and variable rate obligation with rate of the variable obligation tools especially influenced by the change in London Interbank Offered Rate (LIBOR). Organizational discrepant degree obligation commitments represented 32% of the absolute obligation extraordinary.

c) British Airline

The organization oversees worldwide and home-grown planned and sanction trips to 160 objections in 75 nations conveying travellers, load and mail. A ton of the exchanges comes in unfamiliar monetary standards which make up an excess and accordingly however coordinating instalments and receipts of every money. All the unfamiliar money is changed

over into dollars or Sterling on the spot. One circumstance is the US dollar-designated exchanges where the costs each time go past the receipts in view of large thing instalments, for example, capital use, working fuel and lease buys made in USD. Onward unfamiliar trade contracts used to shelter the momentary upcoming incomes with costs in the direction of support alongside unfamiliar money changes. Organisations use their buys alternative under their rent plans and reimbursements of Yen ruled credits as a support to future Yen income being produced.

The organisation utilizes trade arrangements to bargain its inclinations rate weakness. The vast majority of the trade arrangements are developed into the rent and advance arrangements. As toward the finish of the 2016 monetary years, in the wake of thinking about the impacts of the trade arrangements, the amount of obligation through the fixed loan fee understanding remained 53%, where the amount of drifting degree based obligation remained 47%.

The fuel represents 21% of absolute working costs and quite possibly the super costly thing. Fuel value risk is fence utilizing monetary and ware instruments, for example, trades, prospects, advances, choices and collars. For financial year the organization benefitted by of £303 million through supporting agreements, which mirror a 16% advantage. Toward the finish of the duty year, the carrier's fuel risk the board program had supported adjusts of its normal fuel utilization, with fuel agreements of construction as long as two years.

2.14.3 Nuclear Power

According to Acute Market Research, the Global Nuclear Power market is valued at 400GW with annual growth of 4%, and it is expected to reach 694GW by 2022. Seeking to mitigate the environmental impact of greenhouse gas emissions from the combustion of fossil fuels, many nations are turning to nuclear power. However, potentially strong growth is being inhibited by concerns about safety, the risk of future incidents and the enormous costs of storing and monitoring radioactive waste.

Preferably, risk management is to be made the core of every business strategy for organizations working in the industry of waste and nuclear. However, the nuclear industry is different in some of the demands facing it.

If we start with the extreme timeframes we work to; effectively, our industry lifecycle spans decades. Already this complicates the decision-making process and sets the scene around the scope of risk that organizations need to factor into their management approach. For example, horizon scanning becomes necessary, considering threats such as catastrophic terrorism, cyber-crime as well as those posed by the natural world like earthquakes. We're contending with such huge risks – climate change and how this affects rising sea levels – that risk takes on an enormous role.

The Regulations of Industrial Risk

The significant tests that are done in directing modern risks are almost equivalent to those we use in regular day to day existence. They include processing: regardless of whether a managed the cost of risk is so gigantic or the outcome so unsatisfactory that it should be dismissed out and out; or whether the risk is, or has been made, minor to such an extent that no further consideration is required; or if a risk lies between these two expresses, that it has been chopped down to the most minimal level accessible, maintaining as a primary concern the preferences moving from its appropriation and considering into account the expenses of any further decrease.

2.14.3.1 Few Major Risks and their Management in Nuclear Industry

Licensing:

In the business of atomic establishments, the fundamental instrument for practicing these standards is the site permit which is allowed just when NII is content with the plan security of the plant. The contemplations which are vital to every task empower NII after that to regulate progress in consenting to security necessities at each phase of construction, charging and activity. The conditions which can be appended include:

(a) assents, licenses are reliant on the endorsement of NII

(b) endorsements,

the licensee is expected to expand the overall measures for doing explicit exercises and acquire NII's authorization; and

(c) power to give bearings whereby the licensee is approached to make any move which NII thinks about essential.

Individual Risks:

Whenever we are thinking about the opportunity of an enormous scope mechanical mishap, the basic inquiry for every individual is, what is the risk to my family and me? The manner in which this is replied in risk assessment is to compute the risk to any person who lives inside a specific separation from a plant; or who follows a particular example of life that may expose that person to the outcomes of a mishap.

As indicated by the various types of risk for which counts are made, there are different potential manners by which individuals may be harmed. They may kick the bucket pretty much instantaneously from the impacts of blasts, fire or poisonous gas discharge. Radiation is an alternate case, since except if the portion is broad passing inside half a month or even years would be impossible.

The damage from radiation is the main risk from atomic establishments concerns the potential for arrival of material which produces ionizing radiations. There are some other human-made sources, for example, clinical x-beam hardware, and there are characteristic sources. Coming up next is an improved record of what is thought about the damage from radiation; for different adaptations, the peruse ought to counsel the further understanding segments.

All radioactive materials rot and at last become stable, losing the unsafe attributes of their unique radioactivity. Notwithstanding, the rate at which various types of radioactive material rot fluctuates hugely. So when radioactive materials enter the body, some of them will become innocuous rapidly except if they are constantly supplanted.

Brief About the UK Nuclear Industry

The UK is a worldwide pioneer in the atomic business; it required 60 years for them to pick up this position. The UK had a prospering atomic industry since the 1950s when the world's first business atomic force station was shaped in Cumbria. These days, the UK broadens their capacity and aptitude across the whole atomic life cycle, from the plan of another plant to decommissioning and waste administration. Atomic industry in UK workers in excess of

60,000 talented experts, with a one-directional spotlight on security and quality, according to International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) the UK is the best option on the planet to accomplice in atomic energy improvements around the globe.

2.14.4 Automobile

This is a very much evolved area around the globe that is encountering a renaissance as it salvages answers for a few construction drove difficulties, including the cutting of CO2 discharges; advanced availability; computerization; and worldwide development.

The essentials of the UK's assembling industry; the car business make 1.57 million traveller vehicles in 2017, which is required to increment by 6% in 2018 with new models, for example, the Jaguar XE being dispatched as assessed by the Society of Motor Manufacturers and Traders (SMMT). Six of the huge vehicle organizations delivering vehicles in Britain (otherwise called unique gear makers, or OEMs) have expected to put further in their UK plants. Over the most recent five years, £10bn has been certified by Jaguar Land Rover alone. Nonetheless, an absence of certainty further down the store network is as yet keeping a few organizations from contributing.

Additionally, the most basic risk in automotive industry the risk business property to the current expansion and Brexit issues. Supporting rates is the best model between US dollars against British pound around 60% and supporting rates between Japanese Yen.

2.15 Introduction of SME's

This chapter complies to review previous knowledge and research in the area of risk management and SME's in the construction industry and compile all relevant information and current practices.

2.15.1 Definition of SME's

In General, there is no accepted unique definition of SMEs (Hooj, G. 2006, Omer, F and Ismail, A. 2009). The geographical placement of SMEs, as well as country-specific legislation, influences the numerous SME definitions (Leopoulos, 2006).

Little and medium-sized ventures (SMEs) in the construction area are bargaining and face weakness to risks while working without risk management framework set up. The statistical

surveying and industry reviews establish that SMEs fail to meet expectations due to inability to oversee operational risk requests confronting them. The target of this examination is to build up a risk management system in the construction area for SME's to proactively recognize, break down and oversee chances confronting them to improve business and industry execution.

A World Bank study, performed by a distribution known as MSMB Country Indicators confirms that out of 132 nations shrouded in the review, 46 of them or a third think about SMEs as organizations with less than 250 workers (Kushnir et al.: 2010). 'The vast majority of projects is a SME, and SMEs make two out of each three positions' (Cela, Furthermore, Alda, 2015). The greatest number of sources says that SMEs to have a removed a scope of 0-250 representatives (Ayyagari, 2003). There have been a ton of distributions on the right and exact meanings of SME's. The OECD predicts that little and medium projects represent 90% of risks and utilize 63% of the labor force on the planet (Munro, 2013). Besides, in one of the reports distributed by European Commission portrays that the European Union Standard definition for SMEs is any business with less than 250 representatives and a turnover of as much as 50 million Euros and a monetary record of around 43 million Euros (Benjamin, 2013).

2.15.1.1 Definition of Risk in SMEs

Risk has many definitions, the most commonly accepted and used definition relates the risk to the negative events, or a possibility of occurrence of a negative event. Risk is everywhere, it is present in every activity or sector. Every sector has different techniques of quantifying risks, but its basics remain same which are its probability and occurrence.

2.15.2 Importance of SME's in Economic Growth

The SMEs make an enormous commitment to the economies of both created and agricultural nations, regarding employability and advancement impacts. The European Union Commission Report (2005) confirms that SMEs contribute dramatically to the economy of Europe; 99% of all organizations are SMEs, and representative around 75 million positions, and in couple of businesses like in material, construction and furniture, they represent 80% of the work (European Commission, 2005). Princic (2014) reports portrays that the SMEs involves around 90% of UK business and utilize practically 50% of the UK labor force

2.15.3 Contribution of SME's in the Construction Industry of UK

In 2014 the construction industry in the UK contributed £103 billion to the absolute monetary yield, 6.5% of the total. 2.1 million positions or 6.2% of the UK all out were in the construction industry in 2015 (Rhodes, 2015). Alliance of Master Builders (FMB, 2013) gave a report on private area organizations where they exhibits that SMEs contracts are worth nearly £37bn every year which is an astounding 38% of all UK construction yield.

construction SMEs represents a fundamental piece of these business conditions as it claims the duty of most huge scope activities and minor works that are re-evaluated in common works and building recovery and change (Canamares, 2017).

Construction projects are thought to be the accomplishment of the projected target, which includes a progression of exercises and assignments that use assets (Parvan, 2015). The construction area holds a turn place on the planet's economy, which a general public accomplishes its objectives of metropolitan and provincial turn of events (Enshassi, 2006).

One important move of the construction industry is the SME's. Construction recorded a healthy growth of 15.3 %, while SME grew at 6 % in 2015 (Myers, 2015). Every project has a prime contractor who generally subcontracts the specialised works to subcontractors who are mainly SME's contributing to the construction industry and economy directly.

2.15.4 Relation of Risk Management with SME's

As per OECD (2005) about 99 % organizations in the developed countries are SMEs and has a significant proportion in the construction industry of UK (BIS, 2013). Risk is an integral part of any activity, so its management is mandatory, either before or in case of emergency. Whereas construction is a booming industry of any economy, rapidly growing businesses make a pivotal contribution to employment growth as well. However, SME's in the construction industry, which is financial institutions usually perceive fast-growing companies as riskier than the "typical" SME (OCED, 2014). They are using technologies, handling finance on a project basis, it takes courage to maintain rolling and allocation of funds in all the projects equally, which expose them to all sort of right risk categories which have been discussed above.

2.15.5 Challenges faced by Organizations/SMEs

External and internal factors are the primary reason where companies struggle to implement and manage the risk management process. Occasionally the resistance is from inside the organizations, either from senior management or from employees who are not accepting to adapt the extra effort to analyse situations critically which are for their benefit (IRM, 2013). Moreover, sometimes the risk culture is not familiar to risk management to allow its implementation.

There is tremendous proof both from casual statistical surveying and industry studies to guarantee that SMEs are as often as possible impeded and thusly failing to meet expectations because of their failure to oversee operational risk challenges confronting them every day.

2.15.6 Implementation of Risk Managing methods in Organisations Culture and Maturity

Management of Risk is a part of organisational culture, it is not just a process, and people have to accept it with maturity. Institute of risk management (2013), in their report, suggests that the risk management process has to have a proper environment, which SME's lack mostly. To draw the optimised results, it is necessary to raise the risk maturity conversation levels in an organisation. The best example around is of London Olympics 2012 project, where discussions were open, transparent and mature, good working relationships, intent to learn, a better understanding of programme management and project, above all, exceptional people (IRM, 2013).

2.15.7 Risk Management Technical and Traditional Approach

Risk management process is based on its four steps which prove to be logical in any sense; parameters do change project to project to calculate the impact accordingly. Moreover, there is another approach which is not rational but traditional, in which a particular cost of uncertainty is added at a fixed rate to the total cost of the project which is known as conventional deterministic approach (TDA). Analyst Rasheed (2005) was the first to compare both the policies on a practical project and discovered that decisions made on the risk management process (RPM) are more technical and tangible. In contrast, TDA was inadequate and didn't meet the target cost.

SMEs and contracting tiers

The UK branch of business and construction communicated in their report (2013) that specific interest in conceivable monetary issues influencing SMEs in construction. The piece of SMEs in all out construction yield is generally high. SMEs are characterized by the EU as far as numbers utilized and afterward either deals or resources along these lines:

1. Micro firms: have less than 10; deals under 2m Euros or resources under 2m Euros
2. Small firms: utilize at least ten however less than 50; deals of 2m Euros or more yet under 10m Euros or resources of 2m Euros or more yet under 10m Euros
3. Medium firms: utilize somewhere in the range of 50 and 249; deals more prominent than 10m yet under 50m Euros or resources more noteworthy than 10m however under 43m Euros The Companies Act applies a marginally unique meaning of 'little', given beneath. Additionally, the EU size limits don't exactly line up with those utilized in Construction Statistics, 2019,

Consequently, the term 'micro organization' is utilized to show to organizations utilizing 13 or less individuals, or with absolute resources beneath £2m. The term 'little firm' is utilized in differentiation to the miniature firm, it alludes to utilizing individuals somewhere in the range of 14 and 50 or (in setting of 'Development Statistics' information); in the feeling of the Companies Act, to notices to both little firms in the above categorisation and furthermore miniature firms The setting should feature which of these feelings of 'little firm' applies at each spot in the content. The term 'SME' is utilized to allude to all organizations with less than either 250 or (in setting of 'Development Statistics' information) 300 representatives and with absolute resources under £40m It isn't practicable to break down the records of all 'little' measured firms (regarding the Companies Act 2006, presently firms falling beneath in any event two of the accompanying edges: turnover of under £6.5m; resources under £3.26m; utilizing under 50 people - up to this point, turnover under £5.6m, resources under £2.8m) in light of the fact that they are not needed to report full records, including a benefit and misfortune account, to Companies House. A sub-set of the number of inhabitants in little firms do document full records, however its absolutely impossible of deciding if they are illustrative individuals of little firms. Regardless, for firms with insignificant capital, regardless of whether they do decide to document full records, the differentiation between the proprietor's pay and resources and those of the organization may by and by not be sharp. For instance, advances to or from chiefs may overwhelm the accounting report, and working

excess can be 'taken' as benefit or as chiefs' compensation. We, along these lines, chosen we had no choice except for to prohibit firms with deals of under £1m in any one year of the period investigated from our examination. By and by, this rejects most firms with five or less representatives, and a few firms are utilizing more than 5. Nonetheless, it leaves possibly inside our example the sub-set of little firms with deals somewhere in the range of £1m and £6.5m that decided to record full records.

Most business exercises inside business tasks are associated in Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). For instance, in the United Kingdom, it is dictated by the Department for Business Innovation and Skills (2015) that Small organizations represented 99.3% of all private area organizations toward the beginning of 2015 and 99.9% were small or medium-sized (SMEs).

Small and Medium-Sized Companies (SMEs) Expose to risk

The supposition of organization disappointment is a huge and testing worry for the two analysts and professionals. Destruction of an organization may make outstanding misfortunes the business network and furthermore to society. It will concern different partners, for example, speculators, leasers, investors or representatives. Safeguarding the organization disappointment underscores the noteworthiness of building up a powerful model that will permit the early worry of potential organization disappointment before it occurs.

The construction Industry (CI) has various qualities that may hoist the weakness of organizations to chapter 11 contrasted with different areas. Normal attributes incorporate the accompanying: Implementation of activities which has a ton of vulnerability about completing on schedule, time invade is associated with late venture finishing, difficulty of construction cycle, partnering and store network issues concerning various partners, uncertainty and risk engaged with the construction movement.

2.15.8 Risk Management Tools and Techniques Used Locally in SME's

The difficulty in adopting a relaxing method that can improve the RM procedure to obtain the objectives of the organization is also a big major problem in RM (Rostami, 2015). Furthermore, limited profitability and budget of the SME's towards training and development of risk management also play a vital role where managers and experience are termed as the best tool for risk management without considering the intensity and probability of

uncertainty. Most SME's use lessons learned on previous projects as a tool to mitigate the risk in future projects (Parangamage, 2012). Qualitative techniques are used mostly by the companies which include Professional judgement, brainstorming, sensitivity analysis simulation etc. (Jackson, 2015).

The consortium behind RiMaCon recognized a critical imperfection between the accessible risk management techniques and their useful and effective usage by SMEs in the construction area. It was discovered (Rostami, 2015) that there was no hearty risk the board framework accessible for helpful reception or application by SMEs and that current risk management frameworks are used uniquely for impromptu appraisal as opposed to for the constant assessment, observing and survey.

2.15.9 Training on Handling Risk Management Process in SME's

The power of getting profits by RM is associated with the experts' quantitative foundations and their competency to decipher and apply RM measure inside associations (Wood, Ellis, 2003). Instruction and preparing as two basic components makes a huge job in the advancement of experts' capacity inside associations. Experts in construction associations use schooling and preparing to top off the hole among hypothesis and practice in RM (Akintoye, MacLeod, 1997).

Proficient bodies have generally clarified the hypothesis and cycles of risk management and in its idea; notwithstanding, none of these have been tended to the central standards of using the way to deal with the circumstance that little and medium-sized projects end up in (APM, 2010). Cases show that preparation projects to help risk management usage and its proceeded with useful associations are deficient for SMEs. Not many preparing programs exist in the territory of risk management that thinks about the experts' size and capacity; and most instructional classes consider risk management rehearses in huge undertakings with less regard for SMEs' trademark. (Rostami, 2015)

An audit of the writing on RM in the construction Industry features three huge obstructions to preparing (Akintoye, MacLeod, 1997; Chileshe, Kikwasi, 2013). The main hindrance is associated with monetary assets for preparing programs. The second is the inaccessibility of sufficient assets to run preparing programs. What's more, the third is the time imperative for individuals need to go to the preparation programs. Numerous SMEs, because of their qualities, bear from assets limitation as well as from the inaccessibility to complete preparing

programs, notwithstanding there is an importance for starting, arranging and executing the preparation. Wood and Ellis (2003) additionally featured that there is restricted proof of representatives doing preparing on formal RM. Subsequently, there is a tremendous prerequisite for preparing for RM in SMEs in the construction Industry.

Risk management usage inside SMEs is a complex and cash burning-through movement. It requires a full thought of the authoritative inclusion, including the arrangement of the executives; the degree of assets; the level of representatives' information; and destinations of the association. In SMEs, the program of riskmanagement ought to manage more on establishing the learning climate that underpins workers to improve profitability by limiting the risks of exercises.

2.16 Construction Industry, Brexit and SMEs

The 'Vulnerability Shock' and 'No Deal' is probably going to proceed all through arrangement for Brexit, recommending a plunge and shortening in the construction of GDP of UK. An England based risk management firm THSP (2016) showed in their report following focuses:

Construction industry improvement in 2016 has been anticipated at 2.1%; in any case, it seems like that this may drop in 2017 to a degree of 1.7%. The overall assessment is that we won't go into downturn again inside the following two years which can be considered currently to be 2020 as we are close to Brexit with a no arrangement.

More strategy facilitating is required to help spending, especially into lodging, as found in the Autumn Statement. There has been an ascent in arranging applications in 2016 for convenience and instructive foundations, which is by all accounts easing back somewhere near 2019.

The improvement of business space in London will stay solid in 2017/18 however is probably going to decay all through the remainder of the UK before the finish of 2020. There is a continuous 'mechanical turn of events' in coordination's space, which is foreseen to proceed into 2018.

The fundamental ends drawn from the report and the above assertions are that in 2017 we will see a general debilitating in construction project starts and yields by around - 4% contrasted with 2016, and it will additionally go downhill as we will arrive at Brexit.

London will keep on blasting, because of unfamiliar speculation and especially in reasonable and social lodging, training offices and business space, giving critical development to open doors for construction organizations here as lodging is consistently sought after. Monetary development in 2017 is foreseen to be moderate; notwithstanding, the typical cost for basic items increments are required to happen because of costly import obligations.

Monetary upgrades are foreseen for 2018, particularly in the Construction Industry, where construction is relied upon to be around 2.2%. Be that as it may, all plans are broken as COVID-19 has hindered the world economy.

2.17 Construction Industry and Covid 19 Impact

Coronavirus has significantly impacted all the industries, including construction in 2020; businesses across the country have stopped and nearly collapsed in a sudden pandemic.

The UK government has clear instructions about construction sites to continue their activities with all SOP's, but those are just relevant for infrastructure projects. Most of the private construction and financed projects are stopped at this point in time. The impact has been on staff presence, fear of coronavirus and less public transport for the construction workers to attend sites.

Construction line one of the accreditation organizations for contractor did a survey to identify the effects of coronavirus, they found that most of the sites are closed by main contractors due to unavailability of labour and workforce, Second most significant concern is that maintaining 2m distance is nearly impossible on working sites.

Another organization CIOB (Chartered Institute of Building) published their report in August 2020, which they have determined that construction activities have fallen by 2.6% in Q1 2020, and 9% in Q2 2020 and Q3 is predicted to achieve 20%.

There have been a lot of publications by the government to restart businesses, they have provided immense support to business in the form of BBL (Bounce Back Loan), Furlough Scheme and Business rates waving, but still, it's a global pandemic and it will take time to recover from it.

2.18 Types of Risk Management Frameworks

The strategic framework chosen will depend on the industry, business goals, organizational structure, technology infrastructure, and available resources. Some frameworks are more applicable to enterprise-scale businesses, while others provide more customizable, scenario-based approaches to an organization's specific RMF needs.

Following are some common risk management frameworks available in market, but they are not applicable or ideally designed for the SMEs in the UK construction industry

2.18.1 The Casualty Actuarial Society ERM Framework

The Casualty Actuarial Society (CAS) is an international credentialing and professional education entity. The organization focuses exclusively on property and casualty risks in insurance, reinsurance, finance, and enterprise risk management.

The CAS risk management process involves the following seven sequential steps:

1. **Establishing Context:** The first step is setting the context for risk based on how the organization currently operates. This step includes understanding internal and external context and ERM context (for example, danger to specific business units and the organization's environmental risk).
2. **Identifying Risks:** Document threats that prevent your organization from achieving its business objectives. This stage also encourages you to define how you might take advantage of risk to obtain a competitive advantage.
3. **Analyzing Risks:** In this step, analyze risk probability outcomes for each risk and quantify the impact.
4. **Integrating Risks:** In this step, aggregate risk distributions, considering correlations and the effects of risk on portfolios. Measure this stage by the impact to key performance indicators (KPIs).
5. **Prioritizing Risks:** Assess and prioritize each risk to determine how it adds to the aggregate ERM profile.
6. **Exploiting Risks:** This step requires developing strategies for using various risks to the organization's advantage.
7. **Monitoring Risks:** The last step focuses on performing continuous reviews of the risk environment and overall ERM performance.

The steps in the risk management process might apply to each risk individually.

2.18.2 The ISO 31000 ERM Framework

The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) 31000:2018 ERM framework is a cyclical risk management process that incorporates integrating, designing, implementing, evaluating, and improving the ERM process.

The ISO 31000 model is reviewed every five years to account for market evolution and changes to business complexity. This framework covers various risks and is customizable for organizations, regardless of size, industry, or sector.

2.18.3 The COBIT Risk Management Framework

COBIT (2019) is a flexible IT governance and management framework created by the Information Systems Audit and Control Association (ISACA). The conceptual framework is a popular choice for managing risk in a digitized enterprise environment.

COBIT provides a risk management model for large enterprise business capabilities and a model to fit specific areas of small to medium enterprises. Managing information and technology risk is no longer limited to the IT department, due to the integration of IT in every aspect of modern business operations.

COBIT is a flexible umbrella framework for creating an ERM framework with processes that align business and IT goals to prevent risk management silos across an enterprise. The framework identifies the following three core principles for building a governance and management framework:

- **Conceptual:** A governance framework should identify critical components and their relationships to maximize consistency and empower automation.
- **Agile:** A governance framework should be open and flexible to new content and address issues that arise with agility, integrity, and consistency.
- **Aligned:** A governance framework should align with different standards, other frameworks, and regulatory requirements.

2.18.4 The NIST Risk Management Framework

The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) is a U.S. federal government agency (U.S. Department of Commerce). The NIST framework is a cybersecurity framework used by private enterprises doing business with the U.S. government agencies, such as the Department of Defense (DoD).

The NIST framework model focuses on using business drivers to guide cybersecurity activities and risk management with three components:

- **Framework Core:** This is a set of five cybersecurity outcomes, with subcategories, activities, and informative references common to most business sectors and critical IT infrastructure.
 - **Identify:** Asset management, business environment, governance, risk assessment, and risk management strategy
 - **Protect:** Identity management, access control, data security, protective technology, and maintenance
 - **Detect:** Anomalies and events, detection processes, and continuous monitoring
 - **Respond:** Response planning, communications, analysis, mitigation, and improvements
 - **Recover:** Recovery planning, improvements, and communications
- **Implementation Tiers:** This is a mechanism to help organizations prioritize and achieve cyber security objectives to manage cybersecurity risk.
- **Framework Profiles:** Here, use the framework core elements to help develop organizational profiles and align cybersecurity activities with the mission, risk tolerance, and available resources.

2.19 Limitations and Weaknesses of Existing Frameworks

Although there have been a lot of work done in the risk management and frameworks, but the biggest limitation and weakness in all the available frameworks is that they are not specifically designed for construction industry and particularly for SMEs in the UK construction industry.

2.20 Summary

In general, there is no evidence of any particular approach for risk management that has not been adapted by SME's. If there is evidence of risk management process, that relies on intuitive and rules of thumb, which is not logical and sustainable. There is no existence of systematic risk management approach that followed throughout the SME's in the UK construction industry. However, some developed countries use some sort of database computerised assessment techniques which is a prime example to follow anywhere around, but that does not guarantee if SME's in those countries have any prominent framework. Hence it is a system, which helps control risks in construction projects for SME's. Its target should be to introduce a basic, commonsense technique for distinguishing, surveying, checking and overseeing risk in an educated and organized manner. It ought to give direction to actualizing a risk reaction system that is fitting to control construction projects at all levels.

CHAPTER 3

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

3.1 Introduction

This chapter details the conceptual framework of this research. Chapter 2 has highlighted the main issues and gaps theoretically, which are required to be investigated through further field research. The data and literature on the risk management process in SMEs are limited in the construction industry. No one has previously touched on this topic with an intention to find a solution to resolve the difficulties of the sector.

There is no previous research which could become the basis of proposing a strategic framework to encounter the difficulties faced to implement and use the risk management process. To propose the desired strategic framework, a strategy need is developed to identify and collect the relevant data.

In this chapter, the risk in general which be discussed, and the relationship of its elements/components; risk factors, followed by the SMEs in the UK construction industry which require a strategic framework. Moreover, the areas covered by the strategic framework to become the first of its type to be made for the particular sector in the industry.

3.2 Conceptual Framework

Figure 3.1: Conceptual Framework

3.3 SMEs in The UK Construction Industry

It is quite amusing that the economic driving sector of UK, which has more than half companies are the SMEs are lacking the most essential methods and experience of managing risk. In the general UK, and in particular London, where conservation of history and elements are the significant part of any construction project which involves a number of SMEs and they have no formal setup of managing risks from the start to the delivery of the project.

There have been many researchers who have touched the risk management topic in large companies and risk management practices in infrastructure and megaprojects, but there is very little work done in SME sector, where there is just one researcher who is in initial stages of risk management process, i.e. identification of risks.

There is a big gap in this area in terms of literature, data and past records as there is no formal body or method adoptable by the sector for risk management.

3.4 Risk Management in SMEs of the UK Construction Industry

In total, 99 percent of the organisations in the most developed countries are SMEs (OECD, 2005) and their stake in the UK construction industry is significant (BIS, 2013). The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) determines that the economic growth of the member countries is hugely dependent upon the development of SMEs and that their "productivity growth is fuelled by competitive processes in the industry which, to a huge extent, is built on the birth and death, entry and exist of smaller firms" (OECD, 2005). All enterprises need to determine an RM strategy and methodology to identify, assess and treat risks (Verbano, Venturini, 2013). SMEs need to implement RM significantly more than larger organisations because they endure from resource scarcity to respond quickly to internal and external threats which have the potential to become enormous losses and even insolvency of the organisation (Raghavan, 2005). However, SMEs to accomplish a competitive edge and increase the rate of success of their business, they need to take risky decisions and invest their resources in risky activities so that they can safeguard the innovativeness of delivering projects (Vargas, Hernandez, 2011). Moreover, due to the huge of deregulations and the liberalisation of trade, SMEs encounter more threats and challenges which make the SMEs' owner-managers to conceive RM as an integral part of the business management in order to keep the organisations viable and productive (Yeo, Lai, 2004). A thorough literature review on construction risk management between the period from 1991 to

2014 indicated that the challenges implementation of RM among organisations principally relates to the people engaged, organisation characteristics and the process of RM.

3.5 Risk Factors

Risk factors/events/attributes are the causes of risk events which occur in a project life cycle. They are usually same in all the projects but all the projects have additional risk factors which distinguish each project to be unique in its own way. These risk factors/events/attributes are analysed by the risk performance factors i.e. time, cost mainly, and sometimes analysts include quality as a factor as well.

An unplanned increase in cost and time overrun in construction projects are caused by the owner, contractor, environments, etc. in which multiple types of risk factors may happen concurrently. The effect of cost overrun, and time overrun do not only determine the construction industry but the overall economy as well. It is a first step in benchmarking a schedule and time control measures, which is proposed to increase the probability of the planned outcome while minimising risk factors.

It is quite significant that the identified criteria and factors miraculously contribute to the negative event in construction project cost and schedule, which in turn, impact the prediction of cost and schedule overruns.

The questionnaires will be developed to determine the probability of attributes/events/factors in addition to attributes cost impact and time impact, and these questionnaires cover a lot of attributes/risk factors from the literature to apportion numerous categories as per environmental and financial consequences which had dealt by 65 factors and increased up to 70 factors by practitioners' advice.

Data are collected through two questionnaires and structured interviews to collect information on this thesis. A survey is conducted in the form of a questionnaire to collect each project risk factors and its probability of occurrence in addition to its cost, performance and schedule overruns from the construction firms..

3.6 Assortments of Risk

The first stage of risk management is risk identification, where probable risks linked to construction projects are distinguished. Risk assortment is a vital part of risk identification affording to organise different risks influencing a construction project (see appendix B-4). A

number of methods for assortment risks have been advocated in the literature. A list of factors was taken out from some resources by (Perry, Hayes, 2000) which were assorted regarding their connection with clients, consultants, and contractors. (Flanagan, Norman, 1993) recommended three methods of assessing the risk through an incorporated procedure of universal systems theory with an association to work breakdown structure as a structure being as follows: via recognising type, consequence, and impact of risk. (Chapman, 2001) sorting risks to four subcategories: project, industry, client, and environment. Out of 58 risks recognised connected to Sino-Foreign construction joint ventures, (Shen et al., 2001) separated them in 6 groups according to risks" nature, i.e. legal, market, financial, management, technical, and policy and political. Generally, a number of methods exist for reasoning risks linked to construction projects and the cause of why a method is used shall be based on the objectives of the study. The following table will discuss the classification of risks:

Table 3.1: Risk Categories and Description

TYPES OF RISK	UNCERTAINTIES
Design risks	Change in Design, Design delays, changes and mistakes in designs, sketchy details, incomplete specifications, and uncertainty due to different site conditions.
Construction risks	Health and safety, quality control, site access, accidents, machinery failure, labour shortage/absent, inadequate equipment, the productivity of equipment, labour strike.
Financial & economical risks	Cash flow inadequacy, payment delays, wrong estimates of price, the extra cost of planning delays, Changes in legislations, abiding laws, fluctuation in trade rate/price.
Political risks	Change of government, Political parties disputes, sectorial conflicts, foreign forces pressure, disputes between the federal and provincial government, change in authorities.
Legal and regulatory risks	Currency rate uncertainty, Inflation/deflation; Price/cost fluctuation, Import restrictions/taxes, unusual permit and license delays, complicated/unstable tax procedure;
Sub-contractor risks	Reduced workmanship, lack of skilled labour, lack of specialisation, unlawful construction methods, subcontractor failure, subcontractor bankruptcy.
Environmental risks	Ecological damage, air/water pollution, waste management, recycling or material and waste disposal.

3.6.1 Risk Probability Impact Matrix

Risk impact probability matrix is an empirical calculation of time and cost overrun in a project. The impact of the negative event is calculated by plotting the time on y-axis and cost on the x-axis with a scale of 1-5. The risk matrix allows the analyst to compute the impact related to the probability of an event.

Risk impact calculates the rating of each risk event/factor that how severe its impact is on a project lifecycle. Risk impact can accumulate more variables other than time and cost, which can be performance and quality, but most commonly time and cost are used by the analysts as they have a major impact on the completion deadline and the budget of the project. The following figure illustrates the concept.

Figure 3.2: *Concept of Risk (Norman, 2018)*

The Risk Impact/Probability Chart is based on the principle that a risk has two primary dimensions:

1. **Probability** – A risk is an event that "may" occur. The chance of it happening can array anywhere from just above 0 percent to just below 100 percent. (Note: It can't be exactly 100 percent, because then it would be a certainty, not a risk. Moreover, it can't be exactly 0 percent, or it wouldn't be a risk.)

2. **Impact** – A risk, by its very type, invariably has a negative impact. However, the magnitude of the impact changes in terms of cost and impact on health, human life, or some other critical factor.

The chart allows you to rate potential risks on these two dimensions. The probability that a risk will occur is represented on one axis of the chart – and the impact of the risk, if it occurs, on the other.

The corners of the chart have these characteristics:

- **Low impact/low probability** – Risks in the bottom left corner are low level and can be frequently ignored.
- **Low impact/high probability** – Risks in the top left corner are of moderate importance – if an event occurs in this section, you can deal and move on. However, efforts should be made to reduce their probability.
- **High impact/low probability** – Risks in the bottom right corner are of high importance if they do occur, but they're very unlikely to happen. For these, however, policies should be made to minimise their occurrence and if happens, there should contingency plan available.
- **High impact/high probability** – Risks towards the top right corner are of critical importance. They are of high level and should be addressed immediately, with a close eye on them.

3.6.1.1 Time, Cost and Performance

These are the variables which around which a whole project is running. Risk management process is responsible of reducing the impact of the time, cost and performance impacts.

Figure 3.3: Mapping of Risk as per variables (Raftery,2019)

These variables can be used to prioritise the risks on any project to deal accordingly. The analysis will give a real-time profit loss and timescale of the project.

3.6.2 Risk Nature

Risk has two natures, either they are controllable or uncontrollable. Every risk event needs to be classified on every project to forecast the risk response development. It does give an analyst a clear understanding of whether a particular risk can be dealt with a prescribed methodology will be sufficient to counter the effect of a risk event or no one has control on the impact.

Particularly for an SME, it is essential to know the nature of risk so that a contingency response is preparing a plan for an alternative course of action and implementing it when the risk arises. (An, 2010)

3.7 Actual Risk Allocation

The liability to counter the risk has to be transferred to a stakeholder of the project. Which can be contractor, client, consultant, shared etc?

It is decided at the beginning of the project in the contract terms that who is responsible for the sort of risk which will occur and the risk which occurs unplanned, are also dealt accordingly during the life cycle.

3.8 Risk Response

When the risks are identified and assessed, the following step of the risk management process is to react to these risks. The nature of the reactions depends on the decisions carried out by the management team. In order to respond appropriately, the team has to digest the information present for the risk. There are two types of responses to risks: prompt response and contingency response. The prompt response minimises or eliminates the risks through modifications of the project plan. The nature of eventuality response is preparing a plan for a substitute course of action and implementing it when the risk arises. (An, 2010)

There are four basic patterns of treating the risk and they are risk retained, risk transfer, risk reduction and risk avoidance. In order to efficiently manage a risk, it is significant to adopt a combination of strategies to treat it. The selection process can be different every time until the most effective treatment strategy is developed. (Smith, 2006)

3.9 Risk Management Framework for SEMS and its Need.

It will provide a formulated step by step procedure for the easy implementation of the Risk Management process in SMEs. Recommending a frame work is similar to providing a guidance leaflet with a device or machine. Even if you are not the expert, if you follow step by step procedure provide with a machine, you can easily handle it. Risk Management Framework will require basic knowledge of the overview of the process, which is easy to understand on any level of an organisation or and SME.

3.10 Anticipated Impact of Risk Management Framework on SMEs Performance

If you have a handling manual for every product and its easy to operate the product, similarly framework for risk management will benefit the people with the least knowledge or have zero experience can perform risk management with the framework provided. It's a thought process which will be required to perform the steps outlined in the framework, whose success can be quantified at any given time or event in the project lifecycle.

3.11 The reason for Investigating SMEs

The significance of analysing system in SMEs causes from their economic significance. A set number of studies have determined the strategy process within SMEs. Still, it is unclear whether enhanced strategy conceptualization would have a positive impact on the universal economy, "SMEs are socially and economically significant to society as they ordinarily represent 99% of all enterprises in Europe and America." (Burke, 2007; Lou , 2011). However, SMEs are usually deficient in strategic planning (Wang, Walker, Redmond, 2007), the restricted information on the strategy process within SMEs has identified that they tend to ignore strategic activities (Augustine, Bhasi, Madhu, 2012). It is, therefore, important to understand to what magnitude they are involved in strategy and how they execute the procedure. The study regards the modern strategy process stage. Intention as a practice approach, three factors can be studied: practitioner, activity, and tools (Whittington, 2006). The concentration of the study concerns to the activities that are associated within each phase of the strategy process and the tools of risk management, if any, that are utilised to affirm these activities.

3.12 Summary

Risk management in the construction industry is still developing and efforts are still made to drive and implement risk management from different sectors. But in SME's of the construction industry it is still not being adopted as a formal method of analysing your negative event probability.

CHAPTER 4

METHODOLOGY

4.1 Introduction

The literature review discussed in Chapter 2 and the conceptual framework in Chapter 3 furnishes a background of the numerous facets of the current body of knowledge about construction safety. It spotlights the lack of a complete, integrated model of uninterrupted strategic entire improvement in the construction industry. Based on the information collected from the literature review, a particular research methodology was arising and is described in this chapter.

More elaborately, this chapter specifies the particular research methodology employed in the development of the risk management framework for continuous risk management improvement in the construction industry, including the data collection procedures, survey instruments development and data analysis techniques. Various statistical test processes, including constructive equation modelling technique waa proposed in the research investigation. The data for this research was gathered using more than one hundred surveys targeting construction contractors, consultancies, architectural firms in the UK to achieve the following objectives:

- To identify the current scenario of key risk management process and practices in the UK construction industry
- To evaluate the impact of risk management process on the overall performance of SMEs in the UK Construction industry.
- To identify the critical risk factors with indicators of cost, performance and time.
- To recommend a Risk Management Framework for SME's to mitigate the impact of risk

This chapter intends to appear in what type of methodologies is being used in this research. This chapter also includes an abbreviated discussion about research methodology, research philosophy, research approach, research design, research methods, research strategy, data collections methods, sampling, reliability and validity. In the end, the researcher will demonstrate the ethical issues, limitations and will vindicate the preferred methods of this research.

Probe for knowledge is known as research. It is an art of constant search for peculiar information. The research includes interpretation and redefining problems, creating a hypothesis or advising solutions, assessing, collecting and arranging data, building acquisitions and reaching conclusions and besides testing the results whether they are reserve for making hypothesis (Clifford, 2011). According to Redman and Mory (2010), research is a systematic attempt to attain the latest knowledge. It is an extensive and focused investigation for understanding and distinguishing of physical and social phenomena (Rajendar, 2008).

As per researchers Collis and Hussey (2003), the purpose of intending this research is to investigate existing conditions or issues, synthesise or reconsider current knowledge, give answers to problems, create or formulate new methods or systems, search and extract more common issues, describe latest phenomena, produce actual expertise or a mixture of any of them. Solving the research problem systematically is known as Research Methodology. It can also be implicit as a science of learning how research is completed scientifically (Kothari, 2006).

Saunders (2007) demonstrated the research process through the "Research Onion" model, according to him; there are 6 phases in the research process that are presented in figure 1.8.

The steps followed in each of the phases are described in the following sub-sections.

4.2 Research Methodology

To accomplish the desired objectives, we need to have appropriate technical knowledge of current risk management process adopted model (maybe) by SMEs, often used strategies, techniques and trends in local construction organisations and try to improve them by best practices, standards.

1. Reviewing the literature and reassessing previously developed frameworks for SME's in the UK.
2. Exploring the risk management process and culture in developed and developing countries.
3. Preparing questionnaires for collecting data through the survey with industry professionals and semi-structured interviews.

4. Collecting data of latest techniques and methods adopted by the SME's in industry.
5. Identifying the critical risk factors affecting the performance of SME's in the local industry.
6. Developing an "easy to understand" risk management framework for the SME's in the UK construction industry.
7. Testifying the developed risk management framework by sharing the model with small/medium construction firms (if possible).

4.3 Research Philosophy

The research onion, developed by Saunders (2007). It demonstrates the steps that must be dealt with when formulating a research strategy. When considered from the beyond a point, each layer of the onion depicts a more elaborated background of the research process (Saunders, 2007).

The research onion supplies a vital progression through which a research methodology can be planned. Its usefulness lies in its ability for almost any type of research methodology and can be used in numerous contexts (Bryman, 2012). This research will probe and describe the different sectors of the research onion and details the concepts at each stage.

Figure 4.1: Research Onion (Saunders, 2007)

Research paradigm and philosophy is a substantial component of research methodology in order to attain data in an effective and suitable way. A research paradigm is a point of view that is demonstrated on a collection of shared values, hypotheses, and practices and ideas (Johnson, Christensen, 2005). It is a variety of two thought processes that are concerned with the function of the researcher and the nature of the world. It caters the researcher to achieve the study in a versatile way. Research paradigm comprises the research methods and research philosophies. This blend helps out the researcher to stretch the knowledge and to understand considering the research topic.

There are three types of research philosophies discussed below:

4.3.1 Positivism

This theory is founded upon the invented methodology to allow scientific and generalised examinations and to compute the result with the help of statistical techniques. Positivism philosophy is generally applied in natural science, and it is an analytical and objective established process. It consists of a range of philosophies of natural science like universal law, unchanging philosophy and the observation of everything that exists in nature (Saunders, 2003).

Researcher compiles all figures and facts that are associated with the research trouble through schematic sources with the help of this philosophy. The aim of the researcher in this research philosophy is vital for the study. To find out the research aims and objectives, the researcher works as a subjective analyst to assess the gathered data and compute the correct result (Saunders, 2003).

4.3.2 Interpretivism

The interpretive philosophy trusts that the societal world of trade and management is too complicated as to be prepared in-laws and theories such as in the positivism philosophy. This research philosophy, there are various realities and meaning of apparent truth, and they are reserved for every condition and all research issue (Johnson, Christensen 2010). In this research philosophy, the researcher's aim is on

realising the explanations and meanings of social actors and to grasp their word from their perspective, is extraordinarily contextual and thus is not extensively universal (Saunders, Lewis, Thornhill, 2007).

There are various factors in this philosophy such as a person has multiple living standards, divergence in a cultural and social environment, individuality and family grouping, etc. that determines the nature of the person (Saunders, 2003).

4.3.4 Realism

It is also a vital philosophy that is based on the confidence of personal beliefs and values. Realism philosophy pivots on the principles that exist in the environment. Its views in the existence of external and objective actuality that affects people's social agreements and actions. This philosophy depicts that how human beings react towards real-world affairs (Johnson, Christensen 2010).

4.4 Research Approach

Considering very low or almost nil data and literature available for risk management practices of SME's in UK construction industry, The inductive approach is selected as there is intensive new data collection to formulate a risk management framework.

There are two types of research approaches:

4.4.1 Deductive Approach

The deductive approach is generally recognised as "testing a theory." In this approach, the researcher finds a hypothesis or theory and formulates a research strategy to reassure the prepared theory (Radwan, 2009)

For Example, the researcher wants to examine what does the word "Satisfaction" meant to numerous individuals. It is clear that what sort of data the researcher wishes to collect. For that reason, the researcher will investigate the topic and find out

numerous definitions of "satisfaction." After gathering the illustrations, the researcher can assure the definition of multiple individuals, by carrying out the structured interviews, using questionnaires or by group discussions. In this approach, the researcher will near select a sample of individuals based on gender, age, occupation, etc.

The data collected can then be compiled, and then the results can be computed and confronted. With this approach, the researcher can testify the established ideas on a variety of people in a paragraph and organised manner. The deductive approach can be best summarised in steps i.e. theory, hypothesis, observation, confirmation (Burney, 2008).

4.4.2 Inductive Approach

The inductive approach is well-known as "constructing a theory." In this research approach, the researcher starts with gathering data in order to construct a theory (Radwan, 2009). Inductive approach follows observation, pattern, tentative hypothesis and theory is made at last (Burney, 2008).

4.5 Research Strategy

A mixed method strategy is embraced as there are qualitative and quantitative both data collection and analysis are involved. Both of the data collection methods will enhance the time of data collection and analysis, but the results will be certain.

There is a variety of research strategies consisting of case study, survey, longitudinal, experimental, fieldwork and action research. The research objectives and questions will create the selection of research strategy, data gathering and testing procedures (Saunders, 2007). Survey and case study methods are used to examine research aims and questions. With the questionnaire survey, the researcher can gather a large amount of data from a big population professionally and economically (Morris, 2007).

The collection and examination of quantitative data can be performed with the assistance of this strategy by using inferential and descriptive data. Case studies are highly useful in achieving a detailed thoughtfulness of the situation and practices being published in the study.

Experimental studies are performed in carefully managed and planned surroundings, and allow the linking relationships of phenomena to be analysed and recognised. A longitudinal study is practiced to monitor the result that time has on the state under inspection and to gather primary data. Action research involves a researcher to manipulate change in any considerable condition and to expose and evaluate the results.

4.6 Research Design

The set up of the research study is called Research design, which lay down what the researcher will perform in the research from writing the hypothesis and its operational inferences to the final investigation of data. It is the conceptual format in which the research would be carried out. Research design's aim is to demonstrate a collection of right information with the cheapest cost, time and effort (Kumar, Ranjit, 2005).

For a specific research problem, the establishment of research design admits the discussion of the following:

- Research Objectives
- Data Collection Methods
- Source of Information
- Tools used to collect data
- Data analysis (Quantitative and Qualitative).

Research Methods

The numerous tools and techniques that are utilised to collect the data for the research are known as research methods. There are two types of research methods..

4.7.1 Quantitative Research Method

It is established on the assessment of quantity. The data collected by the quantitative method is in the form of numbers (Garbarino, Holland, 2009). The concern of this research method is on collecting and computing statistical data, and it concentrates on analysing the range, frequency, scale, etc. of phenomena.

This research method is extremely structured and comprehensive, and the results can be easily generated and presented numerically.

4.7.2 Qualitative Research Method

Qualitative research method formulates data in a textual form. This research method is more subjective in nature in contrast to the quantitative method. This method sums up with observing and reflecting on the less tangible components of the research, e.g. perceptions, feelings, standards. Qualitative research is anxious particular about qualitative aspect relating to quality (Rajasekar, Philominathan, Chinnathambi, 2006).

4.8 Sample Size

The construction industry in UK is enormous, and the central part of it is SME's. The researcher tried to collect as much data as possible in a given time. Considering time and resource limitation and later, Covid made it hard to collect more data or interviews.

A sample size of 100 respondents is selected. Sample size calculation is focused on the amount of data needed to draw a conclusion or make an appropriate decision regarding research subject. If there is more data then the decision will be more accurate. However, this does not essentially mean that more sample size is always best in calculating sample size. Thus the researcher used the Pareto Principle when taking sample size of the study. The Pareto Principle, which is proposed by the famous economist Vilfredo Pareto, shows that 80 percent of the result is achieved from the 20 percent of the causes, showing an imbalanced relationship between inputs and outputs. This also commonly known as 80/20 Rule. It is applied to the current study and the researcher took 100 project managers as a sample size.

4.9 Data Analysis

Quantitative data is to be analysed with SPSS, and qualitative data will be analysed with simple excel graphs.

4.9.1 Likert's Scale

Likert scales (named after their creator, American social scientist Rensis Likert) are quite popular because they are one of the most reliable ways to measure opinions, perceptions, and behaviours. The Likert Scale is a 5 or 7 point scale that offers a range of answer options from one extreme attitude to another, like "extremely likely" to "not at all likely." Typically, they include a moderate or neutral midpoint.

The questionnaire of Survey 1 will adopt a 1-5 Likert scale, which will be suitable for the data analysis. Whereas Survey 2 is qualitative analysis and based on semi-structured interviews only (see appendix D-4).

4.9.2 Mean Analysis

Considering the type and need of the research, it qualifies the mean analysis to find out the highest risk impact, risk response, nature of the risk and risk allocation. Different statistical tests such as reliability analysis, correlation analysis, factor analysis, etc. are not qualified in this research due to the nature and need of the research. Also, there are no proposition or hypothesis made for the research, so hypothesis testing is also not qualified for the research. Hence, the risk factors will be assessed on different scales for risk impact, risk response, nature of the risk and risk allocation by using mean analysis method.

4.10 Data Collection Methods

Researchers Knoke and Bohrnstedt (1994) determines that data collection as an act of producing primary data records for a given sample or population of observations. Babbie (1992) another researcher discussed different methods of data collection including experimental, survey, unobtrusive and evaluation. Because survey research demands collecting data by asking questions with selected people, it is known as the most appropriate method of data collection for the phase of the study.

There are two types of data, primary and secondary. The data that has been gathered primarily for the reason in mind is known as Primary data. Such type of data is collected for the first time, and it is in the shape of raw material. Primary data is more objective, reliable and genuine, and it has not been issued yet, transformed or changed by people; hence, its validity

is reliable than secondary data. The data that has been already gathered by someone and accessible from different sources is known as secondary data.

4.11 Sources of Primary Data

The origins to collect primary data are not a lot, and they are at times complicated too, because of either scarcity of support or lack of populace. Some of the sources through which researcher can gather primary data are below (a detailed list is attached in Appendix C1):

- Experiments
- Survey
- Interview (Structured, Semi-structured or unstructured interview)
- Questionnaire
- Observations.

4.12 Sources of Secondary Data

Secondary data is usually abundantly accessible and available. Because of the internet and electronic media, it is easier now to look for the valid secondary data. Sources to gather secondary data are as follows:

- Books
- Journals
- Articles
- Newspapers
- Magazines
- Published Electronic sources
- Blogs
- Website
- Published Printed sources.

4.13 Chosen Research Methods

To calculate the results, a mixed method approach of data collection is regarded, i.e. the interviews(primary data) and questionnaire survey analysis will be compared to the risk management process in the UK construction industry which has been looked into through

secondary data in the literature review to supply the best practice for SMEs to adopt a "easy to understand" risk management framework which is proposed after analysing the collected data and literature reviewed.

The semi-structure interviews and survey allow the researcher to gather in-depth information and provides an excellent chance to explore and investigate questions. The data which was collected through a questionnaire survey one was analysed quantitatively. The questionnaire two was qualitatively analysed.

For the collection of secondary data, the researcher used websites, journals, articles and books. The secondary data became the basis to recover the understanding of the issue, and with the assistance of secondary data the researcher understands numerous segments of the research.

In this study, the researcher has selected mixed methods i.e qualitative and quantitative research methods. The basis for determining the methods is that utilising a qualitative research method in data collection will provide computed data and information and the researcher have the right direction and command of the research with not much restrictions. The Following diagram depicts the relation made between case survey questionnaires and literature review.

Figure 4.2: *Data Analysis Theme*

4.14 Methodology Flowchart

4.15 Grounded Theory Analysis

For the analysis of qualitative data (questionnaire 2) grounded theory analysis is considered to equate the results of interviews and survey. It supplies analysis of textual data and requires continuous comparison thorough out.

4.16 Questionnaire Development

After the literature review, this is the second most extended phase of our project in which all information extracted from the literature review and the knowledge obtained from interviews with the advisor were gathered and comprehended in the formation of two questionnaires for the survey. The questionnaires are formulated, with appropriate questions in the form of statements that were related to the main objectives and then it was distributed to the SME's throughout the United Kingdom and few were done interviews with the main focus of targeting the businesses for the construction industry. There have been criteria's which were kept in consideration during the design phase, easy to under and simple terms were the priority as we have targeted all kind of SME's in the construction industry.

4.16.1 Questionnaire Design and Survey

This chapter admits methodology acquired for the design and development of the questionnaires, restraining in mind the questionnaires design considerations. Contractors, architects, designers and project management firms have conducted the survey. The questionnaire is divided into two parts, in questionnaire one, critical risk factors affecting the risk management and projects in SME's of the UK construction industry were examined, and in questionnaire two information regarding the current status of risk management practices by the SME's were assessed. This chapter also includes how the questionnaire was divided into different sections to have a grasp of responses for every aspect of the risk assessment procedure.

4.16.2 Literature Review for Survey

Development of useful questionnaires not only required knowledge about risk assessment but also some cognition about how to prepare a helpful questionnaire and how surveys are carried out. To captivate it, data was explored having information about designing questionnaires and conducting surveys. The researcher reviewed many samples of easy to analyse

questionnaires. Eventually, plenteous data was found through research papers and UWS Library.

4.16.3 Questionnaire Design and Development

The considerations for the questionnaire design and development are discussed in succeeding subsections.

4.16.4 Questionnaire Design Considerations

The considerations for the questionnaire following points should be taken into consideration:

- The objective of every question should be clear to the respondent.
- The questions should be precise, as the respondent will lose interest.
- Only those questions should be asked, which are the part of fulfilling the objectives.
- Freedom of speech should be given to all the respondents to comment openly and freely.
- Do not limit the questions to only one option.
- The questionnaire should have no ambiguity so that its easy to understand.
- The font, font size and the wordings of questionnaires should not be of different types.
- Carrying out a small pilot survey will allow the research to improve the final questionnaire for a definite result.
- There should be a cover letter with the questionnaire which clearly depicts your cause and should short and to the point.
- The cover letter should be in requesting formate, and depicts the importance of the response from the respondent.
- Confidentiality should be kept on high priority so that the respondent can answer freely.

4.16.5 Design Process

All proficient, valid, authentic and unbiased questionnaires were kept in mind, and with risk management knowledge. Finally, the questionnaires were designed.

4.16.6 Questionnaire Design

The questionnaire design was the most critical part of the research. Since an effective design can help in improving response rate and the inclusion of right questions which can generate

fruitful data, it will, in turn, enhance the effectiveness of data collected and provide help in developing an efficient risk management framework for SME's.

The questionnaires mainly consisted of mainly six sections:

- Personal Information.
- Company Information.
- Current scenario of Risk Management.
- Need of a Framework in SME's.
- Identifying the critical risk factors affecting SME's.

4.16.6.1 Personal Information

The section of Personal Information was designed to assess the experience level of the respondent.

4.16.6.2 Company Information

This section of Company Information was included to evaluate the structure of the company, the size and category they fit in.

4.16.7 Questionnaire Survey 1

In this questionnaire, the aim was to understand the knowledge of risk managers and their practices in the construction industry (see appendix C-1 and C-2). They were provided a chance to identify the impact of critical risk factors involved in the project life cycles of SME's in terms of:

- Time, Cost and Performance

They were also asked to answer if the particular risk factor is:

- Controllable or Uncontrollable

Allocation of risk thought their perspective, either it is

- Risk of Client
- Risk of Contractor
- Risk of Consultant/Designer

- Shared Risk

Moreover, the last step of risk management was also added, to complete the risk assessment criteria for the future researchers to consider if they want to develop a risk assessment or management tool with:

- Retention of Risk
- Reduction of Risk
- Transfer of Risk
- N/A

Structure

To develop an effective and unequivocal framework, risk factors were detailed in subcategories for the respondents to answer. The data which is collected is more than what is required, but it is done considering the future research possibilities which future researchers can develop risk assessment tool with all the four steps and information of risk management process is present in the questionnaire.

Risk Identification

This section is one of the four main sections of this part of the questionnaire. Under risk identification Risk Causes/Events are directed under different risk categories.

Risk Classification

This section contains two subsections, i.e. Risk Impact and Risk Nature

- Risk Impacts covers the impacts on Time, Cost and Performance. They are being assessed on the scale of 1-5. The description of the scale is defined below.
- Risk Nature deals with risk type that it is Controllable or Uncontrollable. Any one of them is to be selected for the particular risk cause/event.

Actual Risk Allocation

This section comprises allotment of risk that actually to who do it belongs to or who is actually responsible for the risk cause/event. It contains assignation to the Owner, Contractor, Owner, and Shared. Any one of them has to be marked for the regarding risk cause/event.

Risk Response Strategy

This Following section has been added in this questionnaire to acquire the response strategy used by respondents for the following risk causes/events that what type of approach they use in certain conditions to handle the risk cause/event. It constitutes strategies of Risk Reduction, Risk Transfer, Risk Retention and N/A.

Risk Categories Description

These risks categories are placed in order to become a part of the Tool in which they help the user to analyse them easily because they are the risk events which are collected from previous projects. The categories under which these events are located are:

- Design Related Risks
- Construction Risks
- Financial and Economic Risks
- Legal and Regulatory Risks
- Sub-contractor Risks

These categories are further discussed below

Design Related Risks

In this category, certain risk are placed which are related to design of the structure, which occurs during the construction. An incomplete or defective design, errors or omissions in mentioned design, or performing a design that does not correspond to the real site conditions are the most feared risks by construction contractors and subcontractors.

Construction Risks

In this category, such risks events place which arises during construction and becomes a cause of delay and becomes a serious concern for the contactor. The site conditions, project controls, and field performance are key to the success of a construction project. Therefore an incomplete design, an unrealistic schedule, and labour productivity represent the most important risks in this category.

Financial and Economic Risks

In this section, risks events related to finance and economy are placed. The project budget must be under control at all times. If a project has been underestimated or if the client or a contractor has not secured the project's funds, the chances of the project's failure are high.

Legal and Regulatory Risks

In this section risks involving regulatory authorities and other legal laws which concerns the codes and discipline of construction are placed. The changes in laws and regulations and the requirements for permits and their approval are considered to be important issues under this risk category.

Sub Contractor Risks

In the following category risks which are associated with sub-contractor and his working on projects are affiliated.

In the pertaining category risks due to naturally occurring hazards and disasters are referred.

Rating System

There were two types of rating system adopted throughout the questionnaire in order to make it simpler and understandable to the respondents, this is to ensure that the chance of discarding the response in the response analysis phase can be avoided. The final questionnaire was separated into two parts, first was Part A and the other one was Part B. Format of rating system according to the two different parts of the questionnaire is elaborated by the solved Example given under the table 4.1 and table 4.2.

Table 4.1: *Likert's Scale*

Scale for Risk Impact: 1=very low, 2=low, 3=medium, 4=high, 5=very high.
For Risk Nature: 1. C=Controllable, 2. UC=Uncontrollable.
For Actual Allocation: 1. O=Owner 2. CT=Consultant 3. CR=Contractor 4. SH=Shared.
For Risk Response: 1. RT=Risk Retention, 2. RD=Risk Reduction, 3. TR=Risk Transfer, 4. N/A=Not Applicable

SCALE OF PART B WITH EXAMPLE													
Risk Identification	Risk Classification					Actual Risk Allocation				Risk Response			
Causes	Risk Impact			Risk Nature		O	C T	C R	S H	R T	R D	T R	N / A
	Time	Cost	Performance	C	U C								
Natural Disasters	1234 5	1234 5	12345	X				X			X		

Table 4.2: Example of Scale Questionnaire 1

4.16.8 Questionnaire Survey 2

The need of questionnaire two arise when the questionnaire one was consuming too much information already from the respondents. To keep the interest of the respondent, and to consider the time the respondent will spend on questionnaire one, it was mandatory not to add more qualitative analysis questions in the same questionnaire but to develop a second questionnaire which can be floated in form or a survey or face to face interviews.

This questionnaire (see Appendix C-3) was an open-ended semi-structured interview with the respondent. In some cases where the respondent was busy, he was told to fill the questionnaire and send us a voice recording of his answers as well.

Questionnaire two covered the following segments of the research objectives.

Current Scenario of Risk Management

The section of the current scenario of risk management was included to assess the current practices and risk analysis procedures that are adopted by the local industry. It was aimed to acquire the information about the current adopted models or tools which are currently in practice or in any modified tool or model for their need. It made it easier to identify the type of framework required to cater to the need of SME's in the UK Construction Industry. This section subdivided into three sub-sections which carry seven statements regarding:

- key risk management process and practices in UK construction industry
- To ascertain organisation (SME) culture and maturity level of risk management in major projects
- To evaluate the impact of risk management process on the overall performance of SMEs in the Construction industry

4.17 Survey Administration

The survey was targeted to the main stakeholders of the construction industry. It was majorly conducted by interviewing and meeting the professionals to attain higher response, some of the questionnaires were distributed by mailing them on the personnel postal address and emailing them as well.

4.18 Pilot Survey

In order to refine the questionnaire pilot survey was conducted. The main objective of this survey was to identify the aspects that are lacking in the questionnaire or the aspects that are unnecessary and do not provide valid information. So for better consultancy about the questionnaire, experienced industry professionals were approached and their expert opinions were taken about the questionnaire.

4.19 Final Survey

After the pilot survey, some valuable changes in the final questionnaire were made to be more relevant according to need. Contractors, Consultancies, Architects etc were approached in the UK. The data we accessed via FMP, CIOB, RIBA, RICS and CHAS was enough to contact the relevant stakeholders and communicate with them to float our questionnaire (see appendix A-2).

It was decided to make face to face interviews with the respondents to get the maximum output of the prototype. The second approach was for those respondents who were not interviewed because of their busy schedule; questionnaires were dropped at their offices or on email to give them ample time to fill. The survey was conducted to the best of knowledge and

approach to have maximum output and response from the target audience which would assist in analysing questionnaires. (Final questionnaires are attached in Appendix C-2)

4.19 Pilot Survey and Improvement

Before distributing the final questionnaire, a small pilot survey has been conducted to test its ability to be comprehended by prospective respondents and to be completed by them in a reasonable amount of time. Moreover, the feedback from this pilot survey and the assistance provided by the advisors on them, aided in defining the final design of the questionnaire.

4.20 Final Survey

The Final Survey was based on two questionnaire surveys, each questionnaire was detailed to target the different information as per the objectives. The first survey identified the most significant risk factors in the industry for SME's as per each step of risk management process i.e. Identification, classification, allocation, and response, whereas classification was further distributed in risk impact and risk nature, which will be further utilised to identify the critical risk factors. The second part of the questionnaire targets the data collection to fulfil the two other remaining objectives. The primary objective of the questionnaire survey was to examine the current status of the local industry regarding the awareness and the implementation of risk management tools and techniques. It was also aimed to find out the factors that limit risk management in the industry also establish the need for an effective and efficient risk management framework. In order to get the true picture of risks to cater during the execution phase of the project, the survey was targeted the all major stakeholders of the construction industry. The break out of questionnaire distribution is as follows:

Table 4.3: Breakout of Questionnaires

Architects	Contractors	Consultancies	Suppliers	Other's	Total
11	67	13	7	2	100

4.21 Survey Analysis

It was aimed to conclude the data obtained through the surveys prior to the development risk management framework. The questionnaire has been designed to facilitate quantitative analysis of the responses from which data can be identified that has endorsed in the development of the framework and also conclusions with a proper statistical significance can then be drawn. The responses in the questionnaire analysed and reviewed for each statement in the questionnaire and the relevant statistical analysis implemented and then the results were presented in a statistical form also the conclusion was drawn based on the findings of the survey. However, the outcomes of the survey analysis provided the basis for the future researchers to enhance the risk management practice in UK SME's.

4.22 Reliability and Validity

Reliability and validity are the valuable and primary components of any measurement method. Reliability is detailed as the degree to which a test, observation, questionnaire or any measurement method generates the likewise results on repeated attempts (Michael, 2010). If a method or Tool of measurement regularly provides similar scores to entities or persons with the same values, the attempt is considered to be reliable. Reliability contains the reproducibility or constancy of test scores (Thanasegaran, 2009).

The extent to which the instrument evaluates what it claims to measure is known as validity. For example, an assessment that is utilised to monitor candidates for employment is valid if its results are directly linked to prospect work performance (Michael, 2010). Validity has two important factors: internal and external. Internal validity depicts whether the outcomes of the study are reliable considering the techniques used to select the groups, data was entered or analysis completed. External validity determines whether the outcomes are movable to alternative groups of interest (Handly, 2013).

4.23 Ethical Issues

Researchers Lewis and Saunders (2007) determines that ethics nominates the right of the individuals who became the component of the research and are determined by it. Ethics are

the diverse standard of actions that lead towards appropriate solutions of actions to others (Cooper, Schindler, 2008).

In this research, the researcher will use two questionnaires and will do direct interviews and distribute the questionnaire survey with the industry representatives to collect primary data, throughout this process the researcher will not disclose the identity and the personal details of the interviewee and people who filled the questionnaires. The researcher take it seriously that questions that will be asked in an interview or questionnaire will not harass or offend the employee or interviewee.

The researcher will use all the gathered validated data only for research purpose and once the statistical analysis is completed, the researcher will dispose the data in an appropriate way.

4.24 Development of Risk Management Framework

This phase of the project was the most typical and challenging in which all the data that has been collected for literature either from previous research papers or from academic and journals have been gathered along with the results and the statistical analysis of questionnaire survey and by selecting the most common and user-friendly framework is formulated to help the construction professionals in finding out the suitable strategy to counter the risks in any phase of the construction project or business.

4.25 Data Collection Process

In order to develop the formalized Risk Management Framework described above, it is necessary to collect a large amount of data. Similarly, in establishing the empirical evidence, it is essential to collect information from the Company House service of government UK website, Federation for Small Businesses(FSB), Royal Institute of British Architects(RIBA), Royal Institute of Chartered Surveyors(RICS), Chartered Institute of Building(CIOB), Federation of Master Builders(FMB) and International Institute of Risk and Safety Management(IIRSM). Secondary data formed the basis for risk management literature and its procedure in the construction industry, and the remaining objectives are justified by primary data collected through the methods discussed above (see appendix A-3).

4.26 Criteria for Choosing Organization

The companies selected for interviews are chosen based on the Department for Business, Innovation and Skills UK definition for SMEs. Organizations with fewer than 250 employees and turn over not exceeding 50 million Euro are said to be medium-sized companies. Furthermore, within this category, the organizations which have fewer than 50 employees and have turnover no more than 10 million Euros (BIS, 2013) are said to be small size organizations. After getting a benchmark for the selection criteria, the number of different bodies (see appendix B-3) is contacted to gather the statistics of the SME's.

Also, the ability of these institutions(CIOB, RICS etc.) to contribute efficiently and constructively to the research through useful in-depth interviews are also considered. Moreover, it is in the jurisdiction of these institutions and organisations to formulate policies for the risk assessment procedure, boosting morale and promoting SME's to learn and implement process efficiently and diversify methods. It also covers different un chartered bodies(FMB, IRM, IIRSM etc.) to contribute in keeping the past data record for the future endeavours for the SME's to take the guideline.

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Furthermore, SME's were selected depending on their experience, reliability, credibility and staff knowledge about the process. e.g. whether staff employed are sufficient experienced, trained, skilled and knowledgeable to provide adequate and reliable relevant information.

4.27 Data Analysis

Data will be analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) to produce means values and other Statistical values and tests, which provided results for the tests of the hypotheses(if any hypothesis set) guiding the study. The variables used in the analysis of data included dependent and Independent variables. The Independent variables are cost, and time, whereas the dependent variable shows the level of change in performance. They are all factors of risk management which produce a cut of value which assist any risk manager to the treat the risk/cause as per its appropriate approach or company policy and assessment methods.

4.28 Organization of Study

Stage 1

To grasp the complete knowledge on the topic, relevant literature and all sources of information were explored (see appendix A1) to find authentic published research to identify the most the real insights and difficulties faced in implementing risk management process of any of its factors.

Stage 2

Diving all the collected literature in most relevant and less relevant groups. Extracting relevant data and information to formulate the working strategy of the research. Fulfilling any objectives which are based on the secondary data (see appendix A-4).

Stage 3

Developing methodology to fulfil remaining objectives and formulating the questionnaires for the interviews and surveys.

Stage 4

Conducting surveys and interviews in different mode os technology and in person, which will include the pilot survey and distribution, following up and collecting of final survey questionnaires.

Stage 5

Data analysis of all completed surveys, interviews, and extracting the relevant results with the help of qualitative and quantitative analysis to articulate the risk management framework.

Stage 6

Conclusions and recommendations for SME are considering the fact of adding new information to the body of knowledge.

4.29 Plan for the thesis.

After going through the number of publishings about planning the doctorate thesis, eight chapters were intended to be part of the final dissertation. Framework and methodology are in

separate chapters, whereas all the chapter are typical other than chapter 6 (risk management framework) and chapter 7 (framework evaluation) which are the essence of this research.

4.30 Summary

The overall methodology for achieving the prime objectives of the project has been discussed in this chapter which is necessary to develop a risk management framework for SME's. There were four major phases followed in developing the risk management framework. The first step was to review the previous or past researches. The second step was to develop an effective questionnaire and survey. The third step was to analyse the response of the survey and the final step was to formulate an effective and easy to implement risk management framework and suggest the recommendation based on the survey. The next chapter will be highlighting the different aspects on which literature has been reviewed, especially considering the objectives of this study; the next chapter is the most important phase among all. It is underlining how data has been collected by various contractors through different stages from the development of a questionnaire to the final floating process.

CHAPTER 5

DATA ANALYSIS

5.1 Introduction

Although the attitudes towards risks and uncertainties of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) are identified and acknowledged in general, little detail regarding the usage of risk management as a systematic tool is available within the company. In order to critically analyse the risk management process in SMEs, the researcher adopted quantitative analysis and carried out a survey. A detailed multiple-choice questionnaire survey was formed in order to collect the data for the research. The researcher distributed the questionnaire survey to different SMEs operating in the UK to order to critically analyse the risk management process. Different type of risks has already been identified by critically reviewing the literature regarding risk in project management. As the risk management consists of various steps, the researcher included different types of risk in accordance with the impact of cost, time and performance.

Moreover, the questionnaire also included the nature of risk, actual risk response and risk response. The researcher collected the data from the respondents either personally or through emails. A sample size of 100 respondents is selected. One hundred respondents were circulated among the targeted respondents. From 100 questionnaires, a total of 100 were returned by the respondent, leading to an ideal response rate of 100%. Out of 100 received questionnaire, all of them were usable and proceeded for analysis. The Project Risk Management Questionnaire used for the research is attached in Appendix 1. The purpose of this chapter is to provide a comprehensive analysis of the collected data. The chapter first provides the company information and then highlights the risk assessment by following different steps.

5.2 Company Information:

The first category of the questionnaire deals with company information where the respondents of SMEs were asked about the type of projects as well as the yearly turnover of the company. The results are represented with the help of tables and graphs below:

Table 5.1 – Type of projects

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Commercial project	22	22.0	22.0	22.0
Residential project	77	77.0	77.0	99.0
Infrastructural project	1	1.0	1.0	100.0
Industrial project	0	0	0	
Environmental project	0	0	0	
Other project	0	0	0	
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.1 – Type of projects

The table and graph above highlight the type of projects initiated in the company. As stated in the table, around 77% of the projects are residential projects, 22% of the projects are commercial, and only 1% of the projects are infrastructural projects. However, there is no industrial, environmental, and other types of projects are included in the study. It can be concluded that majority of the respondents belong to residential projects which took part in the survey.

Table 5.2 – Annual Turnover of the Company

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Less than 1 million	0	0	0	
1 to 5 million	64	64.0	64.0	64.0
More than 5 million	34	34	34	100

Figure 5.2 – Annual Turnover of the Company

The table and pie chart above represents the annual turnover of the companies included in the study. As the respondents belong to the SMEs of the UK, the researcher provided three different options for the annual turnover of the company. It can be seen from the table above that mostly the respondents have belonged to the companies with the annual turnover of 1 million to 5 million, and the rest belongs to more than 5 million.

5.3 Questionnaire Analysis I

5.3.1 Risk Assessment:

After identification of risks with the help of a literature review, 28 risks have been identified. These risks are classified into Design related risks, Construction related risks, Financial and

Economic Risks, Legal and Regulatory Risks and sub-contractor risks. The next step is to conduct a risk assessment to find out the impact of those risks on the time, cost and performance of the project. In short, the risk impact highlights the indication of the potential effects of risk exposure on the scope of projects.

The researcher has adopted a quantitative risk assessment method to evaluate the risks. The quantitative risk assessment is the process of risk management by numerically assessing identified risks in a project. The primary goal of the quantitative method is to determine the impact of cost, time and performance on the risk of the project. Thus, quantitative risk assessment allows the risk manager to identify the level of risks and the consequence of each risk on time, cost and performance.

For better understand and higher consistency in the representation of the assessment, a quantitative rating method is used for risk assessment. After identifying the risks, each risk then rated to find out their impact. The rating helps in finding whether or not it is safe enough to continue or if it is crucial to execute extra control measures in order to eliminate or reduce the risks. A mean analysis is conducted to find out the level of impact of each driver on the risks. The risks are then rated or ranked after considering the mean value. Generally, the risk rating or ranking is used to find out which risk needs to be prioritised over other risks in terms of determining what to do and when. Based on the ranking and level of risks, the consequences of those risks are also provided. As the risks are assessed with the help of 5 pointed scales, where 1 represents a very low risk, 2 represents a low risk, 3 represents a medium level of risk, 4 shows a high level of risks and 5 represents a very high level of risk. Table 4.3 provides the assessment criteria to evaluate the impact of different drivers on the risk and the consequence of each risk.

Table 5.3 - Impact Assessment Criteria

No.	Assessment	Consequences
1	Very Low	The impact is insignificant, and the loss is meaningless
2	Low	Require direct handling immediately on the spot, and loss becomes the cost of additional expenditure
3	Medium	Require to be managed by the executor, and a loss is quite significant

4	High	Failure, low productivity, significant loss, special handling required
5	Very High	Errors affect other, require handling by the director, colossal loss, require special handling

Each risk will be provided with the consequences stated above depending on the level of risks on time, cost and performance of the project. The following section contains the impact of time, cost and performance on each risk.

5.3.1.1 Time Impact Analysis:

The following table shows the level of risks which affect the time of the projects. The consequences of each risk are also presented in the table below:

Table 5.4: *Time Impact Analysis*

Type of Risk	Mean	Risk Rank	Risk Level	Consequences
DESIGN RELATED RISKS				
Design process delays	4	5	High	Failure, low productivity, significant time loss, special handling required
Errors and Omissions	3.7	6	High	Failure, low productivity, major time loss, special handling required
Inadequate Specifications	2.7	10	Medium	Require to be managed by the executor, and time loss is quite significant
Loss or Delay or Design Changes	2.7	10	Medium	Require to be managed by the executor, and time loss is quite significant
CONSTRUCTION RELATED RISKS				

Quality Problem	1.7	12	Low	Require direct handling immediately on the spot, and time loss becomes the cost of additional expenditure
Site Accidents	3.6	7	High	Failure, low productivity, major time loss, special handling required
Site Access	3.6	7	High	Failure, low productivity, major time loss, special handling required
Equipment Failure	4.3	3	High	Failure, low productivity, major time loss, special handling required
Unavailability of Labor	4.7	2	Very High	Errors affect other, require handling by director, very huge time loss, require special handling
Unavailability of equipment	4.7	2	Very High	Errors affect other, require handling by director, very huge time loss, require special handling

FINANCIAL AND ECONOMIC RISKS

Adequate cash flow	3.3	8	Medium	Require to be managed by the executor, and time loss is quite significant
Delayed payment on the contract	4.7	2	Very High	Errors affect other, require handling by director, very huge time loss, require special handling
Underestimation of cost	3.6	7	High	Failure, low productivity, major time loss, special handling required
Cost overrun due to schedule delays	5	1	Very High	Errors affect other, require handling by director, very huge time loss, require special handling
Changes in regulation	4.4	4	High	Failure, low productivity, major time loss, special handling required

Inconsistent application of laws	2.4	11	Low	Require direct handling immediately on the spot, and time loss becomes the cost of additional expenditure
change in trade aptitude	3.7	6	High	Failure, low productivity, major time loss, special handling required

LEGAL AND REGULATORY RISKS

Exchange rate fluctuation	2.9	9	Medium	Require to be managed by the executor, and time loss is quite significant
Inflation	1.7	12	Low	Require direct handling immediately on the spot, and time loss becomes the cost of additional expenditure
Price fluctuation	2.9	9	Medium	Require to be managed by the executor, and time loss is quite significant
Complicated/unstable tax structure	3.6	7	High	Failure, low productivity, major time loss, special handling required
Import restrictions	4.3	3	High	Failure, low productivity, major time loss, special handling required
Problems with permit and license	5	1	Very High	Errors affect other, require handling by director, very huge time loss, require special handling

SUBCONTRACTOR RISKS

Lack of skilled labour	5	1	Very High	Errors affect other, require handling by director, very huge time loss, require special handling
Improper cash flow	4.7	2	Very High	Errors affect other, require handling by director, very huge time loss, require special handling

Lack of expertise	3.6	7	High	Failure, low productivity, major time loss, special handling required
Improper means of Construction	5	1	Very High	Errors affect other, require handling by director, very huge time loss, require special handling
Sub-contract failure	5	1	Very High	Errors affect other, require handling by director, very huge time loss, require special handling

The figure below represents the impact of different risks on time.

Figure 5.2 – Risk Impact on Time

Design related Risks:

The table above presents the risks and their impact on the time of the project. As shown above, Design related risks are in high and medium level. Design process delays and Errors and Omissions are resulting in significant time loss which requires special attention in order to recover the loss of time. These risks, if not resolved earlier, can lead to a substantial loss of time in a project which will consequently delay the execution of the overall project. Moreover, inadequate specifications in Design and Loss or Delay or Design Changes are in a medium level of risk which can also result in the loss in the time of a designing phase in the project. These both risk factors require to be managed by the executor in order to avoid delays in designing phase so that the project can be executed properly. Since Design related risks are in a medium and high level of risks, this is an essential concern for the project managers. This may result in a massive loss if not handled properly as the designing phase is the initial phase in the projects, and they need to be handled efficiently for the overall success of the project.

Construction-related risks:

Time delays in Construction result in dissatisfaction to all parties involved in the project, and the prominent role of the project manager is to ensure that projects are completed in a budgeted time and cost. In Construction related risks, one risks are of low level, three Construction related risks are of high level, and the remaining two risks are of a very high level. Quality Problem risk tends to have a low impact on time. It needs direct handling on the spot and time loss in quality problem can become the cost of additional expenditure. Therefore, the managers need to handle it immediately to avoid issues in future. Besides, site accidents, site access and equipment failure possess a high level of risk in the time of the project. These risks will fail the Construction of project with low productivity and significant time loss in the construction phase. The managers need to handle and manage in a particular way to avoid construction risks. Most importantly, unavailability of labour and unavailability of equipment can result in a very high level of loss in the construction phase, which can fail the project. Unavailability of labour and equipment are the crucial level of risks which can affect overall operations of the project. These risks need to be handled by the directors as they result in a very high level of time loss of the project.

Financial and Economic Risks:

The next category of risks is financial and economic risks. According to the results, one low level of risk, one medium level of risk, two high level and two very high levels of risks are

detected in the financial and economic aspect of the project. Inconsistent application of laws is a low level of time loss which needs immediate action to avoid further issues. Adequate cash flow is regarded as a medium level of risks which needs to be handled by the executor since the time loss is significant. Underestimation of cost, changes in regulation and differences in trade aptitude are considered as a high level of loss in time. These factors, especially changes in regulation and changes in trade aptitude cannot be estimated beforehand due to a variety of factors, but their chances of occurrence are very low. However, if they occur, they can result in high time loss, failure and low productivity. Delayed payment on contract and cost overrun due to scheduled delays are regarded as a very high-risk factor because the project will get delayed without paying to the agreement and scheduled delays in cost will delay the completion of the project. It is vital to make the availability of payment and avoid expected delays for loss avoidance. These factors do not only result in the loss of time but also affect the overall operation and need to be handled by the director or else it will result in huge loss.

Legal and Regulatory Risks:

The results on Legal and regulatory risks detect one low level, two medium-level risks and two high-level risks and one very high-level risks on the time of the project. As indicated in the table, inflation has a low impact on the time of the project. Due to inflation risk, low level of time loss is expected in the project. Exchange rate fluctuation and price fluctuations risk contain the medium level of loss on time. These two factors cannot be estimated beforehand due to a variety of factors, but their chances of occurrence are very low. Complicated/unstable tax structure and Import restrictions contain a high level of risk impact on time. These risks result in failure, low efficiency and significant time loss, thus, require special handling according to the regulations. Moreover, problems with permit and license contain a high level of risk which have an impact on time. Problems with permit and license result in delays on time which exceed the scheduled timings of projects.

Subcontractor Risks:

The next category of risks is subcontractor risks which have a very high impact on the timings of the project. As indicated in the results, four risk factors have a very high level of impact, and one risk factor has a high level of impact on the time of the project. Lack of expertise or subcontractor has a high level of risk as it results in the performance of the project, and it then needs to be done all over again by hiring a new subcontractor. The risk

managers need to evaluate the skills, expertise and capabilities of subcontractors beforehand in order to avoid such risks. Also, lack of skilled labour, improper cash flow, Improper means of Construction, and Sub-contract failure risks have a high level of impact on time. These factors can impact other activities of the project; hence, they need to be handled by the director to come out from a considerable time loss. The consequences of lack of skilled labour, improper cash flow, Improper means of Construction and Sub-contract failure risks do impact not only the project scope of time but also impact the reputation of the organisations in their respective industry.

Table 5.5 – Highest Ranked Risks (TIME)

Type of Risk	Mean	Risk Rank	Risk Level
CONSTRUCTION RELATED RISKS			
Unavailability of Labor	4.7	2	Very High
Unavailability of equipment	4.7	2	Very High
FINANCIAL AND ECONOMIC RISKS			
Delayed payment on contract	4.7	2	Very High
Cost overrun due to schedule delays	5	1	Very High
LEGAL AND REGULATORY RISKS			
Problems with permit and license	5	1	Very High
SUBCONTRACTOR RISKS			
Lack of skilled labour	5	1	Very High
Improper cash flow	4.7	2	Very High
Improper means of Construction	5	1	Very High
Sub-contract failure	5	1	Very High

The table above shows that overall, sub-contract failure, improper means of Construction, improper cash flow, lack of skilled labour, problems with permits and license, Cost overrun due to schedule delays, delayed payment on contract, unavailability of equipment and

unavailability of labour have a very high impact on time. These risks need special consideration as they will result in failure of the project.

5.3.1.2 Cost Impact Analysis:

The following table shows the level of risks which affect the cost of the projects. The consequences of each risk are also presented in the table below:

Table 5.6 : Cost Impact Analysis

Type of Risk	Mean	Risk Rank	Risk Level	Consequence
DESIGN RELATED RISKS				
Design process delays	1.7	13	Low	Require direct handling immediately on the spot; financial loss becomes the cost of additional expenditure
Errors and Omissions	2.7	11	Medium	Require to be managed by the executor, loss of cost is quite significant
Inadequate Specifications	1	15	Very low	The impact is insignificant, loss of cost is meaningless
Loss or Delay or Design Changes	3.3	8	Medium	Require to be managed by the executor, loss of cost is quite significant
CONSTRUCTION RELATED RISKS				
Quality Problem	4	6	High	Failure, low productivity, major loss of cost, special handling required
Site Accidents	4.7	2	Very High	Errors affect other, require handling by the director, colossal loss of cost, require special handling
Site Access	5	1	Very High	Errors affect other, require handling by the director, massive loss of cost, require special handling

Equipment Failure	3	9	Medium	Require to be managed by the executor, loss of cost is quite significant
Unavailability of Labor	1	15	Very Low	The impact is insignificant, loss of cost is meaningless
Unavailability of equipment	2.2	12	Low	Require direct handling immediately on the spot; financial loss becomes the cost of additional expenditure

FINANCIAL AND ECONOMIC RISKS

Adequate cash flow	1.6	14	Low	Require direct handling immediately on the spot, and financial loss becomes the cost of additional expenditure
Delayed payment on the contract	2.9	10	Medium	Require to be managed by the executor, loss of cost is quite significant
Underestimation of cost	5	1	Very High	Errors affect other, require handling by the director, massive loss of cost, require special handling
Cost overrun due to schedule delays	4.1	5	High	Failure, low productivity, major loss of cost, special handling required
Changes in regulation	4.7	2	Very High	Errors affect other, require handling by the director, vast loss of cost, require special handling
Inconsistent application of laws	2.7	11	Medium	Require to be managed by the executor, loss of cost is quite significant
change in trade aptitude	4.7	2	Very High	Errors affect other, require handling by the director, massive loss of cost, require special handling

LEGAL AND REGULATORY RISKS

Exchange rate fluctuation	4.4	3	High	Failure, low productivity, major loss of cost, special handling required
Inflation	5	1	Very High	Errors affect other, require handling by the director, huge loss of cost, require special handling
Price fluctuation	4.7	2	Very High	Errors affect other, require handling by the director, huge loss of cost, require special handling
Complicated/unstable tax structure	5	1	Very High	Errors affect other, require handling by the director, huge loss of cost, require special handling
Import restrictions	4.3	4	High	Failure, low productivity, major loss of cost, special handling required
Problems with permit and license	3.6	7	High	Failure, low productivity, major loss of cost, special handling required

SUBCONTRACTOR RISKS

Lack of skilled labour	5	1	Very High	Errors affect other, require handling by the director, huge loss of cost, require special handling
Improper cash flow	3.6	7	High	Failure, low productivity, major loss of cost, special handling required
Lack of expertise	2.9	10	Medium	Require to be managed by the executor, loss of cost is quite significant
Improper means of Construction	4.7	2	Very High	Errors affect other, require handling by the director, huge loss of cost, require special handling
Sub-contract failure	5	1	Very High	Errors affect other, require handling by the director, huge loss of cost, require special handling

The figure below represents the impact of different risks on cost.

Figure 5.3 – Risk Impact on Cost

Design related Risks:

The table above presents the risks and their impact on the cost of the project. As shown above, Design related risks are at the medium level, low level or same level. Loss or Delay or Design Changes and Errors and Omissions are resulting in a moderate level of effect on the cost, which requires significant attention in order to recover the loss of cost. Although the impact of these risks is the moderate level, they can lead to the significant loss of cost in a project which will consequently impact the successful execution of the overall project. Moreover, design process delays have a low level of impact on the cost of the project. However, design process delays need to be handled immediately on the spot as the financial loss becomes the cost of additional expenditure. Also, inadequate specifications have a very

low level of impact on the cost of the project, which is considered as insignificant and meaningless. Since Design related risks are in the low level of risks, this is a positive signal for the project managers. In case the impact of these risks was higher, it may result in a huge loss if not handled properly as the designing phase is the initial phase in the projects. Overall, Design related risks do not have a major impact on the cost of the project.

Construction-related risks:

In Construction related risks, one Construction related risk is of very low level, low level, medium level and high level each and two Construction related risks have a very high impact on the cost of the project. Unavailability of labour has a very low impact on the cost of the project, and the impact is considered very insignificant and meaningless on the overall project. Unavailability of equipment has a low level of impact on the cost of the project as it requires direct handling immediately and it will result in the cost of additional expenditure due to the unavailability of equipment in the project. Equipment failure risk possesses a moderate level of impact on the cost, which is required to be managed by the executor. Due to the equipment failure, the project will require an additional cost and the loss is considered significant. Quality Problem risk tends to have a high impact on cost as its quality problem in the project can result in a major loss of cost with a low level of productivity. This requires special handling of the quality team to overcome the loss. Besides, site accidents and site access possess a very high level of risk on the cost of the project. These risks need to be handled by the directors as they result in a very high level of time loss of the project, and consequently, these risks will lead to the failure of the project. The construction phase is the most crucial phase in projects and case of any changes and hazards in this phase; it might result in changes in project scopes. Overall, Construction related risks have a moderate level of impact on the cost of the project.

Financial and Economic Risks:

The next category of risks is financial and economic risks. According to the results, one low level of risk, two medium levels of risk, one high level and three very high levels of risks are detected which have an impact on the cost of the project. Adequate cash flow is regarded as a low level of risks which needs to be handled immediately, and the loss of cost can be significant if not handled properly. Inconsistent application of laws and Delayed payment on contract have a moderate level of impact on the cost, which needs immediate action to avoid further issues, and the loss of cost is significant. Cost overrun due to scheduled delays has a

high level of impact on the cost of the project. This risk needs to be managed initially as this can result in high-cost loss, failure and low productivity due to the constant scheduled delays. Underestimation of cost, changes in regulation and changes in trade aptitude have a very high level of loss on cost. These factors, especially changes in regulation and changes in trade aptitude cannot be estimated beforehand due to a variety of factors, but their chances of occurrence are very low. However, if occur, they are most likely impact the scope of the overall project. These factors do not only result in the loss of cost but also affect the operations of the project. Overall, financial and economic risks have a high level of impact on the cost of the project.

Legal and Regulatory Risks:

The results of Legal and regulatory risks found three high-level risks and three very high-level risks on the cost of the project. As indicated in the table, exchange rate fluctuation, import restrictions and problems with permit and licenses have a high level of impact on the cost of the project. These risks result in failure, low efficiency and major time loss, thus, require special handling according to the regulations. Exchange rate fluctuation is the unpredictable factor which is not in control of the manager. However, the managers need to consider this factor beforehand to avoid major loss of cost. Most importantly, inflation risk, price fluctuations risk and Complicated/unstable tax structure contain a very high level of risk on the cost of the project. These risks result in failure, low efficiency and major time loss, thus, require special handling according to the regulations. However, their chances of occurrence are very low, but in case of occurrence, these risks can impede the execution of the project. Overall, legal and regulatory risks have a very high level of impact on the cost of the project.

Subcontractor Risks:

The next category of risks is subcontractor risks which have a significant impact on the cost of the project. As indicated in the results, three risk factors have a very high level of impact, and one risk factor has a medium and high level of impact on the cost of the project. Lack of expertise or subcontractor has a moderate level of impact as it results in the performance of the project, and it then needs to be done all over again by hiring a new subcontractor. This type of risk needs to be managed by an executor promptly as the loss of cost is significant. Improper cash flow has a high level of impact on time. This can result in failure and major loss of cost if not handled properly. Lack of skilled labour, Improper means of Construction

and Sub-contract failure risks have a very high impact on the cost of the project. These factors can impact other activities of the project; hence, they need to be handled by the director to come out from a huge time loss. These risks have a powerful impact on the project scope and need to be handled carefully for the success of the project. Overall, subcontractor risks have a very high level of impact on the cost of the project.

Table 5.7 – Highest Ranked Risks (COST)

Type of Risk	Mean	Risk Rank	Risk Level
CONSTRUCTION RELATED RISKS			
Site Accidents	4.7	2	Very High
Site Access	5	1	Very High
FINANCIAL AND ECONOMIC RISKS			
Underestimation of cost	5	1	Very High
Changes in regulation	4.7	2	Very High
change in trade aptitude	4.7	2	Very High
LEGAL AND REGULATORY RISKS			
Inflation	5	1	Very High
Price fluctuation	4.7	2	Very High
Complicated/unstable tax structure	5	1	Very High
SUBCONTRACTOR RISKS			
Lack of skilled labour	5	1	Very High
Improper means of Construction	4.7	2	Very High
Sub-contract failure	5	1	Very High

The table above shows that overall, site accidents, site access, Underestimation of cost, changes in regulation, growth in trade aptitude, inflation, price fluctuation, complicated/unstable tax structure, sub-contract failure, improper means of Construction and lack of skilled labour have a very high impact on the cost of the project. These risks need special consideration as they lead to the failure of the project.

5.3.1.3 Performance Impact Analysis:

The following table shows the level of risks which influence the performance of the construction phase. The consequences of each risk are also presented in the table below:

Table 5.8: Performance Impact Analysis

Type of Risk	Mean	Risk Rank	Risk Level	Consequences
DESIGN RELATED RISKS				
Design process delays	1.7	13	Low	Require direct handling immediately on the spot; performance loss becomes the cost of additional expenditure
Errors and Omissions	2.7	10	Medium	Require to be managed by the executor, loss of performance is quite significant
Inadequate Specifications	2.7	10	Medium	Require to be managed by the executor, loss of performance is quite significant
Loss or Delay or Design Changes	3	9	Medium	Require to be managed by the executor, loss of performance is quite significant
CONSTRUCTION RELATED RISKS				
Quality Problem	2.6	11	Medium	Require to be managed by the executor, loss of performance is quite significant
Site Accidents	5	1	Very High	Errors affect other, require handling by director, very huge performance loss, require special handling
Site Access	4.4	3	High	Failure, low productivity, a significant loss in performance, special handling required

Equipment Failure	4.4	3	High	Failure, low productivity, a significant loss in performance, special handling required
Unavailability of Labor	4	5	High	Failure, low productivity, a major loss in performance, special handling required
Unavailability of equipment	4.7	2	Very High	Errors affect other, require handling by director, very huge performance loss, require special handling

FINANCIAL AND ECONOMIC RISKS

Adequate cash flow	4	5	High	Failure, low productivity, a major loss in performance, special handling required
Delayed payment on the contract	4.7	2	Very High	Errors affect other, require handling by director, very huge performance loss, require special handling
Underestimation of cost	4.3	4	High	Failure, low productivity, a major loss in performance, special handling required
Cost overrun due to schedule delays	4	5	High	Failure, low productivity, a major loss in performance, special handling required
Changes in regulation	4.7	2	Very High	Errors affect other, require handling by director, very huge performance loss, require special handling
Inconsistent application of laws	2.4	12	Low	Require direct handling immediately on the spot, and performance loss becomes the cost of additional expenditure

change in trade aptitude	1.7	13	Low	Require direct handling immediately on the spot, and performance loss becomes the cost of additional expenditure
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LEGAL AND REGULATORY RISKS

Exchange rate fluctuation	1.7	13	Low	Require direct handling immediately on the spot, and performance loss becomes the cost of additional expenditure
Inflation	3.1	8	Medium	Require to be managed by the executor, loss of performance is quite significant
Price fluctuation	3.6	7	High	Failure, low productivity, a major loss in performance, special handling required
Complicated/unstable tax structure	2.4	12	Low	Require direct handling immediately on the spot, and performance loss becomes the cost of additional expenditure
Import restrictions	4.3	4	High	Failure, low productivity, a major loss in performance, special handling required
Problems with permit and license	5	1	Very High	Errors affect other, require handling by director, very huge performance loss, require special handling.

SUBCONTRACTOR RISKS

Lack of skilled labour	5	1	Very High	Errors affect other, require handling by director, very huge performance loss, require special handling.
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Improper cash flow	4.7	2	Very High	Errors affect other, require handling by director, very huge performance loss, require special handling
Lack of expertise	3.8	6	High	Failure, low productivity, a major loss in performance, special handling required
Improper means of Construction	4.7	2	Very High	Errors affect other, require handling by director, very huge performance loss, require special handling
Sub-contract failure	3.8	6	High	Failure, low productivity, a major loss in performance, special handling required

The figure below represents the impact of different risks on performance.

Figure 5.4: Risk Impact on Performance

Design related Risks:

As shown above, out of four Design related risks, three of the risks are of medium level, and one is of low level. Design process delays have a low level of impact on project performance. Design process delays need to be handled immediately on the spot as the performance loss becomes the cost of additional expenditure. Also, inadequate specifications, Loss or Delay or Design Changes and Errors and Omissions are resulting in a moderate level effect on performance which requires significant attention in order to achieve ideal performance and success of the project. Although the impact of these risks is the moderate level, they can lead to the significant loss of performance in a project which will consequently impact the successful execution of the overall project. Since Design related risks have a moderate level of impact on the performance, the managers need to pay attention to these factors

immediately as they will result in a huge loss if not handled properly. Overall, Design related risks have a moderate level of impact on the performance of the project.

Construction-related risks:

In Construction related risks, one Construction related risk is of medium level, three Construction related risks have a high level of impact, and two Construction related risks have a very high impact on the performance of the project. The quality problem contains a moderate level of risk impact on project performance. Quality problems impede the efficiency and effectiveness of the project; thus, this type of risk must be managed by the executor or else it will result in significant performance issue. Also, site access, equipment failure and unavailability of labour contain a high level of risk impact on the performance. Due to the equipment failure, the project will require additional effort and the performance loss is considered significant. Unavailability of labours results in delays which further affect the project's performance. The project managers need to make sure that the substitute or extra labours are available to work in case of availability of labour or else, it will result in major delays and performance issues. Site accidents and unavailability of equipment contain a very high level of risk impact on performance. Site accidents are hazardous for the organisation. The project managers need to ensure safety precaution beforehand to avoid major loss in performance. The probability of site accidents is low, but in case of occurrence, they can have a major influence on the success of the project. Due to the equipment failure, the project will require additional time, energy and cost; thus, the performance loss can be regarded as significant. These risks need to be handled by the directors as they result in a very high level of performance loss of the project, and consequently, these risks will lead to the failure of the project. Overall, Construction related risks have a high level of impact on the performance of the project.

Financial and Economic Risks:

The next category of risks is financial and economic risks. According to the results, two low levels of risk, three high level and two very high levels of risks are detected that have an impact on the performance of the overall project. Inconsistent application of laws and changes in trade aptitude have a low level of risk impact on the performance of the project. The impact of these risk is meaningful, which require immediate consideration or else it will impede the performance of the project. Adequate cash flow, Underestimation of cost and Cost overrun due to scheduled delays have a high level of risk impact on performance.

Underestimation of cost can result in the dissatisfactory performance of the process. The managers must estimate the cost properly as it will result in failure and low productivity of the project. Most importantly, Delayed payment on contract and changes in regulation have a very high level of risk impact on the project's performance. Due to the severity of these two factors, the managers must have better payment cycles to avoid delays in the payment. These risks do not have an impact on the performance but to the overall scope of the project. Thus, these factors need to be handled by the directors. Overall, financial and economic risks have a high level of impact on the performance of the project.

Legal and Regulatory Risks:

The results on Legal and regulatory risks found two low levels of risks, one medium, one high and two very high-level risks and three very high-level risks on the cost of the project. As indicated in the table, exchange rate fluctuation and complicated/ unstable tax structure have a low-risk impact on performance. These are uncontrollable risks, so management cannot do anything about such fluctuations. However, they need to adopt appropriate strategies considering these factors as performance loss is significant. Inflation risk has a medium risk impact on the performance of the project. Inflation results in fluctuation in prices which impact the efficiency of the project. Inflation factor needs to be considered in the risk by the executor as it can result in significant loss of performance. Price fluctuation and import restrictions have a high level of impact on the performance of the project. These risks result in failure, low productivity and major performance loss, thus, require special handling according to the regulations. Most importantly, problems with permit and license contain a very high level of risk on the performance of the project. However, their chances of occurrence are very low, but in case of occurrence, these risks can impede the execution of the project. Overall, legal and regulatory risks have a moderate level of impact on the performance of the project.

Subcontractor Risks:

The next category of risks is subcontractor risks which have a significant impact on the performance of the project. As indicated in the results, three risk factors have a very high level of impact, and two risk factors contain a high level of impact on the performance of the project. Lack of expertise of subcontractor and sub-contractor failure have a high level of impact on performance as it results in the efficiency of the project and it then needs to be done all over again by hiring a new subcontractor. This type of risk needs to be managed by

an executor promptly as it will lead to failure. Improper cash flow, lack of skilled labour and improper means of Construction have a very high-risk impact on the performance of the project. These factors can impact other activities of the project; hence, they need to be handled by the director in order to come out from the huge performance loss. These risks have a very strong impact on the project scope and need to be handled carefully for the success of the project. Overall, subcontractor risks have a very high level of impact on the performance of the project.

Table 5.9: Highest Ranked Risks (PERFORMANCE)

Type of Risk	Mean	Risk Rank	Risk Level
CONSTRUCTION RELATED RISKS			
Site Accidents	5	1	Very High
Unavailability of equipment	4.7	2	Very High
FINANCIAL AND ECONOMIC RISKS			
Delayed payment on contract	4.7	2	Very High
Changes in regulation	4.7	2	Very High
LEGAL AND REGULATORY RISKS			
Problems with permit and license	5	1	Very High
SUBCONTRACTOR RISKS			
Lack of skilled labour	5	1	Very High
Improper cash flow	4.7	2	Very High
Improper means of Construction	4.7	2	Very High

The table above shows that eight factors have a very high level of impact on the project's performance. These factors include site accidents, unavailability of equipment, delayed payment on contract, regulation changes, problems with permit and license, lack of skilled labour, improper cash flow and inappropriate means of Construction. These risks need special consideration as they lead to the failure of the project.

5.3.2 Risk Nature:

Another step of risk analysis is to find out the nature of risk if the risk is controllable or uncontrollable. The researcher provided two options to each risk where one is coded as controllable, and two is coded as uncontrollable. Considering the mean values, the nature of risk is given below in the table.

Table 5.10: *Risk nature*

Type of Risks	Mean	Nature of Risk
DESIGN RELATED RISKS		
Design Process Delays	2	Uncontrollable
Errors and Omissions	1	Controllable
Inadequate Specifications	1	Controllable
Loss or Delay or Design Changes	2	Uncontrollable
CONSTRUCTION RELATED RISKS		
Quality Problem	1	Controllable
Site Accidents	1	Controllable
Site Access	1.3	Controllable
Equipment Failure	1.7	Uncontrollable
Unavailability of Labor	1	Controllable
Unavailability of equipment	1	Controllable
FINANCIAL AND ECONOMIC RISKS		
Adequate cash flow	2	Uncontrollable
Delayed payment on contract	1.7	Uncontrollable
Underestimation of cost	1.3	Controllable
Cost overrun due to schedule delays	2	Uncontrollable
Changes in regulation	2	Uncontrollable
Inconsistent application of laws	1.3	Controllable
change in trade aptitude	1.7	Uncontrollable
LEGAL AND REGULATORY RISKS		

Exchange rate fluctuation	1.7	Uncontrollable
Inflation	2	Uncontrollable
Price fluctuation	2	Uncontrollable
Complicated/unstable tax structure	2	Uncontrollable
Import restrictions	1.7	Uncontrollable
Problems with permit and license	1.3	Controllable
SUBCONTRACTOR RISKS		
Lack of skilled labour	1.3	Controllable
Improper cash flow	2	Uncontrollable
Lack of expertise	1.3	Controllable
Improper means of construction	1.3	Controllable
Sub-contract failure	1.7	Uncontrollable

According to the table, Design related risks are both controllable and uncontrollable. The results show that Design process delays and Loss or Delay or Design Changes cannot be controlled because they design-related risks occur in initial phase and processes can be delayed which are not in control of project managers. However, errors and omission and Inadequate Specifications are regarded as controllable risks which can be controlled during the designing phase.

The results also show that Construction related risks are mostly controllable. Quality Problem, Site access, Site accidents, unavailability of labour and unavailability of equipment can be controlled by formulating appropriate strategies beforehand to avoid their occurrence. The quality team should take care of the quality-related issues in a project or else it will affect the cost, time and performance of the project. Site access and accidents are in control of the project managers of the study. Proper measures should be provided in case of accidental losses. Unavailability of equipment can also be controlled because the project team needs to make sure the availability of equipment beforehand. In case of unavailability, the equipment can be purchased to run the operations successfully. On the other hand, equipment failure is not in control of the project managers. However, they need to ensure that equipment is operative and efficient enough to function during the project.

The nature of Financial and Economic risks are mostly uncontrollable according to the results. The results show that Adequate cash flows, Delayed payment on contract, regulation changes, Cost overrun due to schedule delays and differences in trade aptitude is not in control of the project managers. Changes and delays are unpredictable in the majority of cases. Therefore, such risks cannot be controlled in case of commercial, residential and infrastructural projects included in the study. In contrary, Underestimation of cost and Inconsistent application of laws are in control of the managers. They need to conduct proper planning before the execution of the project to avoid such risks.

The nature of Legal and Regulatory risks are mostly uncontrollable according to the results of the study because they are in control of legal and regulatory authority, and a company must adhere to it. The results show that Exchange rate fluctuation, inflation, price fluctuations, Complicated/unstable tax structure and import restrictions are regarded as uncontrollable risks. These risks have an impact not only on the project but also on the overall economy and businesses. However, Problems with permit and license can be controlled.

The results also show that Subcontractor risks are a mixture of controllable and uncontrollable risks. Lack of skilled labours, lack of expertise and improper means of Construction can be controlled before or during the project. Labours and resources can be increased, changed or replaced during the project. However, improper cash flow and Sub-contract failure cannot be controlled during the project. Such type of risks can cause a considerable loss of time, cost and performance.

5.3.3 Risk Allocation:

After the identification and assessment of risks, the next step is to allocate the risk. Risk allocation involves assigning management responsibility and accountability for risks. Four options were provided to the respondents, which include owner, consultant, contractor, and shared. The risks are allocated by giving the percentage to owner, consultant, contractor, and shared to find out the level of accountability assigned to the risk. For the purpose of the research, Table 4.11 provides the details of risk allocation related to the projects.

Table 5.11 – Risk Allocation

Type of Risks	Owner	Consultant	Contractor	Shared
DESIGN RELATED RISKS				

Design Process Delays	0	100%	0	0
Errors and Omissions	70%	0	0	30%
Inadequate Specifications	100%	0	0	0
Loss or Delay or Design Changes	0	0	0	100%

CONSTRUCTION RELATED RISKS

Quality Problem	0	30%	70%	0
Site Accidents	0	0	100%	0
Site Access	0	0	100%	0
Equipment Failure	0	0	100%	0
Unavailability of Labor	30%	0	70%	0
Unavailability of equipment	30%	0	70%	0

FINANCIAL AND ECONOMIC RISKS

Adequate cash flow	100%	0	0	0
Delayed payment on contract	70%	30%	0	0
Underestimation of cost	0	0	100%	0
Cost overrun due to schedule delays	0	0	70%	30%
Changes in regulation	0	0	0	100%
Inconsistent application of laws	0	0	30%	70%
change in trade aptitude	0	0	70%	30%

LEGAL AND REGULATORY RISKS

Exchange rate fluctuation	0	0	30%	70%
Inflation	0	0	0	100%
Price fluctuation	30%	0	70%	0
Complicated/unstable tax structure	0	0	100%	0
Import restrictions	0	0	30%	70%

Problems with permit and license	0	0	30%	70%
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SUBCONTRACTOR RISKS

Lack of skilled labor	0	0	70%	30%
Improper cash flow	70%	0	0	30%
Lack of expertise	0	0	100%	0
Improper means of construction	0	0	100%	0
Sub-contract failure	0	30%	70%	0

According to the results shown in the table, the approach towards risk allocation is reviewed below for each one:

Design Related Risks:

According to the table, Design related risks are allocated to different parties.

- Design Process Delays

The survey result showed that risk related to design process delays is assigned to the consultant. The design process sometimes results in delays, errors or mistakes and consultant must assume this risk according to the study.

- Errors and Omission

Errors and omission risk is allocated to both owner and shared. However, the owner is majorly responsible for this risk.

- Inadequate Specifications:

The result showed that insufficient specification risk should be assigned to the owner.

- Loss or Delay or Design Changes:

The survey shows that it is sharing risk and all the parties should be responsible for the loss, delay or change in Design.

Construction-related risks:

According to the table, Construction related risks are majorly allocated to contractors.

- Quality Problem:

The results show that contractors and consultant are responsible for the quality problems in Construction. They allocate the task to themselves. However, quality problem risk is majorly allocated to contractors of the project.

- Site accidents:

The site accidents risk has very high importance as it results in a major loss of the project. The site accidents risk is allocated to the contractors of the project. Only contractors must assume the accidental related risk.

- Site Access:

The survey results showed that site access risk is allocated to the contractors. Contractors tend to rush projects to save time or money, but this risk can be very hazardous.

- Equipment Failure:

According to the results, the risk of an equipment failure is allocated to the contractors.

- Unavailability of labour:

The results showed that the risk is shared between the contractor and owner. However, the contractor is majorly responsible for this risk.

- Unavailability of Equipment:

According to the table, unavailability of equipment risk is shared between the contractor and owner. However, the contractor is majorly responsible for this risk.

Financial and Economic Risk:

According to the table, financial and economic risk is mostly shared between parties.

- Adequate cash flow:

This risk depends on the level of vulnerability of a company's receivables and payables to the potential differences. The risk is completely allocated to the owner as the owner is responsible for the major decision making regarding cash flows.

- Delayed payment on contract:

This risk is allocated to the owner and consultant. However, the owner is majorly responsible for the payment delays.

- Underestimation of cost:

This risk has a major impact on the cost of the project and is designated to the contractor of the project.

- Cost overrun due to schedule delays:

The results showed that the risk of cost overrun is allocated to the contractor and shared. However, the contractor is majorly responsible for this risk.

- Regulation changes:

The result indicates that changes are regulation is a sharing risk.

- Inconsistent application of laws:

The risk is a sharing risk as well as allocated to the contractor. Contractors are majorly responsible for this risk.

- Change in trade aptitude:

According to the result, 70% of the risk is allocated to the contractor, whereas 30% is a sharing risk.

Legal and Regulatory Risk:

All parties majorly share legal and regulatory risks because these risks are uncontrollable, and they have a huge impact on the project.

- Exchange rate fluctuation:

The risk of exchange rate fluctuation is majorly a shared risk, and 30% of the risk is allocated to the contractor as well.

- Inflation:

Inflation risk is shared by all the parties of the project.

- Price fluctuation:

According to the results, 30% of the risk is allocated to the owner and 70% of the risk is allocated to the contractor. It can be assumed that in the case of higher prices, the owner tends to assume more risk, and in case of lower prices, contractors are more willing to undertake the risk of price fluctuation.

- Complicated / unstable tax structure:

This risk is the responsibility of the contractor, thus, allocated to the contractor of the project.

- Import restrictions:

Import restriction is majorly shared by all parties; however, 30% of the risk is allocated to the contractor.

- Problems with permits and licenses:

Problems with permits and licenses risk are majorly shared by all parties; however, 30% of the risk is allocated to the contractor of the project.

Subcontractor Risk:

As shown earlier, subcontractor risks have a very high impact on the cost, time and performance of the project. These risks are majorly allocated to the contractor of the project.

- **Lack of skilled labour:**

Lack of skilled labour risk is allocated 70% to the contractor and 30% to the sharing basis.

- **Improper cash flow:**

Owner is majorly responsible for the improper cash flows, which delays the payments. According to the results, the risk is allocated 70% to the owner and 30% to the sharing basis.

- **Lack of expertise:**

Contractors are responsible for the lack of expertise of subcontractors.

- **Improper means of Construction:**

Contactors are responsible for the improper means of Construction.

- **Sub-contract failure:**

This risk is shared between the consultant and the contractor. 30% of the risk is allocated to the consultant; on the other hand, 70% of the risk is allocated to the contractor.

5.3.4 Risk Response:

After the identification, assessment and allocation of the risk, the next step is to provide the response of each risk. Risk response is a crucial step for risk management, based on different consideration, for each risk factor, different risk measurements are chosen from various angles. Considering the results of risk identification, risk assessment, risk nature and risk allocation, risk responses are determined. After the determination of each response, the execution of plans to manage the risk and to reduce losses is executed to generate better outcomes. The researcher provided four responses to the risk, which include risk retention, risk reduction, risk transfer and not applicable. These options are coded as 1, 2, 3 and 4, respectively. According to the mean values of the responses, each risk response is given in the table.

Table 5.12: *Risk Responses*

Type of Risks	Mean	Risk Response
DESIGN RELATED RISKS		
Design Process delays	4.0	Not applicable
Errors and Omissions	2.0	Risk reduction
Inadequate Specifications	3.3	Risk Transfer
Loss or Delay or Design Changes	3.0	Risk Transfer
CONSTRUCTION RELATED RISKS		
Quality Problem	1.0	Risk retention
Site Accidents	3.0	Risk Transfer
Site Access	2.7	Risk Transfer
Equipment Failure	2.0	Risk Reduction
Unavailability of Labor	2.0	Risk Reduction
Unavailability of equipment	1.9	Risk Reduction

FINANCIAL AND ECONOMIC RISKS		
Adequate cash flow	3.0	Risk Transfer
Delayed payment on the contract	2.7	Risk Transfer
Underestimation of cost	1.7	Risk Reduction
Cost overrun due to schedule delays	2.3	Risk Reduction
Changes in regulation	3.7	Not Applicable
Inconsistent application of laws	2.3	Risk Reduction
change in trade aptitude	1.9	Risk Reduction
LEGAL AND REGULATORY RISKS		
Exchange rate fluctuation	2.7	Risk Transfer
Inflation	4.0	Not applicable
Price fluctuation	3.3	Risk Transfer
Complicated/unstable tax structure	3.3	Risk Transfer
Import restrictions	3.3	Risk Transfer
Problems with permit and license	2.6	Risk Transfer
SUBCONTRACTOR RISKS		
Lack of skilled labour	1.3	Risk-retention
Improper cash flow	3.0	Risk Transfer
Lack of expertise	2.3	Risk reduction
Improper means of Construction	1.6	Risk reduction
Sub-contract failure	2.0	Risk reduction

Design related risks:

The table above provides the risk responses for each type of risk. In Design related risks, different answers are given to each risk. Design process delays cannot be responded with any strategy as delays are unexpected and unplanned. Errors and omissions are responded with

risk reduction. The contingency plan and strict terms and conditions may avoid the chance of occurrence of this risk. Inadequate specifications and Loss or Delay or Design Changes are the type of risks that cannot be eliminated. According to the results, they need to be transferred to the other parties who can manage these risks. In this case, the project management team does not possess enough knowledge and expertise to deal with inadequate specifications and Loss or Delay or Design Changes risks. Therefore, these risks are transferred to the parties with enough knowledge and expertise in order to avoid the loss.

Construction-related risks:

In Construction related risks, different responses are given to each risk. According to the results, the quality problem requires the response of risk retention. Risk-retention refers to taking responsibility for a particular risk instead of transferring it to another party. The project team needs to handle quality problems to avoid further losses immediately. The response for site accidents and site access is risk transfer. These type of risks are transferred to the insurance companies, and then the insurance companies handle these risks. According to the results, the response for equipment failure, unavailability of labour and unavailability of equipment is risk reduction. By making the proper changes in activities and resources, the chance of risk occurrence is diminished.

Financial and economic Risks:

According to the results, adequate cash flow and delayed payment on contract require the response of risk transfer. Changes in regulation is an uncontrollable risk, and the answer is not applicable. Underestimation of cost, Cost overrun due to schedule delays, Inconsistent application of laws and changes in trade aptitude require risk reduction response. The measurement objective is to reduce the likelihood of occurrence of such risks by adopting strict terms and condition and checking. In implementing the measures to mitigate the risk, it is essential to reduce certain risk to an acceptable level.

Legal and Regulatory Risks:

Legal and regulatory risks are uncontrollable risks; however, they can be responded by using the right strategy. Inflation is not in control, and nothing can be done for the increase or decrease in the inflation rate. Thus, no response is given according to the survey results. However, exchange rate fluctuations, price fluctuation, Complicated/unstable tax structure, import restrictions and the problem with permits and licenses require risk transfer response.

Since, these risks are uncontrollable and can lead to a considerable loss of cost, time and performance, and the risk is transferred to the insurance companies to avoid the financial risks.

Subcontractor Risks:

As indicated earlier, subcontractor risks have a significant impact on the cost, time and performance of the project; these risks should be appropriately handled and responded with the proper strategy. According to the results, the lack of skilled labour risk is responded with risk retention strategy. The company takes responsibility for this risk instead of transferring it to another party. It is crucial to arrange substitute labours who are skilled to avoid such risk. Improper cash flow is a financial risk. Thus, it requires risk transfer response where the risk is transferred to the insurance company to handle the financial risk. Lack of expertise, improper means of construction and subcontractor failure need risk reduction response. The contingency plan and strict terms and conditions may avoid the chance of occurrence of this risk.

5.3.5 Risk Management Matrix:

The table below provides the summary of risk assessment, nature of risk, actual risk allocation and risk response.

Table 5.13: *Risk Management Matrix*

Risk Identification	Risk Classification			Risk Nature	Risk Allocation	Risk Response
	Risk Impact					
Type of Risk	Time	Cost	Performance			
DESIGN RELATED RISKS						
Design process delays	High	Low	Low	Uncontrollable	Consultant	Not applicable
Errors and Omissions	High	Medium	Medium	Controllable	Owner and Shared	Risk reduction
Inadequate Specifications	Medium	Very low	Medium	Controllable	Owner	Risk Transfer

Loss or Delay or Design Changes	Medium	Medium	Medium	Uncontrollable	Shared	Risk Transfer
CONSTRUCTION RELATED RISKS						
Quality Problem	Low	High	Medium	Controllable	Consultant and Contractor	Risk retention
Site Accidents	High	Very High	Very High	Controllable	Contractor	Risk Transfer
Site Access	High	Very High	High	Controllable	Contractor	Risk Transfer
Equipment Failure	High	Medium	High	Uncontrollable	Contractor	Risk Reduction
Unavailability of Labor	Very High	Very Low	High	Controllable	Owner and Contractor	Risk Reduction
Unavailability of equipment	Very High	Low	Very High	Controllable	Owner and Contractor	Risk Reduction
FINANCIAL AND ECONOMIC RISKS						
Adequate cash flow	Medium	Low	High	Uncontrollable	Owner	Risk Transfer
Delayed payment on the contract	Very High	Medium	Very High	Uncontrollable	Owner and Consultant	Risk Transfer
Underestimation of cost	High	Very High	High	Controllable	Contractor	Risk Reduction
Cost overrun due to schedule delays	Very High	High	High	Uncontrollable	Contractor and Shared	Risk Reduction
Changes in regulation	High	Very High	Very High	Uncontrollable	Shared	Not Applicable
Inconsistent application of laws	Low	Medium	Low	Controllable	Contractor and Shared	Risk Reduction
change in trade aptitude	High	Very High	Low	Uncontrollable	Contractor and Shared	Risk Reduction
LEGAL AND REGULATORY RISKS						

Exchange rate fluctuation	Medium	High	Low	Uncontrollable	Contractor and Shared	Risk Transfer
Inflation	Low	Very High	Medium	Uncontrollable	Shared	Not applicable
Price fluctuation	Medium	Very High	High	Uncontrollable	Owner and Contractor	Risk Transfer
Complicated/unstable tax structure	High	Very High	Low	Uncontrollable	Contractor	Risk Transfer
Import restrictions	High	High	High	Uncontrollable	Contractor and Shared	Risk Transfer
Problems with permit and license	Very High	High	Very High	Controllable	Contractor and Shared	Risk Transfer
SUBCONTRACTOR RISKS						
Lack of skilled labour	Very high	Very High	Very High	Controllable	Contractor and Shared	Risk-retention
Improper cash flow	Very High	High	Very High	Uncontrollable	Owner and Shared	Risk Transfer
Lack of expertise	High	Medium	High	Controllable	Contractor	Risk reduction
Improper means of Construction	Very High	Very High	Very High	Controllable	Contractor	Risk reduction
Sub-contract failure	Very High	Very High	High	Uncontrollable	Consultant and Contractor	Risk reduction

5.3.6 Commutative Risk Factors Ranking

In this research, the researcher considered the impact of time, cost and performance of the risk factor. The table below represents the highest risk factors calculated based on the findings of the overall impact of time, cost and performance. This is calculated by considering the mean value of each factor.

Type of Risk	TIME	COST	PERFORMANCE	TOTAL MEAN	RANK
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DESIGN RELATED RISKS

Design process delays	4	1.7	1.7	2.47	23
Errors and Omissions	3.7	2.7	2.7	3.03	18
Inadequate Specifications	2.7	1	2.7	2.13	25
Loss or Delay or Design Changes	2.7	3.3	3	3.00	19

CONSTRUCTION RELATED RISKS

Quality Problem	1.7	4	2.6	2.77	22
Site Accidents	3.6	4.7	5	4.43	5
Site Access	3.6	5	4.4	4.33	7
Equipment Failure	4.3	3	4.4	3.90	10
Unavailability of Labor	4.7	1	4	3.23	17
Unavailability of equipment	4.7	2.2	4.7	3.87	11

FINANCIAL AND ECONOMIC RISKS

Adequate cash flow	3.3	1.6	4	2.97	21
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Delayed payment on contract	4.7	2.9	4.7	4.10	9
Underestimation of cost	3.6	5	4.3	4.30	8
Cost overrun due to schedule delays	5	4.1	4	4.37	6
Changes in regulation	4.4	4.7	4.7	4.60	3
Inconsistent application of laws	2.4	2.7	2.4	2.50	24
change in trade aptitude	3.7	4.7	1.7	3.37	15

LEGAL AND REGULATORY RISKS

Exchange rate fluctuation	2.9	4.4	1.7	3	20
Inflation	1.7	5	3.1	3.27	16
Price fluctuation	2.9	4.7	3.6	3.73	12
Complicated/unstable tax structure	3.6	5	2.4	3.67	13
Import restrictions	4.3	4.3	4.3	4.30	8
Problems with permit and license	5	3.6	5	4.53	4

SUBCONTRACTOR RISKS

Lack of skilled labor	5	5	5	5	1
Improper cash flow	4.7	3.6	4.7	4.33	7
Lack of expertise	3.6	2.9	3.8	3.43	14
Improper means of construction	5	4.7	4.7	4.8	2
Sub-contract failure	5	5	3.8	4.60	3

After calculating the cumulative mean of time, cost and performance, it can be observed from the table above that Lack of skilled labors, Improper means of construction and sub-contract failure are the highest risk factors which also belong to the category of sub-contractor risks. It is then followed by the risk factors including Problems with permit and license, site accidents, Cost overrun due to schedule delays, site access, improper cash flow, etc. Considering that highest three risk factors belong to the category of sub-contractor risk, lack of skilled labors and improper means of constructions are controllable risks, however, sub-contract failure is the uncontrollable which has a huge impact on time, cost and performance of the project.

5.4 Questionnaire Analysis 2

5.4.1 Introduction

The data for this questionnaire has been gathered by carrying out the semi-structured interviews described in Chapter 3 and 4, and will be analysed in this section question by question under heading 5.4.2 "Analysis of Interviews". This part also includes an assessment of the secondary data supplied by an analysis (here) of the Literature Review in Chapter 2.

5.4.2 Analysis of Interviews

As cited in the division above, interviews were carried out to demonstrate the source of primary data for this research questionnaire. Each interview was half an hour or less.

Interviewees were inquired about questions that were applicable to meeting the research Objectives. There are total four objectives (see Chapter 1.6). To achieve objective one, there were five questions to be asked in an interview. Similarly, to satisfy the second objective, there was a set of five questions that were inquired from the interviewees. Remaining objectives were fulfilled by with literature (secondary data) or the questionnaire one.

Interviewees responded to the statements from a pre-prepared questionnaire which is attached in Appendix D-1. There were 35 eligible interviews, few with executives from building contractors and others from the consultants, architects and suppliers etc working as an SME's individually or on large projects in project teams. These stakeholders are the significant shareholders in the economy of the UK at present. The professionals were picked out for an interview in order to gain from their current relevant risk management technical knowledge relating to the projects under construction or completed recently in the UK.

In the next sections of this chapter, analysis of the statements is put down, and further details, such as summary of the answers can also be found in the text. The questionnaire is attached in appendix.

5.4.2.1 Risk Management Process in the UK construction industry

The purpose of this section with its composition of 5 questions (see Appendix D-1) is to inquire the risk management processes being adopted in development projects which will be considered as the benchmark to develop or risk management framework.

Statement 1

An overview of risk management in the project lifecycle?

Analysis of Responses

This question asks about the detail of risk management process, which is being accomplished in the project and the particulars of risk management process steps. It also unveils the

priorities that risk managers have given to certain risk factors which are of high probability and impact. About 59% of the risk managers/analysts risk manager did not have any idea of risk management process, and they take decisions solely on their experience. 13% of them are identifying the risks, but are not aware about the actual framework or process to eradicate the risk. Moreover, 2.85% (which is just one respondent) did not expose the actual risk management summary in the project, and he gave his perception of what should be the exercise which includes engagement of stakeholders, and the process demands participation from all the levels of the organisation in risk management. The 25.15% risk managers gave an embracing answer to this question. They referred that time, cost, quality and efficiency of the task are the significant considerations to avoid risk threat, which can be diluted by demanding every stakeholder on an individual platform by means of workshop for example, so that every risk can be entered and can have numerous impressions on its exposures.

Figure 5.4: *Statement 1 Analysis*

Statement 2

Can you demonstrate if there is any flow chart to the risk management process hierarchy?

Analysis of Responses

In this statement, interviewees were inquired about the RMP plan/hierarchy which they implement in the organisation. 83% of the risk managers do not record/register any risks, mostly they are either working individually or working in small teams for the private client. 13% of risk executive mentioned about the process that how they recognise and register their risks in the organisation, whereas, 4% of risk executives gave an arrow based framework which initiate from planning and closes at monitoring, which is the most basic form of any risk management process. It is found that there shall be a formal process for the organisation for risk management that how they need to identify, analysis, control and then monitor. Each stage has versatile techniques that should be followed for the fortunate implementation of risk management process. Organisations should preserve a risk register which has all the items about the preceding, current and upcoming risks which consequence the project.

Figure 5.5: Statement 2 Analysis

Statement 3

What are the standards and measures you take here for the process of?

Risk identification, Assessment and Management?

Analysis of Responses

This statement purpose is to inquire about formal methods of executing each step of risk management process in perspective projects. All the risk executives gave the answers with the best of their knowledge and practice. 77% of the risk managers only identify the risk, and there is no formal process of assessment and management. 11% of risk managers were identifying and analysing risk and involving their stakeholders to mitigate or transfer the risk at a given time. 12% of the managers do not do anything at all.

There has to be some process which should be oriented or taken over (APM, ARM, BS ISO 31000, etc.) to generate a formal process of quantified risk management in the organisation. It is impossible to deal with all the risk without registering them, analysing them, and make everyone mindful about it in the organisation, and then monitoring it until the finish where it gets mitigated or transferred successfully. To register and inquire more, risks workshops, site meeting, brainstorming sessions that include stakeholders' meetings, monthly meetings or weekly client meetings can be arranged to take hold of risks. These meeting could have an agenda of past, present and future risks and their responsible stakeholders.

Figure 5.7: Statement 3 Analysis

Statement 4

Any special risk management tools or techniques which are adopted, generic, or sector-specific?

Analysis of Responses

Aim of this statement is to inquire about the tools and techniques used in projects performing risk management. 69% of the risk managers said that they do not use any tool; they only used their experience to identify the risk which is basically a technique. 21% of the risk managers said that they do not do anything. Whereas 10% do not know what are risk management tools and techniques.

Most common risk management tools used in developed economies are ARM, Oracle Risk Analysis, Risk AMP, these are quantitative software-controlled tools which are applied effectively. Risk management handbook techniques which can be very useful and gentle to understand and explain are fishbone diagram and PESTLE analysis which can be confronted easily in workshops and meeting as everyone is used to with them.

Figure 5.8: *Statement 4 Analysis*

Statement 5

(a) Do all [responsible] employees understand the appropriate Risk definitions as per their roles and responsibility?

(b) How is Risk monitoring passed on to the employees?

Analysis of Responses

None of the risk managers reported any method in this question. There have been no formal recognition of risk manager role or definition process, due to lack of funds, knowledge, and resources. This question details about the awareness and participation of employees and their apprehension of roles in risk management process. It also demonstrates the information flow of all the risks in the project or company. Every employee should be made aware about what their responsibilities are, they shall be given duties with respect to their role in risk management process and they shall be tagged and monitored by the person in charge of their performance.

Statement 6

How can you establish this project follows the Best Practice?

Analysis of Responses

Preceding experience of likely projects determines the best practice to perform, this was the answer of all the respondents, it does not mean that they had the best results in previous and current projects, but at least they have learned from their last project. This statement aims to find out how the risk executives can be guaranteed that they have the risk management process at its best of knowledge. To duplicate the practice, they should have good determining end results to register to exercise them further and make them an illustrate for other projects. Environment is built doctored up to the limit but still, it demands maturity, the success of the previous projects establishes that they have been on best practice as further projects can only be guaranteed by finishing the last project successfully. Experience matter, and it acts as a vital role but still every project is unique on its own, so it requires particular attention.

5.4.2.2 Effect of Organisations Culture and Maturity on Risk Management Process (RMP)

This part is founded on the answers from the next set of five questions (see Appendix D1). It attempts to inquire information about culture and maturity level has consequences on the overall performance of risk management process on its implementation. This division also entails existence of two-way communication on Risk Management Process in an organisation.

Statement 7

How are your project's risks being:

(a) monitored?

(b) managed?

Analysis of Responses

There is no formal procedure or framework is deployed or adopted at any stage of the construction project life cycle as per the 93% of the respondents. All risks are dealt on their own independently as per the need. 7% of the respondents have adopted a formal procedure to monitor and manage the process of supervising and managing of the identified risks, which are gathered from weekly/monthly meetings. Once the risks are identified, it is vital to keep their records up to date, the working carried out on it and compiling the information from the participants who are held creditworthy for dealing with it. In order to cut down its chance and intensity, it is essential to recall the identified risks in planned meetings with the client and all the stakeholders to demonstrate the operation and process to deal with its vulnerability. Risk executives normally keep in touch with every accountable person of allocated risks to keep their risk registers up-to-date. It is one of the most essential aspects of best practice.

Figure 5.11: Statement 7 Analysis

Statement 8

Does Risk Management is considered on a team level or an individual basis?

Analysis of Responses

The idea of this statement is to investigate about the risk management process consolidation in the organisation, that on what tiers and which team members are associated in this process. It is best that every stakeholder regard risk as its obligation and own the risks that are generated and associated to him. 95% of the respondents reported that they do all the risk management on the individual basis and there is no process of passing the information or sharing any risk data with their team as they have 0 understanding of the risk management process. It is suggested, for the most beneficial results, it is important that it should be implemented on all the levels of the company and risks shall be integrated in every part of usual meetings with stakeholders. Optimism bias can only produce more risks instead of reducing the current risks, so each soul should evaluate and report his threats to the responsible person.

Figure 5.12: Statement 8 Analysis

Statement 9

What steps do you perform to preserve impetus and application of all Risk Management principles in your organisation/projects?

Analysis of Responses

Purpose of this statement is to demonstrate the idea about the motivation and risk management process implementation throughout the project or organisation. 84% of the respondents reported that it is impossible to implement the risk management throughout the project life cycle. 7% of them were keen in implementing throughout but they had fewer resources and time take this responsibility. Maintaining the people devoted and engaged to identify and counter risks is an important part. Everyone should realise about what they are doing and how will it welfare our company/project. It is the responsibility of respective executive (commonly risk manager) to keep a tab on everyone and demonstrate his attention to risk management process. It is not possible to keep up the relevance of this process if stakeholder or employee or team member is confused about its advantages and productive outcomes. Remaining 9% had no idea if this can be implemented or not in the project lifecycle.

Figure 5.13: Statement 9 Analysis

Statement 10

How do you make sure that staff react equally, and positively to their roles/ inputs to the Risk Management process?

Analysis of Responses

This statement depicts the dedication of people and the potency of their role in risk management process. This question was on another level, 90% of the respondents, as there is no involvement of the team in the risk management process. Additionally, it is vital that how active the staff is to risk management process steps; it demonstrates their gratification and understanding its implication for productivity. Only one respondent said that if the team have some issues, it is the duty of risk executives to stream the information in a comfortable medium. Stakeholders can make risk executive job relaxed if they highlight the threats on their own and report, most of the time a responsible person is not able to concentrate all over, so it is his team members responsibility to highlight him if they determine something not usual. It is found with the experience of respondents that leaders should behave decently and address people with a chocolate not with the stick to minimising the communication gap.

Figure 5.14: Statement 10 Analysis

Statement 11

- (a) What are the financial effects of your risk demonstration, and**
- (b) is there an uninterrupted loop within your monitoring systems to analyse costs, and**
- (c) do you deliberately evaluate deviation from a set level of risk acceptability?**

Analysis of Responses

Reason of this specific statement is to investigate about the financial welfare of Risk Management Process. 65% of the risk managers unable were able to give a satisfactory answer or recall any example where they have performed risk management considering this aspect It also enquires the recurring cycle which computes the cost to individual risk, affect on the project and any baseline value set for the amputate value of cost for individual risk. 35% of risk managers gave different answers in terms of their own methods of analysing the financial impacts, in which they demonstrated that each project should have the record of the risk management, and it should have some figure to be announced for a list or any detailed risk which can turn a baseline value to address with that risk. Always when dealing with unavoidable risk, it should record the value and equate it with the baseline terms to observe the difference if this becomes the practice, so it will be convenient to estimate similar risks for projects. Optimism bias shall not be believed as it is the first step of failure; it will not

cost a lot to compute and evaluate any threat rather than risking the complete project or any action on its chance of finishing on time and within the given budget.

Figure 5.15: Statement 11 Analysis

Statement 12

How do you measure the risk culture, any method?

Analysis of Responses

This statement inquiries from interviewees that they should mention any conventional or unconventional methods of analysing risk culture in the organisation. It is easy to take over any process, but it is important to get the feedback from the souls to modify the process to its achieve the desired results. Knowledge to risk management is required to analyse the maturity level, there should be a procedure or a framework in place first before the risk managers can quantify the adoption and maturity implanting risk management. None of the risk managers have any procedure of measuring the risk culture in their organisation. Every member desire to find feedback of their action or performance to get propelled of their activities and it shows a positive result, and they enrich their performances. Motivating others costs nothing, but its outcomes are in privilege of project/company. Where risk management associates every member in the project, so it should be drawn and skewed maintaining the comfort of adoption, which is only possible if we ask for feedback.

Figure 5.16: Statement 12 Analysis

5.2.3 Impact of risk management process on numerous Tiers of Construction Industry/project/orgainsation

This section of the questionnaire consists of two statements (see Appendix D1). The aim of these statements is to identify the tier (clients, contractors, designers and supply chain) which has the most exposure to the negative event if formal or informal means of Risk Management Process (RMP) are not adopted.

Statement 13

What are the outcomes of insufficient risk identification, assessment and risk management in the honour of supply chain partners, especially smaller companies with have no well-established risk management culture?

Analysis of Responses

This statement directs to investigate the outcomes for not implementing/performing/counting risk management process by the SMEs associated in the project. All the respondents are mindful of the impact of insufficient risk management as a conventional practice, but they have no process in place. No one wishes the overspent of cost and time, accurate cost estimation is the key to keeping contingency (neglecting optimism bias). If the supplier lets down a facility within a schedule and cost, his future jobs can be at risk, so it will be his

reputation. Similarly, the client will also lose his profit and time of completion; the stakeholders will rethink trusting the supplier and client again, and the overall project will lose its charm.

Statement 14

Evaluate each of the tiers/levels according to the impact.

Analysis of Responses

Aim of this statement is to investigate about the significance of Risk Management Process (RMP) on all the stakeholders in the project. None of them can be prioritised as the most crucial because if any of them lets down, it is the downfall of the whole project. Clients should have a sophisticated assessment criteria as they are the one suffering at the end. Everyone else will also get affected and it will be a negative event for the complete project. All the stakeholders should take their part seriously, to analyse risk and perform daily assessment and management, as it can result in the destruction of resources on the project life cycle. All the respondents are aware about the impact on stakeholders but as said above, they have no knowledge, less resources and unavailability of any relevant framework to implement the risk management process.

5.5 Comparative Analysis of Primary and Secondary Data Collected

Risk management is a formal process, there is no way you can get the maximum results with only doing the process for once in a project lifecycle, or just implementing partial process at a given time. As per the theory the stake of SME's is significant in the economy, but their knowledge and costiveness of managing risks with appropriate risk management procedure is nearly zero.

All the risk management procedure and frameworks are implemented on larger scale project and by large companies who can afford to appoint a proper person who can manage the risk procedure, educate the staff and generate the results to show the massive gain or time and cost in a particular project.

It is not always a conventional procedure of implementing the theory; sometimes the practical events make history. Risk Management Process (RMP) has been reported in the number of different methods and steps by other researchers. It is always not rightful claim that either of them is accurate as all of them are being implemented and being used in decision making for many years.

Best practices follow the fundamentals of all conventional theories and implement them by tailoring the process that suits their needs and projects by adopting different techniques. Occasionally it is an utterly new pattern, and sometimes they stick to the textbook. All formulas are relevant until they are advantageous to the project.

5.6 Summary

In this chapter, analysis and results of the primary and secondary data are symbolised. Next chapter will detail the development of user friends and easy to understand risk management framework for the SME's in the UK construction industry. In summary, best practices are exercised and validated where we have required resources, and where resources are scarce, all conclusions are drawn on the experience of risk managers or directors.

CHAPTER 6

RISK MANAGEMENT FRAMEWORK

6.1 Introduction

This heading is all about the constitution of RMF for the SME's in the UK construction industry. The framework suggests at enhancing the handling of critical threats factors in the UK construction industry where SME's are involved, to enhance their productivity. It depends on the deductive reasoning of the determination and results from the preceding sections besides the conclusions of the literature recaps. Thus it contains the merger of the most beneficial practices found by full literary study and the research determinations.

6.2 Intellectual for the formulation of the risk management framework for SME's in the UK Construction Industry

The research finding from the questionnaire surveys (Chapter 5) for the SME's in the UK construction industry considers that RM in construction projects is frequently conducted with unsatisfactory and that SME's in the UK construction industries. Previous studies and the researchers have detailed that miserable RM is one the significant grounds for unacceptable quality; cost and time overrun. What is more, piteous risk management is distinguished as per World Bank is accountable for overruns in most of the construction projects (Zhang, 2005). In contrast, particularly the leading cause for failed project conveyance in the UK is the deficiency of organized risk management and its framework, mainly for SME's.

Dozens of risks inhabit during the development or stages of the construction project, and they dissent as per the project character, the contract length and the procurement method. This study chiefly mainly for the SME's and their projects in the UK construction industry. Handling risks throughout the lifecycle of a construction project is crucial for the project, if not more critical and complicated than threats in a particular phase. Furthermore, the endeavours where the number of SME's are associated is being observed constituting between the most riskiest construction projects, as a consequence of their length of built period, quality pertain and potential cost overrun (Hashem, Guggemos, 2015).

The interviews with the representatives of SME's detailed that in the present time there is no commonly followed managing risk framework for SME's in construction industry. The primary idea of this thesis is to generate a RMF that could supply a baseline for the SME's

construction industry: stakeholders, contractors and management consultants to handle major risks linked to the construction projects, particularly throughout the project life cycle.

6.3 Development of the risk management framework for the SME's in the UK construction industry

To originate a complete framework, it is highly legitimate to develop on a present framework (Bassioni, 2005). Contrasting rules can be embraced for the generation of a solid framework. This study has utilized the pursuing key rationale for the formulation of the RMF:

- Critiquing current developments, working and principals of construction risk management.
- Analyzing the extinct written material on RM process; RM procedure and methods.
- Utilizing suitable data accumulation methods.
- Establishing subsisting RMF, rather than 'recreating the wheel.'
- Constituting current risk management instruments which are currently flourishing in developed countries
- Intending to furnish pragmatic leads for practitioners engaged with or for SME's.

Compiling the evaluation of risk management frameworks and cognitive process in chapter 2, a cosmopolitan risk management framework is generated, the detailed framework is in Figure 6.1. The suggested framework (Figure 6.1) complies the paradigm of the universal RMF It comprises of five discrete steps: risk management planning, risk identification, risk analysis, risk response planning, and risk monitoring and review. Their assigned definitions for every one of these steps are relying on a questionnaire survey and interviews determinations of this study over and above results out of literature critique. They are distinguished in the succeeding sections.

Figure 6.1: Risk Management Framework for SME's in the UK Construction Industry

6.4 Guidelines for Application of Framework

The risk management framework roadmap is detailed in this section; the particular objective is to guarantee efficient management of adverse events in SME's of the UK construction industry, it can be employed throughout the complete project timeline (from planning to handover of construction). These guidance extend data to project managers, risk managers, company directors (sole traders) and project teams, considering clients, contractors and consultants, with the management of the risks obligations in the succeeding patterns: detailing an authentic guide to undertake the project risk management tasks; offering methods and tools for risk management, and allowing direction on how to pre-plan actions to risks. The framework comprises five phases, as talk about beneath.

6.4.1 Project Risk Management Planning (RMP) for SME's in the UK Construction Industry

The first phase of the framework presents the advancement, planning and implementing risk management jobs for projects. This stage increases the potential of accomplishment for the rest of the steps of the framework. Project executive should admit the obligation for and applause of the risk management planning by the mutual understanding with the project team members and the accord the funder of the project. The risk management planning concedes the result or milestones, denoted to as the risk management plan, which depicts the actual plan for risk management execution. It is a beneficial recording that the risk management plan should not comprise predetermined risks nor their matching reaction tasks. The risk management planning of the suggested framework includes the following steps, but are not limited to the proceeding steps:

- **Risk management methodology:** Depict the methods, tools, and data records that can be utilized to attempt risk management in the project lifecycle. It primarily demonstrates how to act, plan and carry out all tasks of risk management. The aim of the framework's risk management drawing up is to administer the probability of negative events (See appendix five).
- **Roles and responsibility:** This part assigns the duty of the project team members of their obligation for each of the risk management activities in the risk management plan. (See appendix five).

- **Budgeting:** This segment depicts how to assign resources and quantify the cost needed for the management of risk by the project risk management team for the life cycle of the project (see appendix five).
- **Schedule of project RM meetings:** elaborates when and how often the risk management process is to be performed for the project at every stage.
- **Risk reporting:** Entails how the outcomes of the risk management processes will be recorded, computed, and conveyed to the project stakeholders. It is suggested that a duplicate of the risk register Performa should be affixed to the risk management plan.
- **Tracking Progress:** States the procedure to be followed to chased named risks and distinguish the occurrence of novel risks that are potential to influence the project delivery ratio. It also records how threat activities will be documented for the gain of the project, which is underway as well as for future practice and lessons learned.

Appendix five can be seen, for an example of a risk management plan template.

A risk register should be generated collaboratively by the project executive, project funder, risk executive, decision-maker and team members that will allow them to identify, analyze, and develop a response to monitoring and inspect the project risks. **Appendix 5** can be reviewed for a prototype of risk register. The risk management planning is the first thing which should be finished during the planning phase of an endeavour, and this has significant value if the productivity of the further steps has to be achieved.

6.4.2 Identification of Project Risks for SME's in the UK Construction Industry

The aim of the risk identification stage of the framework is to record the crucial risks that could affect negatively to the scope of the project. It generates the results or output called the project risk register Qualitative risk analysis and a proper response strategy will improve the over risk register, which will be critiqued and modify the complete project lifecycle. The risk register is an instrument (an excel based sheet) that can be utilized by the project team report and update the register of project risks in project lifecycle (Patterson, R. and Neailey, Z. 2002, PMI, 2008, Caltrans, T. 2012). This tool has significant importance to convey project risks and aid the team members to embrace the useful adverse events planning from start to the end of the project.

Successful project completion can be enhanced by managing and updating a risk register throughout the project cycle. The risk register makes sure that project risks, analysis and responses are conveyed through the project stages so that threats are highlighted, realized, and efficiently treated.

A risk management squad in an SME comprises of project executive, the project manager, or mostly there is just a single representative who is dealing complete project. The project conveyance team (e.g., contractors, client, consultant) will apply any blend of historical data, brainstorming, consulting experts, interviewing to distinguish possible negative events that can hinder the scope of the project at any phase of the project lifecycle. Whilst, identification of risk is a combined effort of the team, this the responsibility of the project executive, project risk manager and project team to assist each other with the agreement of project funder. Results of the potential risks highlighted should be assorted and sorted, which is available in questionnaire 1. Risk register data should be updated accordingly. The risk management team should identify a risk responsible for every threat and mention that in the risk register and reviewed in the project lifecycle.

To identify construction risks, there are numerous tools and techniques which are widely accessible and mentioned in chapter 2. Established on the research findings (questionnaires and interviews) and literature critique, the following methods are advocated in the framework.

6.4.2.1 Checklist

Previous similar projects information and historical data benchmark the risk identification checklists, another source of information can also be considered, which included any information available in company records. Occasionally, the checklist is determined by experienced risk managers and representatives in small groups from all departments and stakeholders part of the project. The checklist can also have the risk category description, which can be found in the appendix, which should be continuously reviewed or on a daily basis to update and review it as per the needs of the project. Most of the times every project is unique, so they have their risk items, which are not on the checklist, it's the project executive and project team obligation to identify any threats or measures which are not available of the current checklist. This is considered as the most convenient and easy to adopt the technique at the root level.

6.4.2.2 Brainstorming

Sharing ideas and discussing all issues in the project team minds generate a brainstorming session, which is useful of originating a complete list of threats which have the potential to impact the project scope. The industry practitioners widely adopt this technique as it requires the least knowledge and expertise; this is the reason this is practised comprehensively. It is an extensive team drill, which generates different ideas regarding the potential risks and threats to the project by the project team. The project manager acts as the facilitator in brainstorming sessions and asks the input of all stakeholders of the project, including project team, clients, contractors and project funder. Appendix demonstrates the categorized and identified risks.

6.4.2.3 Consulting Expert

The term consulting expert is the definition in its name; it refers to talking or taking advice from someone in the industry who has appropriate knowledge and experience in managing and identifying the possible and potential risks. The project executive or manager should look for relevant people with above qualifications and pursue them to get comprehensive advice on the potential risk in the current project as per their experience. This will not be the most cost-effective way for an SME to hire a professional within the limited budget, resources and profit margin on a single project.

6.4.3 Analysis of Risk for SME's in the UK Construction Industry

Risk analysis is the second step where the identified possible threats are analysed on the basis of their potential and impact on the construction project. Risk analysis correspond to the risk register outcomes, which are planned initially.

Risk analysis is performed by two means of qualitative and quantitative techniques which are used as per the situation. There are the number of methods which ranges from a naïve to the expert level analysis of the risk identified in the project lifecycle to mitigate them eventually. Risk register has the all required information and the details of analyzing technique for the risk to be adopted. Qualitative analysis has been found suitable for this research as per the conclusions of interviews, questionnaire survey and literature review

Quantitative analysis (Montecarlo simulation, sensitivity analysis) requires expert-level understanding and knowledge to perform the analysis; they are sophisticated and require numeric calculations which are expensive and requires resources. Small enterprises are still

not fully aware of risk management is a formal procedure for analysing threats to the project. Medium size organizations still have some knowledge and idea about the process, and they still implement in most of the situation, but as it requires resources for SME's to hire personnel who can handle sophisticated software and techniques which consume time and cost. Therefore, it is the last resort they are willing to explore.

However it the project manager or project executive who is responsible of analysis risk or threats through qualitative or quantitative analysis which are detailed in the subsiding headings.

6.4.3.1 Risk possibility and Consequence Analysis

The risk rating is assigned on the scale of 1-5 (= very low, 2 = low, 3 =medium, 4 = high & 5 = very high). This is based on Liket's scale described in chapter 3. These ratings are easy to understand for the lowest level of organization (e.g. labour on-site) to identify a threat and rate them as per their description, which can later be calculated as they are the reliable frame of reference throughout the project lifecycle.

Moreover, it also analyses the nature of risk, i.e. controllable or uncontrollable. Furthermore, a risk representative is obliged in this process who analyse and then further propose a risk response strategy a risk management to comply with the next step of the risk management framework.

6.4.3.2 Risk Possibility and Consequences Matrix

Risks which are identified and are mapped on the matrix of probability and impact (appendix) considering a particular situation in the project lifecycle. The project risks are quantified and ranked (as per questionnaire one and top critical risk factors in chapter 6) based on project success factors i.e. cost, time and performance. The matrix places each risk in the graph where they depict their high or low severity with high or low impact. The high prioritizing risks are identified and treated on urgent basis whereas less severe risks are kept under a tab which is observed over time (See appendix D-5).

Each risk is assessed on the stated Likert's scale and mapped according to the matrix, and this is the basic principle of this technique to identify the risk rank as per probability and impact.

The risk matrix in an appendix should be used as a sample; if there is any modification in scale, it can be redeveloped as per the need.

To analyse a particular adverse event, the probability and impact of the threat generate a risk rank on an aggregate score, which is then placed and identified by yellow, green or red colour which are low, medium and high risks respectively. The colour depicts the severity of the risk and its priority on the analysis or mitigation list. For example, if a risk has medium probability and a high impact, it is denoted in the red zone. The sample is explained in the appendix with the help of the matrix.

6.4.3.3 Expert Judgement

It has frequently noted that an experienced executive can judge the situation or a threat efficiently, rather than someone new in a particular situation. The expert judgement has its significance on scoring a risk in the matrix. The expert panel can be a combination of all stakeholders or project team, for example, contractor, project manager etc. or can be a one-person show as per his previous experience.

6.4.4 Risk Response for SME's in the UK Construction Industry

Developing a strategy to deal with the identified and quantified risks and proposing an appropriate methodology to reduce the impact of a possible threat in a project represents a risk response strategy. It is similar to developing a vaccine to encounter the COVID-19 threat in 2020. The project risk response is the planning which involves the project management, project executive, risk owner, project delivering teams and the project funder particularly. The responsible for project completion, which is a project manager is held liable to delegate each risk owner to implement the response strategy, in conjunction with the team on site.

The desirable, tangible and sensible strategy is developed in this response planning phase, which is realistic and appropriate to adopted by the project manager whose duty is to perform the check mentioned for each strategy and makes sure that the planned actions. The outcomes from the risk response strategy are updated in the risk register and further in the risk management plan of the project (Caltrans, 2012). Sometimes these outcomes can influence the contingency (which is usually kept 5% of the project price) to deviate from its planned amount.

6.4.4.1 Risk Response Strategies for SME's in the UK Construction Industry

The widely practised strategies on a small or a large scale project for risk response are to avoid risk, transfer the risk, mitigate the risk or if none of the above, then accept the risk. To avoid the risk, it is essential to eradicate the risk, which can be either safeguarding your project from its impact or eliminate it. Risk transfer is about transferring the liability to other stakeholder or a third party who can deal with the risk with a better strategy or if that is their responsibility as per the scope of the project. Most of the time insurance, performance bonds, guarantees, warranties are taken to avoid the risk; for example, a contract takes non-negligence insurance to avoid any mishap during the construction period to next-door property.

The other items in the list are accepting or retaining the risk. It happens when the situation does not assure the complete eradication of risk or the cost to deal with the risk is undervalued. Sometimes the probability of the risk event is so low, and its impact is not high, which can affect the project, in that scenario, the risk is accepted and retained as well.

Risk mitigation occurs and implemented when the risk is accepted, or it occurs without any previous identification, then the only way to deal with it is to reduce its impact to a permissible degree on the projects lifecycle. If we plan to reduce the impact, it will have a low impact on cost and time, which will not affect much on the contingency funds available.

The suggested framework for the SME's in the UK construction industry is formulated with mitigation techniques to exercise and test risks around them. An expert judgement can be of significant importance in developing risk response strategies and planned actions. The mitigation strategy for the top 10 identified and ranked critical risk factors(Appendix D-6) for the SME's in the UK construction industry is suggested in the risk management framework henceforth the risk register for the respective project is updated, and the manager moves on to the next step of the framework. Extensive literary critique in chapter 2, and questionnaire survey and interviews analysis in chapter 5 helped extract these mitigations measures. The RMF provides risk reduction techniques for the identified top risk factors.

6.4.5 Monitoring and Reviewing

In the final phase of RMF, it involves overseeing the risks identified, adding new uncertainties, allowing complete implementation of the agreed responses and reviewing their effectiveness, the effectiveness of the agreed response to the identified risks, identifying new risks, ensuring appropriate implementation is the part of the final phase of the newly developed RMF, the amendments are also monitored during the construction process of the risk management process. The project manager deals with project risk monitoring and risk owner, other team members and the risk manager to support the central staff. The risk register is then developed and updated as a result of these objectives. The results also play a vital role in adopting appropriate measures to relevant risks involved in future projects(Caltrans, 2012). Risk review workshops should frequently help the project manager get the best result (appendix), which also involves the other team members and helps update the risk register for the relevant identified risks and their mitigations.

Risk rankings and their severity to deal with, does change during time to time in a project. To deal with these ever evolving risks, it is mandatory for the responsible people to develop monitoring and controlling strategies in advance. During the project life cycle, most of the times, risk ratings and rankings tends to change. Planned response strategies changes when there is an unexpected risk event take place with an unpredictable impact.

6.4.5.1 Risk reassessment

New risks are usually identified when monitoring and reviewing processes are done correctly. During this process, reassessment of current risks and the resolved risks is also chosen. Risk review should be done as per the project demand, if the project is simple, it can be done monthly, but if the project is involved, then risk review should be done regularly as per the project managers suggestions.

6.4.5.2 Review meetings

The main agenda of any project risk management framework should be reviewing the existing project risks in scheduled meetings. Priority and the significance of risks set the rate of risk review meetings. Most of the risks are identified when the risk and threats are discussed frequently in the project team's project lifecycle.

Risk identification is the process which goes on throughout the project life cycle; it can also be seen in figure 6.1. The emergence of new risks and the review of existing risk are the main constituents of the proposed risk management framework. Mitigation strategies make sure that all the concurrent risks are identified promptly, and the impact of the existing risk is reduced, this systematic and continuous process improves the overall risk mitigation process.

6.5 Summary

The research findings from the critique of literature review in chapter 2, survey and interview findings in chapter 5, and correct implementation of the proposed framework make the risk management easy for the SME's in the UK construction industry to implement and practice. It consists of five phases which are: Project Risk Management Planning for SME's in the UK Construction Industry, Identification of Project Risks for SME's in the UK Construction Industry, Analysis of Risk for SME's in the UK Construction Industry, Risk Response for SME's in the UK Construction Industry, Monitoring and Reviewing.

CHAPTER 7

EVALUATION OF RISK MANAGEMENT FRAMEWORK

7.1 Introduction

This chapter discuss the testifying of the newly developed RMF for the SME's in the UK construction industry (see appendix D-7). This chapter is to ensure that the newly developed risk management framework fills the gap of risk management practices for the SMEs in the UK construction industry.

7.2 Evaluation of the Framework

In construction sector research, RMF practical application is necessary to make sure that it fulfils the baseline targets of the risk management, and it also satisfies its proposed objectives (Lucko, Rojas, 2009). It is termed to be most essential part of research to validate the proposed risk management framework for SME's in the UK Construction Industry. A framework justifies the evaluation if it is going to be an integral part of any process Mahmoud (2009). Researcher should involve the industry professionals and practitioners to validate the established framework. Internal and external validities are the two broad areas which has been highlighted while the literature was investigated (Lucko, Rojas, 2009; Saunders, 2015). Face validation, criterion validation, content validation and construct validation are few other type of commonly used validation processes.

7.2.1 Comparison of Developed Framework with ISO 31000:2018 ERM Framework

The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) 31000:2018 ERM framework is a cyclical risk management process that incorporates integrating, designing, implementing, evaluating, and improving the ERM process, whereas the risk management framework developed in this research has the similar basis and concept, but an additional option of providing risk mitigation strategies to the identified risks and genuinely customised for the SMEs of the UK construction industries.

7.3 Evaluation Findings

Figure 6.1 presents the newly developed risk management framework which is to be evaluated by expert opinions of professionals involved in mega projects ongoing in the construction industry. Semi-structured interviews were performed with three mega

infrastructure industry practitioners extracted out of three projects in the construction phase or completed infrastructure construction project where SME's were involved in a large scale infrastructure projects. Every survey was done out on a face to face criteria, on pre set questions. The questions are distributed into two segments: segment 1 gathers the basic rational details and segment 2 accumulates framework testifying questions. It was made sure that the participants have dense experience in built environment construction projects where SME's plays a vital role in accomplishing the objectives, and they have been involved in many projects where numerous SME's are involved. They had managerial designations for managing risks in the mega projects in construction sector and were approved by specific professional bodies and are aware about the issue of SME's and their struggle managing risks. They were the best people to validate the framework as they are know the best practice.

Other section of the evaluation gathers perceptions and recommendations on the proposed framework as a basis for amendment and improvement. This section made the grounds for the unbiased testification of the framework with respect to the criteria of clarity, comprehensiveness, practical relevance and suitability of the framework. These ideas were extracted from the pas published RMF in the construction industry (Holsapple, Joshi, 2000; Mahmoud, 2009; Dey, 2012).

Evaluators were also inquired about their perceptions on the following details: specific guidelines/instructions for implementation of all the segments of the framework individually; viability or importance of the newly added risk book for countering risks for SME's in the UK building industry; listed reduction techniques for the top ten most severe risks identified by the data analysis for SME's in the UK construction endeavours; restrictions or shortcomings of the framework; further improvement sections of the framework and basic overview and recommendations (if any) for the betterment of the framework

7.3.1 Clarity and Richness of the Overall Framework

Participants were asked to remark on the vision and comprehensiveness of the RMF. So that the researcher has a good idea about the viability of its adaptability and implementation. Difference in opinios was recorded between participants that the framework is 'technically complete'. According to X2, the framework is straightforward and complete, particularly how *the processes were outlined*'. Moreover, interviewee X3(Project Risk Manager) highlighted the segment that provided more comprehensive details makes it relevantly eye catching and user friendly. Participant X1, other professional, *'the framework is loud and complete as it*

entails the conceptual segmental process of RM in built industry'. Participants X1 and X2 added that *'The framework evenly distributed in segments and consists of the key RMP with loud and complete details*'. Participants X2 and X3 added that the framework has no ambiguity, and it consists of essential details required. Interviewees X1, X2 & X3 clarified that the proposed RMF and its risk monitoring sections are easy to understand, easy to implement and self-explanatory. Concluding the recommendations of the UK built industry professional on provided judgement, the mathematical understanding and completeness of the proposed SME's RMF in the UK construction industry can be judged.

7.3.2 Practical Relevance and Suitability of the Framework

Interviewees were asked to comment on the practical useability and adaptability of the framework to the SME's construction project risk management. In response to this question, all the interviewees assured that the practical relevance and suitability of the framework for the SME's in the UK construction industry. X2, stated that *'the SME's in the UK construction process does not adapt rigorous risk assessment, management and mitigation as expected. This framework, if fully fitted and implemented, will improve the risk management*'. This details that risk management is currently on an 'ad hoc' basis. From the perspective of X3 & X1: *'the framework is very constructive and adaptive; best practice and best-fit approach for the SME's in the construction industry*'. According to X1, *'the framework is relevant for SME's in construction industries. Considering the limited resources of SME's and unavailability of resources, this framework is cost-effective and, with training for the project teams, suitable to implement on all scales of projects and low to medium size construction projects*'. It will undoubtedly be a part of a well-organised project management team to implement any risk management framework, no matter how good the comprehensiveness and clarity of the framework. Participants comment sums that, the proposed risk management framework is practically relevant and considered suitable for the SME's in the UK construction industry.

7.3.3 Specific guidelines/instructions for the application of each of the phases of the framework

Interviewees were requested to express their views on each of the specific guidelines/instructions for the application of each of the phases of the framework. The findings of the interviews revealed that specific guidelines/instructions for the application of

each of the phases of the framework are: quite comprehensive, self-explanatory, concise and adequate for realistic risk management processes. Other useful information was contributed by X3, *'Like I have stated earlier at the commencement of my review, every guide line listed are just in time. SME's is long overdue for the implementation of a global standard framework. From the view point of X2 the guidelines were: 'Quite logical in nature and represent an all-purpose mechanism for managing project risks in construction industry'. X1 added that, 'They are very good and useful especially the logical sequence of the guidelines'. X2 and X3 also recommended that 'there should be practicable enforcement rules to support the guidelines; otherwise there will be evasion of instructions'. This recommendation is outside the control of the researcher. If the framework has satisfied the entire fundamental requirement it is up the responsible SME to adopt a system to implement it. In view of the interviewees' comments, it can be said that overall there are valuable, clear and detailed guidelines/instruction for the application of each of the phases of the framework.*

7.3.4 Usefulness or relevance of the proposed risk registers

Interviewees were asked further to evaluate the other aspects of the framework, relevance and usefulness was the next part brought under analysis. In response to this question, the interviewees described the proposed risk register as very comprehensive and extremely relevant. X1 described that *'the framework is wholesome and ready to be used'*. X2 narrated that, *'it's an essential framework for the whole project'*. X3 said that, *'post mitigation analysis also benefits with this framework'*. X1 and X2 stated that *'the risk register Template gives the overall details of the risk at a glance, which includes the risk identification, risk analysis, risk response and post mitigation analysis. This makes it very useful and relevant register for managing risks for SME's in the UK construction projects'*. X3 also narrated : *'it has all clear and loud instructions. Risk management process for SMEs got a useful tool in form of this framework. It is comprehensive as it covers all the risk management stages even up to the extent of post mitigation strategies'*. The satisfaction level of interviewees, it was analysed that risk register is comprehensive and a useful element of the framework and adding an important value to the over risk management framework developed for the SME's in the UK construction industry.

7.3.5 The proposed mitigation measures for the top ten most critical risks

To evaluate the more aspects of framework, interviewees were asked, ‘the mitigations measures proposed (see Appendix D-6) for the top ten most critical risks for SMEs in the UK construction industry you think is/are not relevant that should be removed? Please comment.’ The interviewees are convinced that the proposed risk mitigation methods are most relevant and best suited for the risk factors, and improvement is not required.

7.3.6 Limitations and Weaknesses of the Framework

Limitations and weakness of this frameworks are the other aspects where analysed. Response of interviewees was highly satisfying and confident boosting for the framework evaluation. However, most of them believed that the success of its application depends on:

- A well-organized project team to drive this through, considering the under regulated projects mostly where SME are involved such as private projects of individual landlords, where the scope of works changes in no time.
- SME’s situations, where there is more emphasis of saving cost, rather than investing in resources.
- The willingness of the SME’s and industry practitioners to integrate the risk management framework into the system.
- The lack of resources and education in this subject.

The overall response of the framework evaluation from the interviewees proved that to get the full benefits of this framework, it is mandatory that the rules and support guidelines should be adopted fully, otherwise there will be less benefits. Referring to the overall risk management framework presented in Figure 6.1, one of the interviewees suggested that the orange arrow should feedback into the risk management plan to make it cyclical.

7.3.7 Potential Areas of Usage of Risk Management Framework

To assess the risk management framework and its extensive areas of application, the interviewees were requested to identify other potential areas where they thought the framework could be used. The interview findings reveals that they believed the framework has a comprehensive coverage and as such could be used on all residential, commercial and

infrastructure projects across the UK construction industry. According to X3, *'the framework has a comprehensive coverage and could be used on all projects by SMEs, namely buildings, residential, commercial and infrastructure etc., in the UK. In the same domain it can also be used in other developing countries that shared some similarities with the UK'*. According to X1: *'I think all aspect of the economy should see this as veritable tool. I.e. all aspect Constructions, be it, Building, Civil and other engineering works'*. X2 stated that the framework is suitable for private projects and even for government projects.

7.3.8 General overview and suggestions (if any) for improvement of the framework

Overall compatibility and suitability of the framework for the SMEs in the UK construction industry were asked. The interview findings of their general overview of the framework are that it is a comprehensive, sufficient, well-researched and well-versed framework that is compatible with the UK construction industry. X1 narrated that, *'complete'*! X3 asserted, *'It covers all the process involved in the risk management framework from planning to closeout'*. According to X2, *'Construction projects can utilise this framework and adopt as a complete package. All elements are covered and provide complete guidelines for the adoption. This framework has my approval to be adopted'*. X1 said, *'this is a thorough work. Risk management requires the involvement of professionals who are responsible for dealing with risks directly'*. X2 further added that *'Risk management is required for the projects which are to be completed on time and within the budget,'* while X3 ended with a positive note: *'for the very first framework, it cannot be better.'*

X1 commented that *the framework is ambiguity free and accumulates all the requirements for comprehensive risk management and that the guidelines are complete as well but would like to recommend that other stakeholders, like the local community within the project corridor, must be involved from the onset and "through and through"*. According to X1: *'the framework is good, and the guiding notes have made it more convenient.'*

7.3.9 Any existing Risk Management Framework for SME's in the UK Construction Industry

At the end of the interview, In the last question, interviewees were asked: Are you aware of any existing risk management framework for the SMEs in the UK construction industry? If yes, please provide more details to include any difference between the existing risk management framework and the one I have developed. All the answers are below from the respondents: *We expect a formal risk management process from the SMEs, as mostly SMEs*

does not have their own. So we ask them to adopt ours, which is not convenient. (V1); Not to the best of my knowledge for the SMEs (V2); Not sure of any comprehensive risk management framework for addressing risks for SMEs in UK (V3).

.After the complete survey, it can be said that there is no existing risk management framework for the SMEs in the UK construction industry. Judging from the interviewees' comments on all the components of the developed framework, it can be said that the proposed framework is a valuable approach for managing risks associated with the SMEs in the UK construction industry that could potentially improve the performance of the projects.

7.10 Summary

Semi-structured interviews were conducted with industry professionals to validate the newly developed risk management framework with the help of risk management professionals across the industry in the UK.

Early adoption in the project lifecycle is mandatory for the complete results from the framework. More importantly, for the effective implementation of this framework, the contractors and consultants need to be educated about the potential time and cost savings that will be gained through implementing the framework.

It is considered that this chapter has filled the knowledge gap area for the SMEs in the UK construction industry regarding the lack of a comprehensive risk management framework for improving the management of risks. It has established that the proposed mitigation measures for the key risks are suitable to guide the SMEs in managing risk associated with their projects.

RESEARCH FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, RECOMMENDATIONS AND SUMMARY

8.1 Introduction

The management of key risks for the SME's in the UK construction industry by the proposed risk management framework is the aim of this research. The objectives mentioned in chapter one are fulfilled, and the research outcomes summary is presented in this chapter. Recommendations for the researchers of the future, limitations of the study, the implementation of the risk management framework, and conclusions are drawn in this chapter.

8.2 Research findings and fulfilment of research objectives

The ambiguity of implementing the risk management framework has been identified in the survey and literature results, which requires rigorous improvement and implementation to attain better results for the project and client. Risk management has to be adopted by the SME's through the formal process from the start to the construction project's finish. This research presents an easy to adopt and understand risk management frameworks for the professionals, particularly SME's.

Conclusions from the study as per the set objectives are in proceedings headings.

8.2.1 To identify the current scenario of key risk management process and practices in the UK construction industry

SME's are the main constituents of the large and infrastructure projects, and risks associated with them, efficient management of critical risks, are vital irrespective of the project's size, i.e. small house of large infrastructure. Major infrastructure projects are only completed on time and within cost only if their risks are managed comprehensively (Wang, 2016). If concerned risks are identified at the right time in the project, they can finish within planned time, cost and required quality.

Risk is imminent and are present in a construction project from the planning to the handover, and they have a straight effect on project planned timeline, total cost and the quality of finish product. The results from interviews and questionnaire survey have depicted a big gap of knowledge and implanting knowledge of risk management process, which are not up to the demands for SME's (Choudhary, Iqbal, 2013). The ever-growing sector of construction in the

UK has a significant proportion of SME's, which demands an appropriate risk management framework. Lack of knowledge and proper adoption of risk management procedure is the crucial argument of miserable performance in a large SME project (Choudhry, Iqbal, 2012; El-Sayegh, Mansour, 2015; Reza, 2016).

Further conclusions have determined the succeeding gaps:

- There have been developments and proper research evidence for a large organization and their formal risk management implementations. However, for SME's in the UK construction industry, there is no data found on a dedicated risk management framework for SME's in the UK construction industry, proving improvements in managing risks in the sector.
- Data on SME's risk management practices and understanding is limited.
- Evidence found on identifying risks in SME's, but there is no or minimal grounds implementation of the risk management framework for the SME's in the UK construction industry.
- Henceforth, risk management in SME's of the UK construction industry requires an easy to understand and a practical risk management framework to advance the process's implementation.

It is substantial to acquire all the relevant knowledge of risk management framework, to develop a pragmatic framework, determinations are below:

- To deal with the adverse events (risks), the risk management process adopts the step by step procedure of identifying risks, analysing their impact (if they happen), developing a strategy to mitigate the risks and reviewing and monitoring them time to time to achieve the desired results.
- SME's has no dedicated risk management framework, and they do not have resources and knowledge to manage risks in the project lifecycle.
- Another gap in the research is that all stakeholders (funder, consultant, owner etc) participation is missing, if they collectively give their input in identifying, analysing

and mitigating risks associated with SME's in the construction industry to rank the risks accordingly, can improve the risk management framework.

- The study has only involved the risk identification, their mitigation, ranking and a dedicated risk management framework for SME's. It is missing an important part of risk management process which is risk analysis, this is also a gap, which require knowledge, resources and skills.
- There is no evidence in past research that has explored the risk management process, or their utilized frameworks being adopted by SME's in the UK Construction Industry with evaluation of their effectiveness.

Ali Rostami (2015) published few research papers about the risk management of SME's in the UK construction industry. His findings were also significant about the knowledge, expertise and resources which are missing in the SME's of the UK construction industry. Since then there has been no substantial work done in this sector of the driving industry of the UK economy.

Considering all these consequences, it is evident that there is a requirement to overcome the gap in their area of risk management for the SME's of the UK construction industry and the framework adopted. The gaps highlighted in the literature study has made the basis for the proposed objectives to fulfil the gap in their area of research.

8.2.2 To evaluate the impact of risk management process on the overall performance of SMEs in the Construction industry.

Various tiers of construction industry are directly proportional to the risk management of each of the organizations involved. Mostly, the funder/client is the one who has the most adverse effects of risk management failure, as it's all his time and money which is ruined. New projects for SME's always depend on previous successful project completions and adequate earnings. It is very hard for them to survive in the industry without any formal risk management, as their profit margin is low and time estimation is inadequate. They have to adopt risk management as an item on a project, and have to calculate their exposure on every step in a project lifecycle. And this usually happens when they get an opportunity to be a part of mega project, and when their inappropriate risk management fails, they are kicked out of the market because for their scarce resources and severe losses.

8.2.2.1 Organisation Culture and Maturity towards Risk Management Process

Change is always not acceptable to everyone in the organizations, that's why to achieve the best results, it is recommended to bring it slowly considering the most difficult and opposing constraints in the organization. So that everyone is on one page of understanding the benefits of the change. Risk management should be in conjunction with the organization culture so that it has no ambiguity at any level of the organizations to achieve the desired results. Feedback and opinions of the team members is considerable in adopting and improving the best methods, as per their experience to make a successful change. Continuous improvement is a key of any successful process implementation, for example KAIZEN, which is adopted by Ford to continuously improve their performance and quality keeping their time, cost and resources within the limit, which is similar to risk in every project that drives a project from success to failure.

Each of the stakeholders and team members of the organizations have similar information of the risk management process, they should be aware about all the improvements and changes being made with time for the effective implementation, and that the risk managers or responsible persons duty to keep everyone updated. This can be done via regular meetings or brainstorming sessions to consider their level of acceptability or their concerns about the changes being implemented, as it's an extra effort for them to adopt a change and improve their maturity towards the successful further of an organization.

SME's are less in resources and knowledge, their teams and tiers in organizations are also limited to realize the culture and maturity towards risk management, they should develop their own easy to adapt and easy to understand risk management framework with a reference framework to achieve the best results.

8.2.2.2 To identify the critical risk factors with indicators of cost, performance and time.

Twenty Eight critical risk factors are identified from literature and further research. These risk are further distributed in five categories to sort them and made a part of research questionnaire to be distributed in the UK construction industry. Each of the risk factor/event is then further analysed as per their cost, time and performance individually and commutatively as well to draw a concrete result for the SME's in the UK construction industry.

Top 10 most critical risk factors or events are given in Table, which can be treated as per their priorities in a construction project where SME;s are involved.

8.2.3 To recommend a Risk Management Framework to mitigate the impact of risk in SME's.

Considering the limited resources, no expertise and less knowledge, SME's should be provided with an easy to understand, plain and an effective risk management framework which should require no extra resource to implement and practice. It should have baseline set for the whole process which should be easy to understand with the performance indicators.

Projects should be less prone to risks, there should be a control method to minimize the adverse effects from unwanted and unplanned risks, which could overrun the cost and time and at the end effect the whole project and the funder particularly, without any significant increase in cost. Clients prefer partnering with SME's to reduce their costs and control their timeline for the project. On the other hand, they also cannot risk the project completion or any unwanted mishap or delay due to less experience of the SME, or their lack of resources to handle involvement in a large project. That is the reason to adopt a risk management framework to satisfy the clients expectations and fasten their position to work on a high profile project in a controlled environment. They have choice now to spend extra cost and hire professionals or a third party who can quantify their risks or adopt an risk management framework which allows them to perform and quantify their risks in their limited resources.

A new risk management framework is proposed for the SME's in the UK construction industry (Figure 6.1) to manage and mitigate the top 10 critical risk factors generated through the research process which effect the performance of an SME. Rational set up section 6.2 (following existing frameworks, considering frameworks from developed countries and their risk management etc) was considered to propose a new risk management framework. It has five detailed steps and workability of each step through the step-by-step procedure for each phase of the risk management framework (Appendix).

8.2.3.1 To evaluate the proposed risk management framework

To evaluate the risk management framework, professionals working on large infrastructure projects were targeted and semi structured interview was conducted on a Zoom session was conducted. Furthermore, the proposed mitigation strategy for the identified top 10 critical risk

factors were also presented to the industry professionals to share their views about the presented strategy. Previous chapter details the complete evaluation of the proposed risk management framework for the SME's in the UK construction industry. Framework was found to be appropriate, comprehensive, relevant, and fit for purpose by the evaluating professionals in their given feedback. They found the framework to be practical and should be adopted by the SME's in the industry. Its application does not seem to have any ambiguity, so it's a worth full framework, with its adoption including the risk register segment, which is useful in updating each of the top 10 critical risk project threats/risks with their corresponding risk mitigation methods for the SME's in the UK construction industry. Hence, adoption of this risk management framework will surely provide support to the SME's in the UK construction industry to manage and mitigate their critical risks more effectively and efficiently.

However, the interviewees highlighted few of the elementary prerequisites required for its effective implementation:

- All the stakeholders should be involved particularly clients, and they all should have clear knowledge of the adopted framework and its workability (risk register etc), so that its effective implementation is possible.
- Organization adopting this framework (an SME) needs to make sure that risk management is made an integral part of the project lifecycle and it has to be considered as a formal procedure.
- Organization culture should adopt the risk management framework and any resistance should have been dealt in the beginning, so that every working brain is mature enough.

8.3 Contribution Towards the Body of Knowledge

Risk management is relatively untouched where it is about implementation and analysing the risks formally with appropriate methods in SME's of the UK construction industry. The body of knowledge has a clear gap on this topic having less literature and content locally and internationally for the SME's in the UK construction industry. The study aims to bridge the gaps, add valuable literature and real life practical implementation of the risk management framework for the relevant industry with the proceedings results:

- The major contribution of the framework is in providing guidelines for the experts as explained in section 6.5. Easy to understand principles, to implement risk management framework with less or no expert knowledge in the area demonstrated in sections of chapter 6.
- Risk management framework is developed for SME's in the UK construction industry.
- Top 10 critical risk factors are provided with their mitigation methods.
- Risk factors are identified, ranked and sub divided in categories which affect the performance of SME's in the UK construction industry.
- Risk register Performa is produced to manage all the risk involved.
- Planning of qualitative and quantitative risk analysis tools and techniques, with the preparation of identifying and managing project risks in advance is provided.

Following results are gathers on the development of risk management framework:

Appropriate risk management strategies for the identified risks are drawn from the research, which will overall improve the performance of SME's in the UK construction industry.

- Risk management tasks are supplied authentic propositions. Comprehensive measures are given to adopt risk quantification and risk response strategy.
- The risk management framework for SME's will contribute to improve the overall performance of SME's in large projects.
- Framework is providing the comprehensive risk management process with steps to follow i.e. planning, analysing, monitoring and then review the risk process, which is sufficient as per the evaluators. The framework also benefits the user with identification and prioritising the severe risks involved in the project lifecycle which are unique in their own way and sometimes diverse in cultural, environment, religious and variables.
- Moreover, the framework also welfares the organization categorization of risks in different categories, analysing and monitoring of the identified risks, and reviewing the effects of these risks on the project performance factors.
- There is extra information which is about the nature of risk, allocation of risk and risk response strategy. These information sets can be utilized in developing a risk

assessment tool for the SME's in the UK construction industry, which will be first of its type in the local industry that can be as simple as excel based on macros.

- The overall research will benefit both the local and foreign companies that wish to construction projects in the UK, and help them to be extremely careful about the design risks, construction risks, financial and economic risks and legal, and regulatory risks.

These above points are validating that this research made a valuable contribution to the body of knowledge. The risk management process for SME's in construction industry will benefit with the proposed framework and particular care will be given to risk planning, identification, analysis, mitigation and risk review. Evaluations was conducted by a survey to reconfirm the authentication of the framework and mitigation methods for the identified top 10 critical risk factors which are prioritized as per their risk score.

The given list of critical risk factors can be used as a reference for the SME's in the UK construction industry in projects, but if they are involved in large infrastructure project, they should consider reanalysing the risks considering few more new risks involved in the projects.

Risk register will allow the risk managers to store the data regularly, it will in turn provide more solid risk management practice for the SME to finish the project within budget and provided time. It always assist the responsible person to easily pass on the relevant information of critical risks to the project team and the stakeholders. Risk register template is provided in appendix D-2 which is suggested to be used as the part of proposed framework, otherwise any modified version can also be used as its easy to understand and cost efficient.

8.4 Limitation of the research

Besides all the results and conclusion, the research was still limited due to time, resource and COVID-19 constrains. Few of the limitations are discussed below:

- The scope of this research is limited to investigating SME's in the UK construction industry only. Whilst, the research has been made in such a manner that it can be implemented or exercised in different countries, considering variables and risk factors

of a respective organization or a country. Risk is everywhere, and they are similar in their management i.e. risk management process, so as the phases of the project, so risk management and its framework is uniform around the world.

- .When there is less knowledge on the topic in the industry, it is hard to collect the data as people are either unaware or have less knowledge. In our case, as we have targeted SME's, we have encountered number of organizations where there is no job role of person managing risk, either it's the project manager or the director himself talking all decisions. Few of the medium size organizations had proper risk professional inhouse or they have outsourced it. Overall this situation has hinder the data collection process and COVID-19 (as the virus threat was high and university advised against travelling around the UK played its part where we could not go to the respondents to interview during the framework evaluation phase. Some of the respondents turned down to participate in the survey as they were working on some ongoing projects and that was against their company policy to give any information, this scenario troubled most in the framework evaluation where we approach some professionals working on large ongoing infrastructure projects and we could only get three respondents to reply.
- This research has focused to develop a framework for risk management which has more practical implementation rather than just another theoretical framework which becomes a part of books. It is precisely developed to support SME's in the UK construction industry to implement and gain benefit.
- The researcher initially planned to implement the proposed risk management framework on real life projects, to quantify its suitability and improve the experience of the user. But at the end, the evaluation was only conducted via expert opinions.
- Developing or tailoring a framework does not guarantee a job done for risk management, but it requires to be tested on real time information from an ongoing project. The evaluators motioned that there are many driving factors in a project which are requires being associated the risk management framework (for example: experience of the project team, scope of clients, pitch in of involved stakeholders, and more). To cover all these gaps/limitations could be part of a future research, but it is not in the scope of this research.

8.5 Recommendation for Future Research Possibilities

There is always a chance of improvement and adding more to the body of knowledge, following are the future research recommendations:

- The SME's are the part of the construction industry, and more often they work on large projects by some means, it will be fruitful if there is a research carried on large infrastructure projects which highlights the success factors and risk management policies on large projects by clients and SME's themselves. In this way there will be improvements made to the proposed risk management framework for SME's in this research with reference to best practice in the industry. At the moment the framework is solely developed for the SME's in the UK construction industry.
- Cross country comparison is done in literature review, which does elaborates the risk management practices by developed and developing countries. It will be a valuable research if SME's of developed countries are examined of their risk management techniques and frameworks and a comparison is done with the SME's in the UK construction industry.
- Mixed methods research was choose in this research, in which quantitative and qualitative methods were applied. There has been a lot of data which is left used from the questionnaire survey, which can be utilised in developing a risk analysis tool for the SME's in the UK construction industry.

8.6 Summary

This study contributed in discovering and betterment in the extensive area of Risk Management for SME's in the UK construction industry to the researcher with the broader view. This study has contributed the local construction industry and the maturing risk management industry for every stakeholder of the contraction industry at the lowest level, they will get to know how easy is to adopt risk management framework and its process in a real life projects.

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APPENDIX A-1

SOURCE OF LITERATURE

Source of Papers

The papers were collected from the following journals and conference proceedings

- Automation in construction.
- Association for the advancement of cost engineering international (AACE)
- Building and environment
- Construction management and economics
- Draft report Florida international university
- International Conference on Construction.
- International Research Journal of Finance and Economics
- International journal of project management
- International Conference on Construction in Developing Countries
- International software engineering research network
- Journal of construction engineering and management
- Journal of project management.
- Journal of management in engineering

Source of Books

Books were adopted from following publishers.

- Project Management Institute
- McGraw Hill, London
- Blackwell Scientific publishers Ltd.
- E & FN SPON publishers.

Source of Thesis & Dissertation

Following universities research work were involved.

- University Of Technology, Malaysia. (MSc. Thesis)
- College of Engineering, Guindy Campus, Anna University Chennai, India (MSc. Thesis)
- King Fahad University of Petroleum and Mineral (MSc. Thesis)
- Center construction industry studies, University Of Texas, Austin. (Report)

List of Websites and Net Libraries

1. www.ascweb.org
2. www.accessengineeringlibrary.com
3. www.accessscience.com/
4. www.agc.org
5. www.ascelibrary.org
6. www.books-google.com
7. www.buildingteam.com
8. www.ce.cmu.edu
9. www.construction-institute.org
10. www.construction.st
11. www.c-risk.com
12. www.coso.org
13. www.conrisk.com
14. www.dfid.gov.uk
15. www.fiu.edu
16. www.fedpunseminars.com
17. www.holderconstruction.com
18. www.inderscience.com
19. www.insweb.com
20. www.proj-man.com
21. www.sitation.aip.org
22. <http://www.sciencemag.org>
23. www.sciencedirect.com
24. www.theirm.com
25. www.uflib.ufl.edu
26. www.ask.com

27. <http://chandoo.org/wp/2009/09/02/pareto-charts/>
28. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Analytic_hierarchy_process

**APPENDIX A-2
DATASHEET**

S. No.	Company	Trade	Contact Person	Position	Contact Email	C. No.
1	4 Housing Professional Services Ltd	Consultancy	Farooq Mohammed	Director	farooq@4housing.org	07
2	9 Yards Property Limited	Architects	Colin Logan	Director	design@9yards.co.uk	02
3	A&H Nicholson LTD	Contractors	A Nicholson	Director	info@ahnicholson.com	02
4	A D Bly Construction Ltd	Contractors	Sturat Hirst	Director	info@adbly.co.uk	01
5	ADS Building Services	Architects/Surveyors	A M Frame	Director	info@party-wall.co.uk	01
6	A K Design Partnership	Designers	M P Allen	Director	office@akdesign.co.uk	01
7	A Line Southern Limited	Contractors	R C Mcdowell	Director	info@a-linesouthern.co.uk	02
8	ABGM Contracts Limited	Construction Law	A P Beckett	Director	andy@abgm.co.uk	
9	Abbeymead Building Ltd	Contractors	R J Maccarthy	Director	enquiries@abbeymeadbuilding.co.uk	01
10	AC Mauger & Son Ltd	Contractors	J Kent	Director	enquiries@acmauger.com	01
11	Acivico Ltd	Consultancy	T B Haynes	Director	trevor.haynes@acivico.co.uk	01
12	Acoustic Associates Sussex Ltd	Acoustic Services	Peter Attwood	Director	peterattwood@aasussex.co.uk	01
13	Adkins Consultants Ltd	Consultancy	David King	Director	s.jenkins@adkinsconsultants.com	02
14	Advanced Safety Consultants Ltd	H&S Consultants	Roland Crane	Director	info@advanced-safety.co.uk	01
15	Aedis	Building Control	David Barley	Director	david.barley@aedis.com	01
16	Air 3 Limited	Contractors	Peter Morgan	Director	petermorgan@air3.build	01
17	Alan R Collinson	Contractors	A R Collinson	Director	alanrcollinson@hotmail.com	20
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22	AMMCASS Limited	Contractors	Adam Marley	Director	adam@ammcass.com	02
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26	Arthur Bryant Surveying Services Limited	Surveyors	John Kelly	Director	john.kelly@arthurbryantltd.co.uk	01
27	ASF Bespoke Developments Ltd	Contractors	Andy Fuller	Director	andy@asfbd.co.uk	01
28	Ash Design Services	Consultancy	Peter Bartley	Director	ashdesignservices@live.co.uk	01
29	Ashe Construction Limited	Contractors	M J Petts	Director	martinpetts@ashe-con.co.uk	01
30	Aspectum	Consultancy	Trevor Barfoot	Director	tjb@tjbarfoot.co.uk	01
31	Atlas Environments Ltd	Environmental	A G Muscovitch	Director	design@atlasenv.com	01
32	Axis Project Controls Limited	Consultancy	Niel Pickavance	Director	office@axisprojectcontrols.co.uk	01
33	B M H Contract Services Limited	Contractors	K F Bicknell Richard	Director	info@bmhcontract.co.uk	01
34	B38 Projects Ltd	Contractors	Sommerville	Director	vicki.sommerville@b38group.com	01
35	Baily Garner (Health & Safety) Limited	H&S Consultants	P N Lennon	Director	general@bailygarner.co.uk	02 :0 44
36	Bardsley Construction Limited	Contractors	Bardsley	Director	info@bardsleyconstruction.com	01
37	Barker Morris Ltd	Contractors	D Barker	Director	info@barkermorris.com	01
38	Barlow Project Solutions Ltd	Consultancy Consultancy/Surveyors	Nick Barlow	Director	nick@barlowprojectsolutions.co.uk	01
39	Batty France	Consultancy	C W France	Director	info@battyfrance.co.uk	01
40	Bayliss Building Consultancy Ltd	Consultancy	F Bayliss	Director	fb@baylisscbc.co.uk	01
41	Beardwell Construction Ltd	Contractors	Diana	Director	info@beardwell.com	01
42	Benjamin Associates Ltd	Contractors	M Benjamin	Director	info@benjaminassociates.co.uk	01
43	Benning Brothers Limited	Contractors	G Selby	Director	info@bbl-uk.com	01
44	Bermar Building Company Ltd	Contractors	M P Kelly	Director	enquiries@bermarbuilding.co.uk	01
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49	Brant Associates Limited	Construction Law	Ian Brant	Director	ian@brantassociates.com	01

50	Brennan Associates	Surveyors	G Brennan	Director	george@brennan-associates.co.uk	01
51	Brett & Associates	Contractors	Dennis Brett	Director	info@brett-associates.co.uk	02
52	Bridgewater Surveyors	Surveyors	M J Butler	Director	info@bridgewatersurveyors.co.uk	01
53	Briga Consulting Ltd	Consultancy	D J Stockdale	Director	dstockdale@brigaconsulting.com	01
54	Broadstaff Construction Limited	Contractors	D A Broad	Director	accounts@broadstaff.co.uk	01
55	Broham Forecourt Developments Ltd	Contractors	Kevin Porter	Director	forecourts@broham.co.uk	01
56	Building Construction Consultancy Services	Consultancy	K Munn	Director	km@bccs.fsnet.co.uk	01
57	Building Control Solutions	Building Control	R Paine	Director	roger.paine@wokingham.gov.uk	01
58	C A Duquemin Ltd	Contractors	David Dequemin	Director	david@caduquemin.com	01
59	Cadam Construction Ltd	Contractors	Cain A Green	Director	info@cadamconstruction.co.uk	17
60	Calcula Ltd	Consultancy	Liam Perry	Director	enquiries@calcula.co.uk	01
61	Caldew Ltd	Consultancy	J R Aiery	Director	robin.aiery1@btinternet.com	01
62	Camilleri Construction Limited	Contractors	Robert Camilleri	Director	ceri.camilleri@camillerigroup.co.uk	03
63	Carmarthenshire Building Control Unit	Building Control	H L Davies	Director	haldavies@carmarthenshire.gov.uk	01
64	CASL Management Development Limited	Contractors	L G Saunders	Director	enquiries@caslgroup.co.uk	01
65	Cen QS Consulting Ltd	Consultancy	John Peplow	Director	info@cenqsconsulting.co.uk	01
66	Chapman & Chapman Construction Consultancy	Consultancy	Simon Chapman	Director	info@chapmanandchapman.co.uk	07
67	City Build Manchester Ltd	Contractors	Toby Rexstraw	Director	admin@city-build.co.uk	01
68	ClarkBuild Ltd	Contractors	M C Clark	Director	mailbox@clarkbuild.co.uk	01
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70	Clasby Construction Ltd	Contractors	Partick Clasby	Director	pat@clasby.co.uk	01
71	Colinglen Construction	Contractors	James Mc Sorley	Director	info@colinglen.com	02
72	Colmar Construction (Poole) Ltd	Contractors	Nick Cuffe	Director	nick@colmarpoole.com	01
73	Conlon Construction Ltd	Contractors	M G Conlon Richard	Director	enquire@conlonconstruct.co.uk	01
74	Constructing Professionals Ltd	Contractors	Humphrey	Director	r.humphrey@hotmail.co.uk	07
75	Construction Direct UK Limited	Contractors	Gary Durick	Director	gary@constructiondirect.com	01
76	Construction Leaders Club Limited	Contractors	Terry O Mahony	Director	terry@constructionleadersclub.com	

77	Construction Management Training Ltd Copeland Borough Council Building Control Service	Contractors	Dawn Paria	Director	dawn@constructionmanagementtraining.co.uk	01
78	Corniche Builders Limited	Building Control	M A Key	Director	building.control@copeland.gov.uk	01
79	D&J Mew Developments Ltd	Contractors	M G Smith	Director	office@corniche-builders.co.uk	02
80	Damic Building Contractors Ltd	Contractors	Joe Mew	Director	info@mewdevelopments.co.uk	01
81	Darlington Associates Limited	Contractors	Michael Skilton	Director	mickskilton@btopenworld.com	01
82	Datim Building Contractors Ltd	Contractors	Niel Darlington	Director	info@darlingtonassociates.net	01
83	David Aitken MCIOB	Contractors	Tim Barrett	Director	tim@datimbuilding.com	01
84	David Barrington Limited	Contractors	David Atiken	Director	david@lochlie.co.uk	01
85	David Jameson Roofing Services Ltd	Contractors	D J Barrington	Director	barringtonepc@yahoo.co.uk	07
86	Davis Consulting Limited	Contractors	David Jameson	Director	davidjr@djrs.co.uk	02
87	DCH Construction	Consultancy	Owen Davis	Director	odavis@davisconsulting.co.uk	07
88	Diacore Concrete Cutting Ltd	Contractors	D G Cameron	Director	mkennedy@dchconstruct.co.uk	
89	DLB Building Consultancy Services	Contractors	Anthony Sales	Director	info@diacore.co.uk	01
90	E G Carter & Co Ltd	Consultancy	David L Bergin	Director	enquiries@davidlbergin.com	07
91	East Midlands Building Consultancy	Contractors	M E C Carter	Director	mail@egcarter.co.uk	01
92	Edgar Taylor (Buckingham) Ltd	Consultancy	Heather Jones	Director	heather.jones@eastmidlandsbc.com	03
93	Ekins Builders Ltd	Contractors	J R Taylor	Director	building@edgartaylor.co.uk	01
94	Elliott Projects Limited	Contractors	F J Norman	Director	contracts@ekinsbuilders.co.uk	01
95	Ellis Associates Limited	Contractors	D Pearson	Director	partners@elliotts.gb.com	01
96	Ellis Building Contractors Limited	Consultancy	J Ellis	Director	john@ellisassociatesltd.co.uk	05
97	Elliston Steady & Hawes (Bldg)	Contractors	D L Godfrey	Director	admin@ellisbuilders.co.uk	01
98	Every Project Counts Ltd	Contractors	M C Phillips	Director	mark.phillips@eshbuilding.co.uk	01
99	Evolution5 Limited	Contractors	William Maywell	Director	Bill@everyprojectcounts.co.uk	01
100	Findlay Homes Limited	Contractors	Liz Clarke	Director	enquiries@evolution5.co.uk	:0
101	Farrans Construction	Contractors	R G Findlay	Director	findlayhomes@hotmail.com	01
102	Fletcher Homes (Shropshire) Limited	Contractors	Raymond Miller	Director	wrmillar@farrans.com	02
103		Contractors	A C Benfield	Director	homes@fletcherhomes.co.uk	01

104	Flint Construction Limited	Contractors	A R Newman	Director	office@flintconstruction.co.uk	01
105	FORRME Ltd	Contractors	Mark Currie Daniel	Director	info@forrme.co.uk	02
106	G and V Joinery	Contractors	Woodham	Director	daniel@gandvcontracts.co.uk	01
107	G Loosemore & Son Ltd	Contractors	N D Loosemore	Director	loosemorebuilder@btconnect.com	01
108	GCG Development Partnerships Ltd	Contractors	Darren Chadwick	Director	office@gcggroup.co.uk	01
109	Geda Construction Genesis Construction Consultants Limited	Contractors	Damian Murray	Director	dmurray@geda.co.uk	60
110	Geostructures Ltd	Consultancy	E M Eden	Director	genesis.eden@btconnect.com	01
111	Gerry Pounder Associates Ltd	Consultancy	Michael O Meara	Director	enquiries@geostructures.co.uk	01
112	Glendamere Services	Consultancy	Gerry Pounder	Director	info@gpalimited.com	01
113	Godfrey Martin Limited	Consultancy	S Tippins Anthony	Director	glendamere@glendamere.com	01
114	Goldstone Homes Ltd	Contractors	Godfrey	Director	enquiries@godfreymartin.co.uk	01
115	Goodrich Consulting LLP	Contractors	Ivan Over	Director	jon@goldstonehomes.co.uk	01
116	Green Hat Consulting Ltd	Consultancy	R D Goodenough	Director	admin@goodrichllp.co.uk	01
117	Green Project Management Ltd	Consultancy	Andrew Warring	Director	andrew@greenhat-consulting.co.uk	01
118	Greendale Construction Limited	Project Managers	J Greenhalgh	Director	jonathan.greenhalgh@greenpm.co.uk	01
119	Gwynedd Council Building Control	Contractors	R D Hooker	Director	enquiries@greendaleconstruction.com	01
120	Hague Construction Limited	Building Control	A M Jones	Director	buildingcontrol@gwynedd.gov.uk	01
121	Hall Construction	Contractors	P Hague	Director	info@hagueconstruction.co.uk	01
122	Hargreaves Contracting Ltd	Contractors	P A Hall	Director	phall@hallconstruction.co.uk	01
123	Hawk Builders & Shopfitters Ltd	Contractors	Jamie Simons	Director	jamie@hawkgroup.co.uk	01
124	HB Technical Services Limited	Contractors	G M Sweeney	Director	gsweeney@hargreavescontracting.com	01
125	HBD Surveyors Ltd	Consultancy	Tracey Barnes	Director	t.barnes@hbtechnicalservices.com	01
126	Head Projects Building Consultancy Ltd	Surveyors	Deerek Slee	Director	info@hbdsurveyors.co.uk	02
127	Heron Bros Ltd	Consultancy	Antony Birkett	Director	tony.birkett@head-projects.com	01
128	Higgins Construction PLC	Contractors	K G Whan	Director	ken.whan@heronbros.com	02
129	Hilton Abbey Ltd	Contractors	T Sabin S Hilton	Director	info@higginsconstruction.co.uk	02
130		Contractors		Director	sales@hiltonabbey.com	02

131	Hodgson Brothers LLP	Contractors	C J Hodgson	Director	cjh@hbllp.co.uk	01
132	Humphreys & Sons Ltd	Architect	R Humphreys	Director	contact@humphreysandsons.co.uk	01
133	Hurstway Construction Company Limited	Contractors	C P Ditton	Director	admin@hurstwayconstruction.co.uk	01
134	Hutton Construction Limited	Contractors	N Hughes	Director	colchester@hutton-group.co.uk	01
135	I B Project Management	Project Managers	I C Bown	Director	ian@ibprojectmanagement.com	07
136	Inseen Construction Ltd	Contractors	S J Horsley	Director	shorsley@inseen.co.uk	01
137	Intech Property Services Ltd	Contractors	Adam Powell	Director	adam@intechpropertyservices.co.uk	07
138	Invictacut Limited	Contractors	A M Sales	Director	info@invictacut.co.uk	01
139	ISCA Surveying Services Ltd	Surveyors	David Fellows	Director	dave@iscasurveying.co.uk	07
140	Islwyn Pugh Construction Limited	Contractors	C L Pugh	Director	sales@islwynpugh.co.uk	01
141	J Greenwood (Builders) Limited	Contractors	J Greenwood	Director	john.greenwood@jgb.co.uk	01
142	J Owen Associates Limited	Consultancy	J Owen	Director	jowen@joaltd.co.uk	07
143	J. Carpenter Surveyors	Surveyors	Jeremy Carpenter	Director	adeptsafety@yahoo.com	01
144	James Upfold Construction Ltd	Contractors	James Upfold	Director	info@upfoldconstruction.co.uk	01
145	Jenner (Contractors) Ltd	Contractors	Martin Sandall	Director	msandall@jenner-group.co.uk	01
146	John Browning Builders Ltd	Contractors	Carmel Maher	Director	johnbrowningbuilders@btinternet.com	01
147	John Burke Associates	Consultancy	I Carey	Director	office@jba.uk.com	01
148	John Halton Design Ltd	Consultancy	J C Halton	Director	admin@johnhaltondesign.co.uk	01
149	John Wade Groundworks Ltd	Contractors	John Wade	Director	team@wadegroup.org	01
150	Juttland Surveyors Ltd	Surveyors	Harjinder Juttla	Director	info@juttlandsurveyors.co.uk	02
151	K-Net Construction Limited	Contractors	Peter Kent Kevin	Director	peter.kent@k-netconstruction.com	01
152	K&M McLoughlin Decorating Ltd	Contractors	McLoughlin	Director	kevin@kmdecorating.co.uk	02
153	Keith Roberts Projects Limited	Project Managers	K Roberts	Director	kr@krprojects.co.uk	01 :0
154	Kenwood Damp-Proofing PLC	Contractors	G G Petrie	Director	info@kenwoodplc.co.uk	24
155	Kilbury Construction Ltd	Contractors	M J Westbury	Director	sales@kilburyconstruction.co.uk	01
156	Kind & Co (Builders) Limited	Contractors	W S Bassenger	Director	mail@kind-build.com	02
157	Kingfield Developments Limited	Contractors	M G Dickinson	Director	enquiries@kingfield-developments.com	01
158	Kingsmere Construction Ltd	Contractors	D Flanagan	Director	mail@kingsmereconstruction.co.uk	01

159	KLH Architects Ltd	Architects	Alan Howard	Director	klh@klharchitects.com	01
160	KRP Building Consultancy Ltd	Consultancy	Kevin Prior	Director	kevin.prior@tiscali.co.uk	01
161	Kudos Architectural Design and Building Consultants	Consultancy	Cain Green	Director	cgreen@kudosarchitecture.co.uk	07
162	Ladymead Projects	Project Managers	Peter Curtis	Director	petercurtis@ladymeadprojects.com	01
163	Laird Contracts Limited	Contractors	J J Tweedie	Director	construct@lairdcontracts.co.uk	02
164	Landmark Lofts Ltd	Contractors	J Gold	Director	james.gold@landmark-lofts.com	02
165	Leconfield Property Group	Contractors	Andrew De Bertodano	Director	andy@leconfieldpg.com	02
166	Leeming Associates	Consultancy	G Leeming	Director	leemingcqs@btconnect.com	01
167	Limen Construction Limited	Contractors	G Hawkins	Director	graham.hawkins@limen.co.uk	01
168	Lloyd Building Services	Contractors	Anthony Llyod	Director	lloyd.building@gmail.com	
169	London Projects Limited	Project Managers	N J Stuttard	Director	enquiries@londonprojects.co.uk	02
170	M P M H Construction Limited	Contractors	C J Millar	Director	enquiries@mpmhlted.co.uk	01
171	Marfleet Construction Limited	Contractors	I C Pettit	Director	enquiries@marfleetconstruction.co.uk	01
172	Martello Building Consultancy	Consultancy	Andrew Cruttenden	Director	andrewc@martellobc.co.uk	
173	McLaren Construction Ltd	Contractors	R Mortlock	Director	enquiries@mcclarengroup.com	01
174	McMullan Project Management	Project Managers	Ian McMullan	Director	ianmcmullan@virginmedia.com	01
175	Meadowside Building Consultancy	Consultancy	S M Shore	Director	info@meadow-side.com	01
176	M2 Consultancy	Consultancy	M G Willams	Director	enquiries@m2homes.co.uk	01
177	Make Projects Ltd	Project Managers	Michael Teeling	Director	info@makegroup.co.uk	01
178	Mew Developments Ltd	Contractors	Joe Mew	Director	joe@mewdevelopments.co.uk	
179	Michael Dyson Associates Ltd	Contractors	G D Jackson	Director	admin@mdyson.co.uk	01
180	Michael Gerard Consulting Limited	Consultancy	M P Gerrard	Director	info@michael-gerard.co.uk	01
181	Miller Construction Services	Contractors	Keith Miller	Director	keith@millerconstructionservices.co.uk	01
182	Mitchell Building Contractors Limited	Contractors	Harvey Gooch	Director	info@mitchell.je	01
183	MMM Design & Build Ltd	Consultancy	Paul Rafferty	Director	info@mmmdesignandbuild.co.uk	02
184	Morgan Restoration MPA Engineering & Construction Services Ltd	Contractors	B J Morgan	Director	bjm@morganrestoration.co.uk	01
185	Services Ltd	Contractors	Michael Parrett	Director	michael.parrett@ntlworld.com	02

186	Munnings Construction Limited	Contractors		Director	phil.munnings@munningsconstruction.co.uk	4
187	N K S Contracts Ltd	Construction Law	L M Pinker	Director	lee.pinker@nkscontracts.co.uk	01
188	N S J Contract Management Limited	Construction Law	S P Pirouet	Director	nsj@nsj.co.je	01
	Nene Construction Management					
189	Services Ltd	Contractors	C Barnes	Director	admin@nene-cms.co.uk	01
190	Neville Special Projects Ltd	Contractors	I C Trumper	Director	enquiries@nevillespecialprojects.co.uk	01
191	NJC Services Limited	Consultancy	N J Beynon	Director	beynon@njcservices.co.uk	02
192	NWP Consult Limited	Consultancy	Lee Hudon	Director	lee.hudson@nwpcconsult.co.uk	
193	O & P Construction Services Limited	Contractors	R Mitchell	Director	mail@opconstruction.co.uk	01
194	O'Hare & McGovern Ltd	Consultancy	E O'Hare	Director	carbanehouse@ohareandmcgovern.com	02
195	O'Neill Building Services Ltd	Contractors	L O'Neill	Director	liam@oneillbuildingservices.com	02
						07
196	O'Neill Construction	Contractors	Terence O'Neill	Director	info@oneillconstructionni.co.uk	51
197	OLF Construction Ltd	Contractors	Michael Barnett	Director	office@olfconstruction.com	02
	Omnis Construction And Project					
198	Management	Contractors	M D Worrall	Director	martin.worrall@omnisconstruction.com	01
199	On Site Services	Contractors	S Parry	Director	enquiries@onsiteservicesuk.com	01
	P. Mercer Construction Support Services					
200	Limited	Contractors	P Mercer	Director	pm@pmercer.com	07
201	Pacific Building Ltd	Contractors	Brain Gallacher	Director	admin@pacificbuilding.co.uk	01
						+4
202	Parias Commercial Interiors Limited	Contractors	Dawn Parias	Director	dawn@pariasinteriors.com	21
203	Party Wall Matters 1996 Ltd	Surveyors	Ken Power	Director	ken.power@partywallmatters1996.co.uk	02
204	Paul Ennis & Company Limited	Surveyors	B P ennis	Director	office@paulennis.co.uk	01
205	Pavilion Homes (Sussex) Ltd	Contractors	P Scourfield	Director	developments@pavilionhomes.co.uk	01
206	PBS Construction (NE) Ltd	Contractors	P B Smurthwaite	Director		01
207	Pexhurst Services Limited	Contractors	A M Vella	Director	info@pexhurst.co.uk	01
208	Pinnacle Professional Services	Contractors	K W Ryder	Director	info@pinnacle-safety.co.uk	01
209	Pike Partnership	Contractors	C S Pike	Director	pp@pikepartnership.co.uk	01
210	Pinner and Sons Ltd	Contractors	Mark Pinner	Director	mark@pinnerandsons.com	01

211	PLK Design	Consultancy	P Kennedy	Director	info@plkdesign.com	01
212	Power Building Services Ltd	Contractors	Jacqui Power	Director	jacqui@powerbuilding.co.uk	01
213	Powys Building Standards Consultancy	Consultancy	Stephen Andrews	Director	stephen.andrews@powys.gov.uk	01
214	Primary Consulting Ltd	Consultancy	N J Dernie	Director	mail@njdernie.net	01
215	Principal Surveying & Project Services Ltd	Surveyors	Lee Webster	Director	info@psandps.co.uk	01
216	Pro-Plan Projects Ltd	Project Managers	D J Forsyth	Director	proplanprojects@btconnect.com	01
217	Project Eleven Ltd	Project Managers	Neil Gleeson	Director	enquiries@projectltd.co.uk	01
218	Project Management Services (South Coast) Limited	Project Managers	R Newham	Director	ricnewnham@onwight.net	01
219	Property & Capital Projects, Medway Council	Project Managers	Robert Dennis	Director	rob.dennis@medway.gov.uk	01
220	QMAC Construction Ltd	Contractors	R M Quinn	Director	info@qmacconstruction.com	02
221	Quantum Construction Limited	Contractors	D G Ghallager	Director	info@quantumconstruction.co.uk	01
222	Quentin Jones Construction Ltd	Contractors	Mark Jones	Director	info@quentinjones.co.uk	01
223	R G Construction Limited	Contractors	D Goldiman	Director	thegodlimans@tiscali.co.uk	01
224	R.V.Dart (Builders) Ltd	Contractors	A J Stringfellow	Director	enquiries@rvdart.co.uk	01
225	R.W. Armstrong & Sons Ltd	Contractors	S Lewis	Director	info@rwarmstrong.co.uk	01
226	Rand Associates Consultancy Services Ltd	Consultancy	Stephen Downing Robin	Director	sdowning@rand-associates.co.uk	01
227	RBC Surveyors	Surveyors	Muggeridge	Director	info@rbcsurveyors.co.uk	01
228	RED Construction Group Ltd	Contractors	Ian Hopkinson	Director	ihopkinson@redconstruction.co.uk	02
229	Redec Refurbishment	Contractors	Cristopher Moore	Director		01
230	Redgate Construction Limited	Contractors	J Jarvis	Director	aj@redgateconstruction.com	01
231	Reeve Property Restoration	Contractors	M A Reeve	Director	postmaster@reeveproperty.co.uk	01
232	Regent Development Ltd	Contractors	M slater	Director	info@regentgroup.co.uk	01
233	Regional Surveying Services Ltd (RSS Ltd)	Surveyors	B Binfield	Director	bwb@rsonline.co.uk	01
234	Restore London Limited	Contractors	John Rushworth	Director	john.rushworth@restore-london.co.uk	02
235	Richard Coles Builders	Contractors	R T G Colew	Director	richard@rcoles.co.uk	01

236	Richard Ward (Oxford) Ltd	Contractors	Jonathan Ward	Director	jw@richardward-oxford.co.uk	01
237	Richwell Construction Ltd	Contractors	D Richards	Director	info@richwell.uk.com	02
238	RNL Building Consultancy Ltd	Consultancy	R Leahy	Director	rnleahy1@googlemail.com	01
239	Robert W Le Page Architects	Architects	R W Le Page	Director	architect@rwlp.co.gg	01
240	ROK Construction Ltd	Contractors	G Morrisons	Director	g.morrison@roklimited.je	01
241	Rowlinson Constructions Ltd	Contractors	Stebe Weir	Director	enquiries@rowcon.co.uk	01
242	Ryans CDM Ltd	H&S Consultants	GPP Ryan	Director	gordon.ryan@ryanscdm.co.uk	01
243	Sandwood Design & Build	Consultancy	J G Lennon	Director	enquiries@sandwood.co.uk	02
244	Savvy Construction Limited	Contractors	Jon Peart	Director	info@group-savvy.co.uk	
245	SciTech Engineering Ltd	Consultancy	D I Grant	Director	sales@scitech.com	01
246	Scofield Building Services Ltd	Contractors	P A Scofield	Director	info@scofieldbuildingsurveying.com	01
247	SDC Builders Ltd	Contractors	R Ebsworth	Director	rob.ebsworth@sdco.co.uk	01
248	Shiplake Homes Ltd	Contractors	Jon Moulds	Director	jon@shiplakehomes.co.uk	07
249	Shorelands Building Consultancy Ltd	Consultancy	R Johnson	Director	mj@sbcpoole.eclipse.co.uk	01
250	Site Sage	Contractors	D Brett	Director	info@sitesage.co.uk	02
251	Skeer Environmental Surveying Solutions Ltd	Surveyors	G Skeer	Director	info@sess-surveying.co.uk	01
252	Snape Munroe Commercial Building Consultancy	Contractors	A D W Snape	Director	andrew.snape@snapemunroe.co.uk	15
253	Spetisbury Construction Limited	Contractors	Justin Ives	Director	enquiries@spetisburyconstruction.co.uk	01
254	St Albans Basement	Contractors	L Dower	Director	ldower@stalbansbasement.co.uk	17
255	Stephen Russell Construction Limited	Contractors	S R Rockingham	Director	steve@stephenrussellconstruction.co.uk	01

APPENDIX A-3
LAYOUT OF DATABASE

S. No.	Title	Author	Source	Management	Assessment	Model
1	A guide to the project management	Project Management Institute	Project Management..	x		
2	Applying a Risk Management Process	Tummala, V.M.R & Burchett, J	Journal of Construction..	x		x
3	Assessment of Risks Management	Al- Salman, Abdullah M. Al-M	Journal of Construction..		x	
4	COBRA: A Hybrid Method for Risk	Lionel C. Briand, Khaled El Em	Journal of Construction..		x	
5	Construction Risk Insurance Practices	Farooqui, R.U., Gazdar, U., An	International Conference..	x		
6	Evaluating Risk Management Practices	Tauha Hussain Ali, Saifullah Q	International Conference..	x		
7	ICRAM-1: Model for International	Makarand Hastak, Aury Shak	American Society of Civil..			x
8	International Project Risk Assessment	John Walewski, G. Edward Gil	Journal of Construction		x	x
9	Learning from Risks: A Tool for	I. Dikmen, M.T. Birgonul, C. A	Automation in Construct..		x	
10	Project Based Management	Turner J.R	McGraw Hill	x	x	
11	Project risk analysis and management	Chris Chapman	Intern. journal of project..	x		x
12	Project Risk Management in Hong	Shen L.Y	Intern. Journal of Project..	x		
13	M. Project risk management in Quality	Lyons, T. & Skitmore	Intern. Journal of Project..	x		
14	Risk Analysis and Management	Akintola S akintoye, Malcolm J	Intern. journal of project..	x	x	
15	Risk Analysis in Fixed-price design	Ahmet Oztas Onder Okmen	Intern. Journal of building..		x	
16	Risk Analysis in Project Management	John Raftery	E & FN SPON publishers..		x	
17	Risk Assessment in Construction	Osama Ahmed Jannadi, Salma	Journal of Construction..		x	
18	Risk assessment and management	Deviprasadh, A	College Of Engineering..	x	x	
19	Risk Management and Construction	Flanagan, R& Norman G	Blackwell Scientific pub..	x		
20	Risk Management Implementation	Zadeh, M.G	University Of Technol..	x		
21	Risk management in building process	Skorupka	Association for the adva..	x		
22	Risk Management in the Chinese	Wenzhe Tang, Maoshan Qian	Journal of Construction..	x		
23	Risk Management of BOT Projects	Sudong Ye, Robert L. K. Tion	Construction Management	x		
24	Risk Management Perceptions and	Roozbeh Kangari	American Society of Civil..	x		
25	Risk Management Model for the	Ahmed, S.M., Mitrani, J.D., A	Florida International Univ..			x
26	Systematic Risk Management Approach	Jamal F. Al-Bahar1 and Keith	American Society of Civil..	x		

APPENDIX A-4

SUMMARY OF LITERATURE

Following are the details of the literature that have been reviewed. The table highlights the title, name of author, source and year of publication and moreover it provides a brief abstract to all the papers sequentially.

Table A-4.1: Summary of papers

S N	Title	Author(s)	Source	Year of Publication	Abstract
1	Risk analysis and management in construction industry	Akintola S. Akintoye & Malcolm J. Macleod.	International journal of project management.	1997	This paper explains the understanding of the construction industry of risk associated with its operations and risk analysis and risk control strategies on

					the basis of a structured questionnaire survey of general contractor and project management practises.
2	Risk analysis in "fixed-price design-build construction projects".	Ahmet Oztas & onder okmen.	Building and Environment .	2003	This research presents a literature survey on risk, risk management and design-build issues. To propose a schedule and cost risk analysis model, and to illustrate the applicability of these models in scheduling and cost analysis. Estimation through a case study of a' fixed-price design-build construction project.
3	Development of risk Management framework.	Dr. Syed M. Ahmed, Professor Jose D. Mitrani, Salman Azhar, Julio R. Roldan..	Department Florida International University Miami, Florida.	2001	This research project, on the basis of questionnaire survey and interviews, studies the critical risks faced by the Florida construction industry and assesses the latest risk management activities of building contractors and subcontractors in the State of Florida.
S	Title	Author(s)	Source	Year of Publication	Abstract
4	Systematic risk management approach For construction projects.	Jamal F. Al-Bahar1 and Keith C.Crandall.	America society of civil engineers.	1990	This paper introduces a new model of risk, entitled Risk Management Scheme of Building (CRMS). This template offers A systematic, logical, and structured method that allows contractors to define, The study and risk control of a construction project.
5	Assessment of Risks	Al-Salman, A.A.	Construction Engineering	2005	The thesis presents the findings of a

	Management Perception and Practices of Construction Contractors in Saudi Arabia.		and Management Department of King Fahad University, Saudi Arabia.		research review on the evaluation of Risk management of building contractors in the construction sector Construction threats in Saudi Arabia Focuses on risk allocation risk importance and risk effects on a construction project.
6	Evaluating Risk Management Practices in the Pakistani Construction Industry: The Current State of Play.	Tauha Hussain Ali, Rodney A. Stewart.	International Conference on Construction.	2007	This study aims at exposing the current state of use of structured risk management practises in Pakistan. A questionnaire survey tool was implemented, in particular, to define current processes and procedures used to identify, analyse and mitigate risks to project construction.
7	COBRA: A Hybrid Method for Software Cost Estimation, Benchmarking, and Risk Assessment	Lionel C. Briand, Khaled El Emam, Frank Bomarius	International Software Engineering Research Network (ISERN).	1997	We are, in this article, Present a methodology for cost estimation that integrates aspects Algorithmic and experiential approaches (referred to as) COBRA, Price Estimation, Benchmarking and Risk Assessment).
8	Project risk analysis and management PRAM the generic process	Chris Chapman.	International journal of project management.	1997	This paper outlines a method of project risk management originally developed for the Project Managers Association (APM).
S. N	Title	Author(s)	Source	Year of Publication	Abstract
9	Risk Assessment And Management In construction Projects	A Deviprasadh	Department	2007	This study seeks to identify and assess the risks and establish a system of risk management that can

					be applied in India by investors/developers/contractors while contracting construction work. The survey questionnaire is intended to investigate the cross-sectional behavioural pattern of the construction hazards of the building industry.
10	Learning from Risks: A Tool for Post-Project Risk Assessment.	M.T. Dikmenl C. Birgonul, J.H.M. Tah and G. Aouad.	Automation in Construction.	2008	For risk management, a learning-based approach is introduced in this paper. In a method to make life simpler has been developed to apply this approach in practise. Phase of cycle risk management
11	Construction Risk Insurance Practices In Pakistan	Rizwan U. Farooqui, Farrukh Arif, Uneb Gazder & Nida Azhar.	International	2008	The study aims to illustrate the latest insurance practises of the Pakistani construction industry. In this respect, a distinctive approach to targeting insurance firms would be used for data collection.
12	Icram-1:Model For International Construction Risk Assessment.	Makarand Hastak1 and Aury Shaked	Journal of Management in Engineering	2000	The International Construction Risk Assessment Model (ICRAM-1) helps the customer in assessing by extending operations in a foreign market the possible risk involved in expanding Macro sector risk analysis and project stages.
13	Risk Assessment in Construction.	Osama Ahmed Jannadi & Sheikh Almishari.	Journal of Construction Engineering and Management.	2003	A custom risk assessor ~RAMS! Created and computerised To assess the risk associated with a

S N	Title	Author(s)	Source	Year of Publication	Abstract
					specific operation and the element of justification for the proposed solution.
14	Risk management perceptions and trends of U.S construction	Roozbeh Kangari.	Journal of Construction Engineering and Management .	1995	Big U.S. construction firms' current attitude towards risk is discussed in this paper and decides. How building risk management is performed by these contractors.
15	Project risk management in the Queensland engineering construction industry: a survey.	Terry Lyons and Martin Skitmore	International Journal of Project Management .	2004	Survey result to find out the risk management technique used in all over the world
16	Project risk management in Hong Kong.	L. Y Shen.	International journal of project management	1997	Risks and risks delayed by the most extreme project successful strategies to mitigate these risks are known to be in Hong Kong.
17	Risk management in building project.	Dr. Dariusz Skorupka	Association for the advancement of cost engineering international. (AACE)	2003	This research paper reveals new loss avoidance and hence cost reduction opportunities for a construction company
18	Risk Management in the Chinese Construction Industry.	Wenzhe Tang, Maoshan Qiang, Colin F. Duffield, David M. Young & Youmei Lu.	Journal of Construction Engineering and Management	2007	The Chinese industry's survey on the importance of project risks, risk management implementation Techniques, the state of the risk management process and the problems facing risk management
19	Applying a Risk Management Process (RMP) to manage cost risk for an EHV transmission line	V M Rao Tummala & John F Burchett	International Jnt	1999	An RMP is used in this paper to formulate a risk management model to determine the risks associated with a

	project				(EHV) transmission line's project cost. As seen in this article, in evaluating and taking corrective measures over several project life cycle cycles, this model can be effectively applied.
20	International Project Risk Assessment (see appendix B-13): Methods, Procedures, and Critical Factors	John walewski & G.Edward Gibson.	Center construction industry studies, University Of Texas, Austin.	2003	Risk investigation of study Procedures of evaluation for foreign building programmes. To better understand risk assessment and evaluation methods and to strengthen them.
S N	Title	Author(s)	Source	Year of Publication	Abstract
21	The effect of concession period design on completion risk management of BOT projects.	Sudong Ye & Robert L. K. Tiong	Construction Management and Economics.	2003	This article extensively addresses the forms of compromises (build-operate-transfer-a) systems for BOT projects Form of Privately Funded Project for Infrastructure) and Assesses the efficacy of various concession periods
22	Risk management implementation in the Iranian construction industry from contractors' perspective.	Mostafa ghadak zadeh.	University Of Technology, Malaysia.	2010	The goal of this study is to enhance the implementation of risk management within contracting firms in the Iranian construction industry by analysing contractors' perceptions of risk management.
23	RASM: Risk-Based projects Auditing selecting methodology for large scale program.	Zacharias. O, Mylonakis. J & Ankounis. D. T	International Research Journal of Finance and Economics	2007	RASM, a risk-based Auditing Selection Approach project for large scale projects, is introduced in this paper. In the context of large-scale projects, RASM is focused on risk factor

					analysis that recognises a large number of risk factors.
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TOPIC FROM BOOKS

S N	Title	Author(s)	Publisher	Edition & year of publication	Topics
1	Risk management and construction	Roger Flanagan & George Norman	Blackwell Scientific publishers Ltd.	First edition (1993)	Risk identification, classification, types of risk, risk analysis, risk response, risk attitude, Monte Carlo simulation. Sensitivity analysis and types of contract.
2	PMBOK Guide: A guide to the project management body of knowledge.	Project Management Institute.	Project Management Institute.	(2000) edition.	Danger managing of programmes, preparation for RM, detection, qualitative & quantitative analysis, planning of responses, monitoring & control.
3	Risk analysis in project management	John Raftery	E & FN SPON Publishers	Second edition (1994)	Overview of risk management, identification, analysis, response, Different techniques of assessment of risk.
4	Handbook of Project-Based Management	J. Rodney turner	McGraw Hill	Third edition (1999)	Project Management Principals, System for Risk Management, Risk Identification, Risk Evaluation, Risk Analysis and Task Allocations.

APPENDIX B-1

RISK ATTITUDE

The terms 'averse', 'searching', 'accommodating' or 'neutral' speak to a major, discernment-driven, preferred reaction to vulnerability. This phrase represents the working sense of *Risk Mentality/Risk Attitude*, which is a decision taken by a particular person or person. Gathering even with a specific dangerous circumstance, and which is influenced by a scope of perceptual components.

Plate B-1.1: Risk Attitude Spectrum

Names such as risk averse, risk seeking, risk tolerant/ lenient and risk neutral are useful attributes to reflect individuals' elective roles when faced with vulnerability. In spite of the fact that names give important shorthand, their utilization ought not to shroud the way that hazard mentality exists on a constant range, as shown in Plate B-1.1. There are boundless assortments of potential reactions to chance which can be shown by a specific individual or gathering, yet the four essential positions permit a summed up conversation of the theme. These four key danger mentalities are summed up in Plate B-1.2.

Term	Definition
Risk averse	Uncomfortable with uncertainty, desire to avoid or reduce threats and exploit opportunities to remove uncertainty. Would be unhappy with an uncertain outcome.
Risk seeking	Comfortable with uncertainty, no desire to avoid or reduce threats or to exploit opportunities to remove uncertainty. Would be happy with an uncertain outcome.
Risk tolerant	Tolerant of uncertainty, no strong desire to respond to threats or opportunities in any way. Could tolerate an uncertain outcome if necessary.
Risk neutral	Uncomfortable with uncertainty in the long term so prepared to take whatever short-term actions are necessary to deliver a certain long-term outcome.

Plate B-1.2: Definitions of Basic Risk Attitude

Moreover, when choices must be made under states of vulnerability, every one of these impacts is significant, on the grounds that they drive the impression of danger. Risk attitude is the picked reaction of an individual or gathering to vulnerability that is important, driven by discernment. Subsequently, the capacity to comprehend hazard demeanour offers a key to open the secrets of powerful dynamic where risk is included. Understanding risk attitude is a basic achievement factor which advances powerful dynamic in hazardous circumstances, as appeared in Plate B-1.3.

Plate B-1.3: Risk attitude as a CSF for effective risk management

The lack of this awareness, however, is not neutral, but provides a vital cause of failure, leading to decreased efficacy.

APPENDIX B-2

TYPE OF CONTRACTS

The Design-Bid-Build Approach

When implementing this sort of contractual association, the proprietor utilizes an architect who at first readies the plans and details, and later during the development stage the fashioner may embrace assessment, checking, or control. Plate B-2.1 clarifies this methodology. For the development cycle, the proprietor builds up an agreement with a solitary general temporary worker who completes the obligation of developing the task. In any case, the overall temporary worker as a rule subcontracts the colossal measure of the work to singular subcontractors. However, the legitimate authoritative connections of the subcontractors are straightforwardly with the overall contractual worker. Subsequently, the overall temporary worker is dependable to the proprietor for all the work, including the subcontracted works. The plan offer form approach can be actualized utilizing single amount contract, a unit value contract, or an expense in addition to charge contract. In some development projects mixes of these agreements might be used.

Plate B-2.1: Design-Bid-Build Approach

The Design-Build Approach

In the design-build approach, the whole venture stages from beginning through plan and development are relegated to one association. Through this kind of authoritative relationship, the constructor is an overall temporary worker with single firm control, all things considered. Ordinarily, under design-build contracts; development can promptly be performed under a staged development program to limit project term. This methodology can be utilized under different sorts of agreements, including single amount, and cost-in addition to expense contract. Plate B-2.2 clarifies this methodology. As a synopsis, the plan assemble approach includes the presence of a solitary association that is answerable for both plan and development, along with strength subcontractors, and can be actualized with single amount, cost-in addition to expense, or in some cases unit value plan development contract.

Plate B- 2.2: Design-Build Approach

Lump-Sum Contracts

In single amount gets, the temporary worker consents to play out the work at a foreordained cost that incorporates his benefit. This sort of agreements has for quite some time been utilized in the seriously offer, and here and there arranged, general agreement. Under this agreement by and large the overall contractual worker subcontracts the majority of the work to claim to fame contract based workers under single amount subcontracts.

Unit Price Contracts

Unit value contracts are like singular amount, yet in this kind of agreements the costs of the predefined units of work are fixed, and the complete expense to the proprietor will change with the real amounts of units set up. Unit value contracts are best applied where the subtleties and general character of the work are known yet the amounts are liable to change inside sensible cut-off points.

Cost-Plus-Fee Contracts

Under this sort of agreements, the temporary worker consents to play out the work for a fixed or variable charge covering benefit and home office expenses, and all field costs will be estimated at genuine expenses. Additionally, considered charges are regularly reliant on the size and intricacy of the task.

To end with, changing the danger rating of a development project as indicated by the authoritative understanding is subject to the danger natural with each approach. To envision the level of danger for the three distinctive agreement types, Plate B-2.3 analyses the diverse agreement types as per their danger level for both the proprietor and the temporary worker. The figure shows that, the most unsafe agreement type for the contractual worker to work with is the single amount contract. This is on the grounds that under this kind of agreements the contractual worker consents to play out the work which will be led later on with a value

that is fixed in right now. However, the development cycle is engaged with numerous factors that may have incredible impact on the development cost. Then again, the most un-dangerous agreement type is cost-in addition to charge; where the temporary worker has disposed of the danger expected in fixed value contracting as a compromise for a lower ensured expense/fee.

Degree Of Risk	Owner					
	Contractor					
	Contract Type	Lump Sum (No Changes in Contract)	Lump Sum (Some Changes in Contract)	Unit Price	Cost-Plus Fix-Fee	Cost-Plus Percent-Fee

Plate B-2.3: The Degree of Risk Associated with the Different Contract Types

APPENDIX B-3

RISK MANAGEMENT STANDARDS, GUIDELINES AND PROFESSIONAL BODIES

RISK MANAGEMENT STANDARDS AND GUIDELINES

Reference/title	Standards body/publisher	Date
AS/NZS 4360:2004, Risk Management	Standards Australia, Homebush NSW 2140, Australia, and Standards New Zealand, Wellington 6001, New Zealand	2004
BS 6079-3:2000, Project Management – Part 3: Guide to the Management of Business-related Project Risk	British Standards Institution, London, UK	2000
BS 8444-3: 1996 (previously issued as 300-3-9:1995), Risk Management – Part 3: Guide to Risk Analysis of Technological Systems	British Standards Institution, London, UK	1996
CAN/CSA-Q850-97, Risk Management Guideline for Decision Makers	Canadian Standards Association, Ontario, Canada	1997
CP142 Operational Risk Systems and Controls	Financial Services Authority, London, UK	2002
IEEE 1540-2001, Standard for Software Life Cycle Processes – Risk Management	The Institute of Electrical and Electronic Engineers, Inc., USA	2001
ISO 14001: 2004, Environmental Management Systems – Requirements with Guidelines for Use	International Organization for Standardization, Geneva, Switzerland	2004
ISO/IEC 17799:2005, Information Technology – Security Techniques – Code of Practice for Information Security Management	International Organization for Standardization/International Electrotechnical Commission, Geneva, Switzerland	2005
IEC 62198:2001, Project Risk Management – Application Guidelines	International Electrotechnical Commission, Geneva, Switzerland	2001
JIS Q 2001:2001 (E), Guidelines for Development and Implementation of Risk Management System	Japanese Standards Association, Tokyo, Japan	2001
PAS 56:2003, Guide to Business Continuity Management	British Standards Institution, London, UK	2003
PD 6668:2000, Managing Risk for Corporate Governance	British Standards Institution, London, UK	2000

PD ISO/IEC Guide 73:2002, Risk Management – Vocabulary – Guidelines for Use in Standards	British Standards Institution, London, UK	2002
A Guide to the Project Management Body of Knowledge (PMBok®), 3 rd edn., ch.11 Project risk management	Project Management Institute, Philadelphia, PA, USA.	2004
A Risk Management Standard	Institute of Risk Management (IRM), Association of Insurance and Risk Managers (AIRMIC) and National Forum for Risk Management in the Public Sector (ALARM), London, U.K.	2002
Continuous Risk Management Guidebook	Software Engineering Institute (SEI), Carnegie Mellon University, USA	1996
Enterprise Risk Management – Integrated Framework	The Committee of Sponsoring Organizations of the Treadway Commission, USA	2004
Guidelines for Environmental Risk Assessment and Management	DETR, Environment Agency and IEH/The Stationery Office, London, UK	2000
Guidelines on Risk Issues	The Engineering Council, London, UK	1995
Management of Risk – Guidance for Practitioners	UK Office of Government Commerce (OGC)/The Stationery Office, London, UK	2002
Project Risk Analysis & Management (PRAM) Guide, 2 nd edn.	Association for Project Management / APM Publishing, High Wycombe, Bucks, UK	2004
Risk Analysis and Management for Projects (RAMP) 2 nd edn.	Institution of Civil Engineers, Faculty of Actuaries and Institute of Actuaries/Thomas Telford, London, UK	2005

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ate B-3.1: Risk Management Standards and Guidelines

RISK MANAGEMENT PROFESSIONAL BODIES

Professional body	Web address
Association for Project Management Risk Management Specific Interest Group (APM Risk SIG)	http://www.eurolog.co.uk/APMRiskSIG
Association of Insurance and Risk Managers (AIRMIC)	http://www.AIRMIC.com
European Institute of Risk Management (EIRM)	http://www.EIRM.com
Federation of European Risk Management Associations (FERMA)	http://www.ferma-asso.org
Global Association of Risk Professionals (GARP)	http://www.GARP.com
Institute of Risk Management (IRM)	http://www.theIRM.org
International Association of Contract and Commercial Managers (IACCM) Business Risk Working Group	http://www.IACCM.com/risk.php
International Council on Systems Engineering Risk Management Working Group (INCOSE RMWG)	http://www.INCOSE.org
Project Management Institute (PMI) Risk Management Specific Interest Group (PMI Risk SIG)	http://www.RiskSIG.com
Risk Management Association (RMA)	http://www.RMAhq.org
Society for Risk Analysis (SRA)	http://www.sra.org

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ate B-3.2: Risk Management Professional Bodies

APPENDIX B-4

TOOLS AND TECHNIQUES OF RISK IDENTIFICATION

Assumption analysis	Examination of vulnerabilities and weaknesses	Prompt lists
Benchmarking	Expert opinion	Prototyping
Brainstorming	Fault tree analysis	Questionnaires
Case and effect diagrams	Flow charts	Risk assessment workshops
Checklists	Hazard and opportunity studies (HAZOP)	Root cause analysis
Constraints analysis	Historical data	Scenario analysis
Delphi technique	Incident investigation	Stakeholder analysis
Diagramming techniques	Influence diagrams	Structured interviews
Documentation reviews	Interviewing	SWOT analysis
Evaluation of other projects	Lessons learned	System engineering techniques
Event tree analysis	Nominal group technique	System analysis
Examination of past risk experience in similar organizations	Peer review	Taxonomies
Examination of past risk experience in the organization	Personal observation	Technology readiness level
	Previous experience	Testing and modeling
	Project monitoring	

Plate B-4.1: Consolidated list of Tools and Techniques of Risk Identification

APPENDIX B-5

Failure Mode Effective Analysis (FMEA)

A FMEA is a simple to utilize yet amazing favourable to dynamic designing quality instrument that aids the recognizable proof and countering of feeble focuses in the early plan period of items and cycles. While the accentuation of this report is on unique situating (DP) frameworks, FMEA strategies can be applied to any framework, regardless of whether applied to land, ocean or air based gear or frameworks, in which it is required that "no single disappointment will cause a complete disappointment of the framework or cycle". It is regularly characterized as "a deliberate cycle for recognizing expected plan and cycle disappointments before they happen, with the aim to kill them or limit the danger related with them".

FMEA Process

- 1. List the steps of the main cycle in the primary section.** These can come from the most notable placed items in your list of risk occasions.
- 2. For each cycle phase, list the possible disappointment mode:** At the end of the day, figure out how this phase or information of the cycle could turn out badly.
- 3. List the implications of this mode of dissatisfaction:** The effect of the case
- 4. Evaluate how serious this effect is:** 1 is not extreme at all and 10 are extremely serious. Similarly, make this "your own" positioning structure and try not to try to replicate it from a manuscript.
- 5. Identify the reasons for the disappointment in mode/impact:** and score it as the impacts have been made in the event portion. This time, we are determining how likely this explanation is to occur, as the name suggests. Thus, it is extremely unlikely that 1 technique will eventually happen and 10 techniques are required to occur continuously.
- 6. Define the controls set up in order to identify the issue** and determine its feasibility in the discovery segment. Here, a score of 1 would mean we have amazing controls, and 10

would mean we don't have any controls or incredibly poor controls. If a SOP is noted here, you should take note of the SOP number (a powerless monitor as I would like to think).

7. Multiply the magnitude, event, and discovery and store numbers: this opportunity in the RPN section (hazard needs number). This is the key number used to understand where the group can concentrate first. We had a magnitude of 10 (extreme) in the off chance, frequency of 10 (constantly occurs)

8. Order by RPN number and remember the most fundamental problems: The person should choose where to focus first at that point.

9. Assign complex operations to capable individuals: In addition, make sure that the date is included when this task is contingent on completion.

10. Re-score the event and venue after activities have been completed. We would not adjust the severity score most of the time, even if the client concludes this, it is certifiably not a serious problem.

This informative supplement likewise shows the work sheet and the portrayal of components in worksheets for conveying our FMEA technique.

Work Sheet for FMEA

Worksheet No.	Date	Compiled By		
Main System	System	Subsystem		
Reference Drawing:				
1 Code/Ref.				
2 Item				
3 Function				
4 Operational Mode				
5 Failure Modes				
6 Failure Causes				
7 Failure Effects: Component/Subsystem/ System				
8 Failure Detection				
9 Compensating Provisions				
10 Testing				
11 Remarks				
12 Severity Class				

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late B-5.1: Work Sheet for FMEA

Elements of FMEA Worksheet

Worksheet ID	Discrete number assigned to the worksheet.
Main System/System/ Sub-System:	A brief description of the parts of the system under study broken down into levels.
Reference Drawing:	Number of the drawing under analysis.
1 Code/Ref.	A serial number or reference designation identification number for each item is assigned for traceability purposes and entered on the worksheet.
2 Item	The name or nomenclature of the item or system function being analyzed for failure mode and effects is listed.
3 Function	Concise statement of the function performed by the hardware item.
4 Operation Mode	Operational mode in which the failure occurs.
5 Failure Modes	The predictable failure modes for each systems level analyzed will be identified. Potential failure modes will be determined by examination of item outputs and functional outputs identified in applicable block diagrams and schematics.
6 Failure Causes	The most probable causes associated with the assumed failure mode will be identified and described. Since a failure mode may have more than one cause, all probable independent causes for each failure mode will be identified.
7 Failure Effects	<p>The consequences of each assumed failure mode on item operation, function, or status will be identified, evaluated, and recorded. The failure under consideration may affect several systems levels in addition to the systems level under analysis; therefore, "component", "subsystem", and "system" effects will be evaluated.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Component</u>. Component effects concentrate specifically on the impact an assumed failure mode has on the operation and function of the item in the systems level under consideration. The consequences of each assumed failure affecting the item is described along with any second-order effects which may result. • <u>Subsystem</u>. Subsystem effects concentrate on the effect an assumed failure has on the operation and function of the items in the next and higher systems levels above the systems level under consideration. The consequences of each assumed failure affecting the next higher systems level will be described. • <u>System</u>. System effects evaluate and define the total effect an assumed failure has on the operation, function, or status of the main system.
8 Failure Detection	A description of the methods by which occurrence of the failure mode is detected by the operator will be recorded. The failure detection means, such as visual, alarm devices, or none, will be identified.
9 Compensating Provisions:	The compensating provisions, either equipment redundancy, control system response, or operator action, which circumvent or mitigate the effect of the failure.
10 Testing	Description of any special testing required with respect to the failure mode and/or its consequences.
11 Remarks	Additional field in which any remarks can be made regarding recommendations or other considerations.
12 Severity Classification	Severity classification based on the impact of the failure on DP capability. The severity classification can be composed of three elements: 1. Severity Level; 2. Operator Fault Management; 3. Redundancy Limitation. (See text)

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late B-5.2: Elements of FMEA worksheet

APPENDIX B-6

The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)

Most testing of programming occurs at a generally low level. Checking the individual techniques of an application for functional consistency is one model. Nonetheless, there should be some substantial research at an extremely elevated level, for instance, deciding whether a current form is essentially preferable by and large over a past form. In this segment a ground-breaking method called the scientific order measure that will empower client to perform significant level quality investigation of client programming frameworks.

The most ideal approach to delineate where headed is with a solid model. Assume clients are building up an item that looks for records across a nearby organization. Client need to know whether the current form is preferable in general over the past forms, and provided that this is true, how much better? Contrasting the general nature of the works with one another isn't so natural since client need to consider numerous ascribes, for example, execution, usefulness, etc. Utilizing the strategies clarification in the current month's segment will empower to figure measurements like those appeared in **Plate B6.1:**

Performance			Functionality			Overall
	Start-up	File Save	User Interface	Database	Network	
Construction A	0.648	0.571	0.443	0.639	0.638	0.531
Construction B	0.230	0.286	0.387	0.274	0.273	0.329
Construction C	0.122	0.143	0.170	0.087	0.089	0.140

Plate B6.1: Multi Criteria Quality Analysis

On the off chance that client look at the table in PlateB6-1user will see that the general nature of each form comprises of a presentation property and usefulness quality. Every one of these traits is made out of sub credits: Start-up and File Save on account of execution, Because of the utility of the user interface, database, and network.

The method to be shown is completely adaptable and can be tailored with quite a few sub-credits to quite a few ascribes. The general quality calculation Construction A is 0.531 for the current form and the general standard for the two previous forms is 0.329 and 0.140,

respectively. in view of the fabricated inspection details that will appear in the corresponding areas. How to decode these consistency metrics later will be revealed, but it is enough for the moment to say that larger numbers are better. Customers have a truly solid sign along these lines that the present form is entirely in a way that is better than the previous two forms. For each type, the general quality measurements depend on the quality measurements for each property. In this model, Construction A is best at 0.648 for start-up execution, Construction B is subsequent at 0.230, and Construction C is most outrageously bad at 0.122.

It will rapidly represent the speculative Windows®-based application examining for consistency in the following fields, walk client through the application analysis using the scientific chain of command calculation, disclose how to decipher the subsequent quality measurements, and close with a conversation of how client can adjust this strategy to address client own issues. Client will find that the capacity to rapidly assess the general nature of a product framework made out of numerous ascribes is an important expansion to client programming testing, advancement, and the board ranges of abilities.

The System under Analysis

We should quickly take a gander at the application under test so client will comprehend the objective of value investigation. The fake hunt application is a basic structure based application. In the event that client needs to analyse the general nature of a specific form with past forms, client needs to consider numerous frameworks ascribes. For the motivations behind this section just execution and usefulness utilized, yet the method will be indicated can manage quite a few credits. Albeit every product framework is extraordinary, the most widely recognized credits to consider while assessing in general quality incorporate availability, documentation, usefulness, internationalization, module/API, execution, security, arrangement, versatility, steadiness, convenience, and UI.

Obviously there are numerous credits, and each will have a huge number. Likewise, a considerable lot of these qualities cover one another. In any case, by and by, this rundown is a decent spot to begin. This method can manage for all intents and purposes any sort of programming framework—Applications based on Windows, Web applications for ASP.NET, class libraries, etc.

I will possibly offer a solitary benefit that speaks to the general essence of my overall product structure. There are a few open multi-property analysis procedures, but the one preferred is

known as the measure of logical order. Since the mid-1980s, the logical order measure has been around and has been used in a large variety of fields. The initial reference to the subject is the book "*The Analytical Hierarchy Method for Decisions in a Complex World*" by Thomas Saaty (McGraw-Hill, 1980).

Without of an organized procedure, attempting to assess the general nature of various forms of even this little spurious application would be extremely troublesome. In the wake of picking the characteristics, client would need to decide how to look at each expand on each property, how to measure that data, and how to total all that information into a significant measurement. At that point client would need to conclude how to decipher the outcomes. A vastly improved methodology is to utilize the rich insightful chain of command cycle to rapidly assess the constructs.

Setting up the Problem

The initial phase in the insightful pecking order measure is to set up the issue. On account of multi-trait programming quality investigation this implies choosing which fabricates client need to assess, and which ascribes client will use as a reason for the assessment. It has decided to think about the three latest forms of my speculative framework, Construction A, Construction B, and Construction C. The technical approach may require quite a few types, but for evaluation purposes, three or four is a decent sum, based on my experience.

The next client can select which client to use to determine the overall essence of each form. At that point, client will break down each trait into sub credits. It is chosen to separate execution into start-up execution and document save execution, and to separate usefulness into UI, information base, and organization usefulness. The method here permits client to decay sub ascribes into significantly more modest sub-sub credits, etc., to any profundity. When in doubt, client will frequently have high level credits and somewhere in the range of two and five sub ascribes.

Plate B-6.2: Traditional Representation of the Problem

Plate B-6.2 shows a chart customarily used to speak to the issue. It is loathed on the grounds that it joins the objective with the construct options and the quality ascribes in a manner that is hard for programmers to decipher. Issue is in plain structure, as appeared in Plate B-6.3 whichever portrayal design client chooses to utilize, it should obviously sum up the issue to pass on it to other people.

Issue	
Assess fabricate quality	
Choices	
Build A, Build B, Build C	
Traits	
Execution	
	Start-up
	Document Save
Usefulness	
	User Interface
	Information base
	Organization

Plate B6.3: Example Problem

Deciding the Relative Weights of the Comparison Attributes

After issue is arrangement, the following stage is to decide the general loads of every one of the examination ascribes. In my model up until now, I have not decided precisely how significant my picked credits are comparative with one another. For example, start-up execution might be considerably more critical to me than record save execution, or the other way around, or they might be similarly significant.

The scientific progression measure utilizes a couple astute correlation strategies. It works like this: Begin with my characteristic groupings of the most important category, which are execution and usefulness in this model. Create a structure for a table like this:

	Performance	Functionality
Performance		
Functionality		

The table is scale 2?? 2. At the highest level, it has two attributes. If we had three of the attributes at the highest level (for instance, an extra attribute of security) then my table would have been 3 x 3. First, we can use the table shown in; compare the relative value of product functionality versus product quality. Plate B-6.4. have two attributes at the highest level, the table scale 2?? 2. If we had three of the highest level attributes (for instance, an additional security attribute), then my table would have been 3 x 3, and so on. First, we can compare the relative value of product functionality versus product efficiency using the table shown in Plate B-6.4.

Relative Importance	Value
Equivalent significance/quality	1
To some degree more significant/better	3
Certainly more significant/better	5
Significantly more significant/better	7
Amazingly more significant/better	9

Plate B-6.4: Comparison Values

For my model guess It is resolved that usefulness is between "fairly more significant" (esteem = 3) and "certainly more significant" (esteem = 5) than execution, thus we get an estimation of 4 from the table. It is generally normal to utilize the qualities 1, 3, 5, 7, and 9, yet client can utilize a halfway incentive as done in model. The free translation of this value is that, in this product context, usefulness is many times as important to me as execution.

The upper-left components of the table are currently looking at the overall significance of execution against itself and the overall significance of utility against itself in taking down the correct corner to corner. Using the characteristics from the table in Plate B-6.4, customers will see that, in view of the fact that each characteristic has equal meaning relative to itself, we get estimates of 1. By definition, all the upper-left components of a scientific order measure examination table would be 1s to carry down right corner to corner. This fairness leaves my correlation table's upper-right cell, which is the general significance of execution versus utility. Since I recently stated that utility versus execution is a 4 (that is, that utility is approximately many times as critical as execution), the overall significance of execution versus utility should be 1/4 or 0.250. Execution is, as such, 1/4 as critical as utility. The following is the placement of these attributes in the table:

	Performance	Functionality
Performance	1	0.250
Functionality	4	1

Via description, numerical inverses of one another would be the Estimates of cells that are askew (45 degrees) from one another in a correlation table. Currently, in the aftermath of the completion of the general significance table, the "need vector" has been recorded from the table. Once more as a visual demonstration the loop is better explained. Per section first number receiving 5 and 1.250, individually. First, divide each passage by its segment as a whole in the overall significance table. We have 1/5 and 4/5 in the main section for this example, and 0.250/1.250 and 1/1.250 in the following chapter. This supplies the network with:

	Performance	Functionality
Performance	0.200	0.200
Functionality	0.800	0.800

The last step in deciding the appropriate vector is to take the usual of each column. This is or is communicated as a section vector: $(0.200 + 0.200)/2 = 0.200$ and $(0.800 + 0.800)/2 = 0.800$

Performance	0.200
Functionality	0.800

Using Microsoft Excel, the computations are anything but difficult to make, or if the client is more oriented, a C# or Visual Basic .NET programme can be composed to do it.

It is important to process the need vectors for and sublevel in the aftermath of having the need vector for the highest level of correlation ascribed (execution and usefulness). For the higher level trait classes, the loop is almost the same as that. It will be defined by showing how the need vector is determined by the usefulness ascribed (UI, information base, and organization).

Start by constructing a 3-3 table of voids. Next, in a couple of informative designs, look at the general context of each property. In this model, it is concluded that UI usefulness is "fairly more significant" than usefulness of the information base (esteem = 3), UI usefulness is "considerably more significant" than usefulness of the network (esteem = 7), and usefulness of the information base is "somewhat more significant" (esteem = 2) than usefulness of the network. In the correlation table, enter these three characteristics, position on the primary, 1s askew, inverses and join inverses for cell comparison around fundamental inclination. Record every section entirely at that stage. The table at the top of Plate B-6.5 has now emerged. At that point, partition each table cell to get the table at the bottom of Plate B-6.5 by its relative segment absolute. And then record each normal line to get the last vector of need, as seen here:

User Interface	0.681
Database	0.216
Network	0.103

Note that in any need vector, any individual incentive will be anywhere in the range of 0.0 and 1.0, and that the characteristics in any need vector will be entirely 1 (subject to adjusting blunder). What the customer ends up with is such a huge number of standardised loads of and trait required. As the characteristics that are the most accurate with the pair-wise analysis estimates customer join, customer should think about the need loads. The customer could easily generate these loads; however, one of the fun highlights of the informative progress measure is the pair-wise inspection measure that helps the customer to consistently produce the loads.

	User Interface	Database	Network
User Interface	1	3	7
Database	0.333	1	2
Network	0.143	0.500	1
Sum	1.476	4.500	10.000
	User Interface	Database	Network
User Interface	0.678	0.667	0.700
Database	0.226	0.222	0.200
Network	0.097	0.111	0.100

From that point forward, process the need vector for the usefulness credits, and afterward figure the need the vector for both ascribes. Accompaniment shows my examination table and the resulting vector of need:

	Start-up	File Save
Start-up	1	5
File Save	0.200	1
Start-up	0.833	
File Save	0.167	

Plate B-6.5: Two Tables

So now, It has set up issue (assess assemble quality for Construction A, Construction B, and Construction C), decided my examination credits (start-up execution, document save execution, UI usefulness, information base usefulness, network usefulness), and registered the need for each of the vectors to be utilized at the degree of the correlation ascribes.

Compare the Constructions on each Attribute

The next move in the process logical order measure the intention there is to create correlation Each type is based on each of the least-level examinations assigned in the wake of defining the problem of assembly quality assessment and deciding the vectors needed for the examination credits. We need to test Construction A versus Construction B versus Construction C in this model for each of the five assigned exams: start-up, record save, UI, database, and organisation. The measure of construct correlation is actually identical to the measure of trait test. For start-up execution, for instance, look at each type using the measures in the table in Plate B-6.4 along these lines. It obtained the following values in the model:

Start-up	Construction A	Construction B	Construction C
Construction A	1	3	5
Construction B	0.333	1	2
Construction C	0.200	0.500	1

All in all, it found that start-up execution for Construction A is "to some degree better" than for Construction B, that start-up execution for Construction A that is "certainly "Better" than for

Construction C, and that start-up execution for Construction B is "marginally better" than for Construction C. Using a calculation similar to the previous area (figure segment amounts, divide of cell by its segment absolute)

Start-up	
Construction A	0.648
Construction B	0.230
Construction C	0.122

Compare builds and measure ranking vectors using the same approach for the remaining four comparison attributes, as shown in

File Save	Construction A	Construction B	Construction C	Vector Ranking File Save	
Construction A	1	2	4	Construction A	0.571
Construction B	0.500	1	2	Construction B	0.286
Construction C	0.250	0.500	1	Construction C	0.143

UI	Construction A	Construction B	Construction C	Vector Ranking User Interface	
Construction A	1	1	3	Construction A	0.443
Construction B	1	1	2	Construction B	0.387
Construction C	0.333	0.500	1	Construction C	0.170

Database	Construction A	Construction B	Construction C	Vector Ranking Database	
Construction A	1	3	6	Construction A	0.639
Construction B	0.333	1	4	Construction B	0.274
Construction C	0.167	0.250	1	Build C	0.087

Network	Construction A	Construction B	Construction C	Vector Rating Network	
Construction A	1	4	5	Build A	0.638
Construction B	0.250	1	5	Build B	0.273
Construction C	0.200	0.200	1	Build C	0.089

Plate B-6.6: Quality Attributes and Ranking Vectors

To Generate Final Assessment, Aggregate Weights

Subsequent to setting up the construct examination issue, processing the trait need vectors, and registering the assemble correlation positioning vectors, the following stage is to total all the middle information to deliver the last assessment measurements. Likewise with the past advances, it's least demanding to clarify as a visual cue. On the off chance that we put the moderate outcomes into a table, we get one like client find in Plate B-6.7.

Performance (.200)			Functionality (.800)			
	Start-up (.833)	File Save (.167)	User (.681)	Interface	Database (.216)	Network (.103)

Construction A	0.648	0.571	0.443	0.639	0.638
Construction B	0.230	0.286	0.387	0.274	0.273
Construction C	0.122	0.143	0.170	0.087	0.089

Plate B6.7: Intermediate Results

The final quality value for Construction A is:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (.200)(.833)(.648) + \\
 & (.200)(.167)(.571) + \\
 & (.800)(.681)(.443) + \\
 & (.800)(.216)(.639) + \\
 & (.800)(.103)(.638) = 0.531
 \end{aligned}$$

All in all, the last quality measurement for each form is the weighted amount of its trait rankings. Similarly, the last quality incentive for Construction B is:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (.200)(.833)(.230) + \\
 & (.200)(.167)(.286) + \\
 & (.800)(.681)(.387) + \\
 & (.800)(.216)(.274) + \\
 & (.800)(.103)(.273) = 0.329
 \end{aligned}$$

Also, the last quality incentive for Construction C is:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (.200)(.833)(.122) + \\
 & (.200)(.167)(.143) +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & (.800)(.681)(.170) + \\ & (.800)(.216)(.087) + \\ & (.800)(.103)(.089) = 0.140 \end{aligned}$$

Now, I'm currently deciphering my assembly standard. Since the positioning vector values 1.0 client entirely, each expansion can normally be looked at on a rate premise. Construction A is openly $0.53 - 0.33 = 0.20$ in this model, provided the three forms, or 20 per cent better than Construction B. However, this understanding is to some degree deceiving on the grounds that it may apply when considering each of the three forms. Whenever I added a fourth form to my investigation at the end of the day, my quality vector will adjust and ultimately build an under 20 % better vector than Construction B. In addition, let me warn clients that the 3-decimal accuracy of the data is to some degree misleading. Since the data obtained from the table in Plate B-6.4 is normally rough, looking at structures using just two decimals of all things considered is a clever idea.

As I can see it, seeing it carefully as pattern knowledge is the most ideal approach to deciphering the implications of construction quality using the empirical chain of command measure. Customers can see a fairly consistent trend of change here. In view of my experience, when looking at three types, a disparity of 0.15 or greater is an immense contrast (in the ordinary feeling of the word, not in the factual sense) when in doubt of thumb. After the client has some experience dealing with the conceptual chain of significant measurement, the client can develop an appreciation of the client's measurements.

Discussion

As it seems, the indicator of technological innovation is a rich and ground-breaking strategy for determining the general existence of programming frameworks. There are many different customer procedures that could be used for meta-quality monitoring, but there are a few engaging features in the informative pecking order calculation. In programming quality meta-investigation, the use of an abstract scale ("significantly more significant") as compared to a quantitative scale is particularly important. Assume, for example, that the client estimates the execution. For a document save operation, The gap between 2 seconds and 3 seconds (50 per cent contrast) might not as significant as a time distinction of 4 seconds versus 6 seconds (also 50 per cent).The pair-wise correlation methodology used for logical command chain

measurement is also beneficial. Normally, contemplating two items all at once is much better than worrying about numerous things at the same time.

There are some drawbacks in using the informative cycle to calculate the efficiency of fabrication. As stated, the emotional scale is extremely helpful in examining programming efficiency, but precisely on the basis that the scale is abstract; it depends on human mistake. For instance, taking three kinds of my analysis that rely on organisational utility:

Database	Construction A	Construction B	Construction C
Construction A	1	3	6
Construction B		1	4
Construction C			1

On the off chance that the customer looks at the data intently, the customer can see that it is not absolutely steady. On the off chance that Construction A with 3 scores "acceptable parts" is much better than Construction B, as well as Construction A is 6 "acceptable parts" its Construction C, Construction B will probably be 3 "acceptable units" better than Construction C at that point, but Construction B was assessed as 4 compared to Construction C.

The logical chain of command measure has a slick method to assess a supposed irregularity record for every examination grid. Telling client the best way to process an irregularity list gauge is outside the extent of this segment, however it is very simple to ascertain. For the correlation lattice demonstrated before, the irregularity record is 0.05—which is underneath the by and large acknowledged edge estimation of 0.10. What's more, truth be told, my correlation of the three forms dependent on organization usefulness is conflicting and in a creation situation we would examine and reconsider those examinations. A few varieties of the logical progressive system measure alter the trait positioning vector esteems dependent on the relating irregularity record.

Another inconvenience of the insightful chain of command's abstract The size of this is that it is powerless against man's brain science, there is a desire to see change in forms thus client

should be mindful so as not to subliminally swell rankings of later forms. As usual, the last measurements might be on a par with the information.

As I would see it the greatest drawback of utilizing the scientific progression measure is that the quantity of examination tables can turn out to be enormous if client utilize a ton of correlation ascribes. This can prompt a propensity to bar substantial examination ascribes to keep the quantity of counts reasonable. In this segment Excel is utilized to deal with the insightful progressive system measure, yet there are a few great business apparatuses accessible that streamline the information input measure, perform estimations consequently, and have pleasant revealing abilities.

Conclusions

In spite of the fact that the scientific chain of importance measure has been the subject of many exploration papers and the overall agreement is that the strategy is both actually legitimate and for all intents and purposes helpful, there are pundits of the technique. My view on the issue is that client should utilize the logical pecking order measure as only one part of the general form quality investigation. It's an important enhancement to other even-handed and emotional strategies that measure item quality. By and large client ought not to depend totally on any single programming framework quality measurement or procedure.

Here demonstrated how simple and amazing the strategy is when used to screen construct quality. In view of my experience, utilizing the insightful pecking order cycle to gauge by and large programming quality speaks to a huge upgrade to customary methods like bug tally measurements and achievement agendas.

Moreover, client can utilize the procedure in different regions. On one undertaking, it can be utilized for serious examination to evaluate the general nature of my item comparative with major contending items. It is known about different analyser's utilizing comparable approaches to provide details regarding the soundness of another form of an item dependent on weighting the consequences of mechanized form confirmation tests. As the product advancement climate keeps on developing, procedures like the logical progression cycle will turn out to be progressively significant segments of the programming range of abilities.

APPENDIX B-7

Simulation of Monte Carlo

Simulation of Monte Carlo is an adaptable method for breaking down the conduct of some action, plan or cycle that includes vulnerability. The Monte Carlo recreation produces an arbitrary arrangement of added substance blunder esteems, one for every perception and every condition, and figures one bunch of bothers of the boundaries. These new boundaries, alongside the added substance blunder terms, are then used to register another figure that fulfils this new synchronous framework. At that point another arrangement of added substance blunder esteems and boundary bothers is registered, and the cycle is rehashed the mentioned number of times.

The Monte Carlo strategy is only one of numerous techniques for breaking down vulnerability engendering, where the objective is to decide how arbitrary variety, absence of information, or blunder influences the affectability, execution, or unwavering quality of the framework that is being demonstrated.

Monte Carlo simulation is ordered as a testing strategy in light of the fact that the data sources are haphazardly produced from likelihood appropriations to reproduce the way toward inspecting from a real populace. Thus, we attempt to pick a dissemination for the information sources that most intently coordinates information we as of now have, or best speaks to our present status of information. The information produced from the recreation can be spoken to as likelihood circulations (or histograms) or changed over the blunder bars, unwavering quality forecasts, resistance zones, and certainty intervals (See Plate B-7.1).

**Plate B-7.1: Schematic demonstrating the head of stochastic vulnerability engendering
(The essential guideline behind Monte Carlo recreation)**

The means of Monte Carlo replication relating to the proliferation of vulnerabilities shown in Figure 2 are truly basic and can be easily executed for basic models in Excel. We should simply follow the five basic advances that are recorded below:

Phase 1: The parametric model is developed, $y = f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_q)$.

Phase 2: A bunch of arbitrary sources of knowledge are created, $x_{i1}, x_{i2}, \dots, x_{iq}$.

Phase 3: The model is tested and the results stored as y_i .

Phase 4: For $I = 1$ to n , repeat stages 2 and 3

Phase 5: Evaluate the findings using histograms, measures of outlines, periods of certainty, etc.

APPENDIX B-8

FUZZY Logic

Fuzzy logic is a type of logic or probabilistic logic that is valued by many; it handles reasoning that is rough as opposed to set and right. In contrast to traditional logic hypothesis, where parallel sets have two-esteemed, true or bogus logic, fuzzy logic variables can have a real estimate ranging somewhere in the range of 0 and 1. in degree. In order to deal with the idea of halfway fact, where reality value could run between totally obvious and totally bogus, Fuzzy logic was reached out.

The hypothesis of Fuzzy sets manages a subset of the universe of talk, where the progress between full \ participation and non-enrolment is steady as opposed to sudden. For standard sets, otherwise called fresh or non- fuzzy sets, if A is a fresh subset of X, the capacity

$$\mu_{A(x)} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } x \in A \\ 0 & \text{for } x \notin A \end{cases}$$

$\mu_{A(x)} = 1$ for $x \in A$ 0 for $x \notin A$ is known as the trademark capacity of A. The evaluation here has two qualities: 0 and 1, if x is a component of A it's worth is 1; else it is 0.

In fuzzy set hypothesis an item may have a place just somewhat. Hence, the evaluation in a fuzzy set can be anything from zero to one, and its enrolment work is $\mu_A(x): X \rightarrow [0,1]$ with the evaluations 1 and 0 speaking to, individually, full participation and non-participation in a fuzzy set.

APPENDIX B-9

Cost Analysis from Life Cycle

Life Cycle Cost Analysis is a general expense measure of a venture options and selecting the plan that ensures the office can provide its efficiency and capability with the lowest and highest cost of ownership steady. In the plan cycle, the LCCA should be done right off the bat when the ability to refine the strategy to ensure a reduction in life-cycle costs remains (LCC). Cost Analysis Life-Cycle refers to the present value of full annual ownership expenditures for different options by calculating costs in the current dollars and repaying those expenses over the life of the company.

Most important thing in checking the LCCA assignment or any other monetary assessment strategy is to finalize the impact of finances and optional plans of assemblies and constructional outline in addition with the evaluation and expression of the effects in dollars terms.

Plate B-9.1: LCCA for 30 years of a Building

In Plate B-9.1, Viewed over a long term period, introductory structure costs represent roughly only 2% of the aggregate, while tasks and support costs equivalent 6%, and faculty costs equivalent 92%.

APPENDIX B-10

Sensitivity Analysis

Energy and water conservation projects by FEMP are under suggestion of Sensitivity analysis Progressive investigation is accommodating for:

- Questionable Identification info esteems has the best impact on a specific proportion of financial valuation,
- Defining the inconstancy in the information esteem impulses the scope of a proportion of financial valuation, and
- Challenging various conditions to answer “situation imagination in which” questions.

Recognizing the primary boundaries, representing the top and bottom limits or answer "consider the possibility that" questions, basically revise the imagination and participation from top to bottom including all the financial assessment measures expected to be experimented.

Deciding the fitting qualities to dole out to the mathematical things (the information factors) in a model is a basic and testing some portion of the model structure measure in choice examination. Yet, finding mathematical qualities for genuine issues requires gathering pertinent information, which can here and there be troublesome. So we frequently manage with harsh appraisals. On account of the vulnerability about the genuine estimation of a mathematical thing, it is critical to discover how the arrangement got from the model would change (if by any stretch of the imagination) if the mathematical worth relegated were changed to other conceivable qualities. This cycle is alluded to as affectability investigation. We can apply such examination to the different fixings that go into the figuring of the settlements, to the probabilities of the various conditions of nature and even to the chief's utility capacity. Fundamentally, affectability investigation addresses the inquiry, "What has any kind of effect in this choice?" The point of displaying in dynamic is to create an essential choice model - one whose structure and substance are only adequate to tackle a specific issue. That is, the issues that are tended to in an essential choice model are the ones that issue, and those issues left out are the ones that don't make a difference.

Options can be screened based on deterministic and stochastic predominance, and substandard options can be disposed of. Recognizing predominant options can be seen as a

variant of affectability investigation, for utilize from the get-go in an examination. In affectability investigation terms, examining choices for predominance add up to finding out if there is any way that one option could wind up being superior to a second. In the event that not, at that point the primary option is overwhelmed constantly and can be disregarded. So affectability examination can prompt altering the structure of a model.

The Affectability Test is used to assess how "delicate" a model is in terms of changes in the model boundary estimation and changes in the model structure. Here, boundary affectability is at the middle. Boundary affectability is typically followed by a progression of tests in which the modeller sets different boundary estimates to perceive how a boundary change induces an adjustment in the stocks' dynamic behaviour. Affectability research is a helpful instrument in model structure as well as in model evaluation by showing how the model behaviour responds to changes in boundary estimates. Affectability testing helps create trust in the model by considering the flaws in models that are routinely linked to boundaries. Numerous limits in models of structure components speak to quantities that are extremely problematic or even impossible in fact to calculate to a lot of accuracy. Additionally, in fact, some boundary estimates alter. Therefore, the modeller is, for the most part, questionable to a degree regarding the boundary values he prefers and can use gauges when constructing a structural elements model. Affectability research helps him to find out what degree of accuracy is necessary for a limit to make the model sufficiently helpful and valid. In the event that the tests show that the model is unfeeling, it may very well be conceivable to use a gauge at that point as opposed to an incentive with more notable precision. Affectability analysis may also illustrate which boundary values are appropriate to use in the model. It gives some indication that the boundary esteems reflect, at any rate to some degree, "this present reality." on the off chance that the model acts true to form from certifiable perceptions." The modellers are helped by sensitivity tests to grasp elements of a structure. In outrageous situations, doing various items with a wide variety of qualities will provide bits of information in the conduct of a system. Seeing that the system changes tremendously, with an alteration in a boundary value will discern a point of influence in the model, a boundary whose unique value will ultimately affect the framework's behavioural process.

APPENDIX B-11

Baseline Analysis

Baseline Analysis, all information components going into the counts are fixed. The term standard examination is utilized to indicate a total investigation in all regards however one; it doesn't address the impacts of vulnerability.

To think about your information, you pick the examination results that you need to set as the benchmark form. You utilize the gauge rendition to look at all ensuing investigation aftereffects of a similar information source. For instance, on the off chance that you ran a section investigation work on information source An on Tuesday, you could then set the segment examination consequences of source an as the benchmark and save the gauge in the archive. On Wednesday, when you run a segment investigation work on information source A once more, you would then be able to think about the current examination aftereffects of information source A with the standard consequences of information source A.

To recognize changes in your information, a benchmark examination work assesses the substance and structure of the information for contrasts between the pattern results and the current outcomes. The substance and structure of your information comprises of components, for example, information classes, information properties, essential keys, and information esteems. In the event that the substance of your information has changed, there will be contrasts between the components of every form of the information. In the event that you are observing changes in the structure and substance of your information consistently, you should determine a checkpoint at standard spans to contrast with the pattern. You set a checkpoint to save the examination aftereffects of the table for correlation. You would then be able to decide to contrast the gauge with the checkpoint or to the latest investigation results.

APPENDIX B-12

The RAM Process

Risk Assessor Model (RAM)

The RAMP cycle comprises of four exercises, these exercises are done at various phases of venture lifecycle, the exercises along with the occasions into which they expected to be led are demonstrated underneath:

Process Launch: directed from the get-go in the venture lifecycle.

Risk Review: led before key choices or stretches.

Risk Management: directed consistently between hazard surveys.

Process Close-Down: directed toward the finish of the speculation lifecycle or on untimely end.

Moreover, every action contains various stages which in turns comprise of different cycle steps. More to this point, the occasions for playing out every action vary as per the reason for leading them; that is, the beginning and end exercises are performed once as they are identified with building up and shutting down the cycle; notwithstanding, a few danger surveys will be directed at basic stages or time stretches inside the speculation lifecycle. Too, hazard the executives exercises are ceaseless activities performed inside danger audits stretches and with agreement to the investigations, systems and plans came about because of past danger survey. The RAMP cycle is portrayed in Plate B-12.1 and the exercises from which this cycle is comprised are communicated in the resulting areas.

Plate B-12.1: The RAM Process

APPENDIX B-13

International Project Risk Assessment (IPRA)

Introduction

Surveying and overseeing hazard is an intricate and basic undertaking for global development projects, yet not many assessment instruments and rules exist to help proprietors and contractual workers with capital office arranging and development. When undertaking worldwide capital activities, proprietors have restricted assets to evaluate an assorted arrangement of political, geographic, financial, natural, administrative, security, and social danger factors. The IPRA distinguishes and depicts issues that are the basic components identified with a global capital venture and permits the task group to zero in on danger variables of likely concern. The IPRA is expected to assess the danger introduction and give a sign of possible effect of danger during the full venture life cycle. The IPRA demonstrates which segments of the venture should be considered for hazard relief as a component of a general danger the board methodology. The structure of IPRA is appeared in Plate B-13.1.

<p>SECTION I – COMMERCIAL</p> <p>I.A. Business Plan</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> I.A.1. Business case I.A.2. Economic model/feasibility I.A.3. Economic incentives/barriers I.A.4. Market/product I.A.5. Standards and practices I.A.6. Operations I.A.7. Tax and tariff <p>I.B. Finance/funding</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> I.B.1. Sources & form of funding I.B.2. Currency I.B.3. Estimate uncertainty I.B.4. Insurance <p>SECTION II – COUNTRY</p> <p>II.A. Tax/tariff</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> II.A.1. Tariffs/duties II.A.2. Value added tax II.A.3. Legal entity establishment II.A.4. Application of tax laws and potential changes II.A.5. Technology tax II.A.6. Personal income tax II.A.7. Corporate income tax II.A.8. Miscellaneous taxes <p>II.B. Political</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> II.B.1. Expropriation and nationalism II.B.2. Political stability II.B.3. Social unrest/violence II.B.4. Repudiation II.B.5. Government participation and control II.B.6. Relationship with government/owner II.B.7. Intellectual property <p>II.C. Culture</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> II.C.1. Traditions and business practices II.C.2. Public opinion II.C.3. Religious differences <p>II.D. Legal</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> II.D.1. Legal basis II.D.2. Legal standing II.D.3. Governing law/contract formalities and language II.D.4. Contract type and procedures II.D.5. Environmental permitting II.D.6. Corrupt business practices <p>SECTION III – FACILITIES</p> <p>III.A. Project scope</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> III.A.1. Scope development process III.A.2. Technology III.A.3. Hazardous material requirements III.A.4. Environmental, health, and safety III.A.5. Utilities and basic infrastructure III.A.6. Site selection and clear title III.A.7. Approvals, permits, and licensing 	<p>III.B. Sourcing and supply</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> III.B.1. Engineered equipment/material/tools III.B.2. Bulk materials III.B.3. Subcontractors III.B.4. Importing and customs III.B.5. Logistics <p>III.C Design/engineering</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> III.C.1. Design/engineering process III.C.2. Liability III.C.3. Local design services III.C.4. Constructability <p>III.D. Construction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> III.D.1. Workforce availability and skill III.D.2. Workforce logistics and support III.D.3. Climate III.D.4. Construction delivery method III.D.5. Construction permitting III.D.6. General contractor availability III.D.7. Contractor payment III.D.8. Schedule III.D.9. Insurance III.D.10. Safety during construction III.D.11. Communication and data transfer III.D.12. Quality <p>III.E. Start-up</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> III.E.1. Trained workforce III.E.2. Facility turnover III.E.3. Feedstock and utilities reliability <p>SECTION IV – PRODUCTION/OPERATIONS</p> <p>IV.A. People</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> IV.A.1. Operational safety IV.A.2. Security IV.A.3. Language IV.A.4. Hiring/training/retaining IV.A.5. Localizing operational workforce <p>IV.B. Legal</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> IV.B.1. Governing law/operational liability IV.B.2. Permitting IV.B.3. Insurance IV.B.4. Expatriates IV.B.5. Environmental compliance <p>IV.C. Technical</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> IV.C.1. Logistics and warehousing IV.C.2. Facilities management and maintenance IV.C.3. Infrastructure support IV.C.4. Technical support IV.C.5. Quality assurance and control IV.C.6. Operational shutdowns and startup
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late B-13.1: IPRA Risk Structure

Application and use of IPRA

Danger can emerge intensive out the task life cycle, viable danger the board is an intuitive cycle and not restricted to a one-time examination. Given the advancing notion of risk, the most critical assessment of the system is noteworthy during the IPRA instrument should be sent at three phases on the venture timetable: (1) program choice, (2) approval of task plausibility, promotion (3) choice to continue with itemized designing and development. Further employments of hardware happen during project execution and activities. Also, the instrument can be utilized as an agenda any time. Plate A-1.2 delineates the instrument is most significant appropriate during project life cycle

Plate B-13.2: Application of the IPRA tool during the project life cycle

People associated with the undertaking should get comfortable with the organization of the IPRA instrument and utilize the IPRA project appraisal worksheets while assessing a venture. Two kinds of worksheets are accessible, the contrast between them being that members have the assessment of choosing their own overall effect level or utilizing the pattern relative effect for every component. Table B-13.3 gives an illustration of one IPRA sheet.

Plate B-13.3: IPRA Assessment Sheet

CATEGORY	Likelihood of Occurrence (L)					Relative Impact (I)					Baseline	L, I	Comments	
	Very low		Very High			Negligible		Extreme						
	NA	1	2	3	4	5	A	B	C	D				E
IA. BUSINESS PLAN														
IA1. Business case												E		
IA2. Economic model / feasibility												D		
IA3. Economic Incentives / barriers												E		
IA4. Market/Product												D		
IA5. Standards and practices												D		
IA6. Operations												D		
IA7. Tax and tariff												D		

The combination of probability of occurrence and relative effect defines the overall importance of the hazard to an undertaking for a given variable. The blend appears on Plate B-13.4. By finding the directions for the likelihood of event (L) and relative impact, the required relative significance risk level can be found (I). When the general importance of the component has been resolved, it is plotted on the hazard network in its specific region. Dangerous objects in the upper right corner of the hazard lattice represent the most significant danger to the company, while those in the lower left are of minor concern. Obviously, the task group can minimise components of greater relative significance. As the assessment proceeds, major mission hazards and anomalies should be made clear to the business community, and

this expected view should end up being helpful in the risk management, control, and relief measures of the venture.

Plate B-13.4: IPRA Risk Matrix

The IPRA gives the evaluation group a cycle to check the overall significance of the undertaking's danger. It should be noticed that the general significance of a particular danger may change during the existence pattern of the task, and in this manner, relief maybe techniques ought to be changed likewise. Utilizing the direction, the appraisal group decides the sort and level of moderation for the individual components. Components with high relative significance should be additionally tended to.

Conclusion

The IPRA device is an extensive and sound for distinguishing and evaluating the overall effect of most of danger issues experienced on worldwide capital offices. IPRA instrument additionally gives standard relative effect esteems help the undertaking group to distinguish hazard variables of most noteworthy significance to the task group. (12)

APPENDIX B-14

The ICRAM Platform Model of International Construction Risk Assessment (ICRAM-1)

The International Construction Risk Assessment Model (ICRAM-1) allows the customer by breaking down hazards at large scale (or national climate), sector, and venture levels to determine the possible hazards associated with growing activities in a worldwide market. ICRAM-1 offers an organised means of measuring the hazard markers involved in a worldwide development operation and is designed to inspect a specific undertaking in an external country. The model introduced in this paper helps the chief in assessing the expected danger at the large scale, market, and development project levels by utilizing accessible data, information, and skill. All things considered, it tends to be utilized adequately prior to directing broad statistical surveying and interest in a worldwide development market, just as during the undertaking arranging and execution stages. The structure of ICRAM-1 is;

P

late B-14.1: Framework ICRAM-1

Construction Risk Assessment Mode Worldwide (ICRAM-1)

In the initial stages of the company evaluation, ICRAM-1 was intended to assist chiefs to break down numerous hazard indicators and abstractly identify hazards at large scale, sector, and mission levels. The ICRAM-1 device is displayed on Plate B-14.1. As shown in this map, a large-scale environment may cause a portion of the risk indicators at the business and venture level, whereas a portion of the undertaking level indicators may be influenced by the market level climate. Aside from this, because of their special environment, extra pointers can be set off within each of the three levels. A total of 73 hazard indicators were differentiated from the three that could probably have an effect on the undertaking at the full size, sector, or level of the undertaking. Explicit standards and sub-models collected the recognised hazard factors to build up the i. The recognised hazard factors were collected by explicit standards and sub-models to build up the interrelationship and progressive system between the various hazard factors at full scale, business and enterprise levels. It further empowered the investigation of that person and generally had an effect on the cost of the undertaking, as well as on the general adequacy of the undertaking's activities in a given country and its emerging market. The recognised risk factors were collected by explicit criteria and sub-models to build up. The recognised hazard factors were collected by The All The distinguished hazard indicators may not have a comparable degree of significance for various circumstances of the country/market/project. Progressive evaluation requires all danger measures to be deliberately measured in order to build up their degree of relevance for a particular situation.

Modelling Moulds

The ICRAM-1 breaks down 73 danger pointers at three interrelated levels (full scale, market, and task). In this way, a few suppositions were characterized to set up the sensible limits for the choice and danger examination model and to encourage calculation of danger at the three levels. The essential presumptions of the ICRAM-1 are:

1. Models, sub-measures, markers identified with one another as per the pecking order however are autonomous of one another inside the own degree of the progression.
2. Threat pointers at the business level may be directly influenced by the danger environment of the large scale level, and risk pointers at the job level could be directly affected by the conditions of large scale or market hazard.

3. Those measures specifically affected by the upper level (both the full scale and the level of the market) are not affected by the explicit markers at the upper level, but rather by the general environment of risk at that level.
4. A hazard estimate more notable than the level of hazard associated with the level of impact cannot be measured by a marker specifically influenced by the hazard environment at the upper level (for example, a business level pointer affected by the large-scale level of hazard climate).
5. Both pointers specifically affected by an upper level (both the full scale and the business level) are highly affected by that level (i.e. two pointers are not likely to have a comparable level of impact from an upper-level threat climate).

Conversation of Approaches Involved

The ICRAM-1 uses the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) to dissect the chain of command of danger pointers inside each level and to decide the general significance of the danger markers by setting up need among the models, sub-measures, and pointers. This investigation was significant since all the pointers in a specific level probably won't have a similar level of importance regarding the venture, market, and nation viable. The progression of danger pointers is efficiently assessed by utilizing a progression of framework calculations to decide the chief's inclination request among the different criteria. The hazard related with every marker is abstractly settled by the essential leader (PDM) by utilizing a foreordained size of 0–100, where 0 infers no danger and 100 suggests greatest danger (Plate B-14.2). In the overall scale appeared in Plate B-14.2, the hazard is characterised as an aspect of the probability of the occasion and the associated severity (misfortune), where the client is characterised by extreme, medium and low seriousness depending on the client company's risk-taking cap. The assurance of risk associated with each indicator (i.e. the probability and severity) depends on the nation/market/project information that is available and the client information. As shown in Plate B-14.2, the abstract risk assessment and weight associated with the pointers (set up prior to using the AHP) together give the weighted total danger to a particular level, the hazard estimates are calculated using the preordained scale. As more information about the hazard markers is available to the client, the subjectivity of the hazard assessment is reduced. Since the model relies on abstract risk pointer evaluation, it is critical that the client provides feedback based on solid data wellsprings and their own judgement. By and by, the ICRAM-1 allows each customer to work with the model and provide feedback in turn. Nonetheless, a cooperative choice module for incorporating the information and

perceptions provided by a group of specialists evaluating the situation will be incorporated into future advancement of this model.

Degree of risk (1)	Definition (fn. = function of) (2)	Assessment (3)
No risk (improbable situation)	fn. (lowest probability, lowest severity)	0
Low risk	fn. (probability, low severity)	25
Moderate risk	fn. (moderate probability, moderate severity)	50
High risk	fn. (moderate–high probability, high severity)	75
Prohibitive risk	fn. (high probability, very high severity)	100

Plate B-14.2: Risk Assessment Scale

Conclusions

The ICRAM-1 offers an organised way of measuring the threat pointers involved in a global development operation. It is intended to evaluate a specific venture in an outside country and can be used as a device to assess the danger involved in global development speculation as one of the primary steps in task evaluation. From the ICRAM-1 study, four primary results are obtained: (1) high-hazard indicators; (2) the impact of the national environment on a particular undertaking; (3) the effect of the business climate on a specific task; and (4) the overall danger of the undertaking. For each of the three levels, high-hazard pointers can be differentiated by specifying the threshold-weighted risk. The limit estimates will depend on the client company's risk taking capacity.

Another conceivable utilization of the ICRAM-1 is in breaking down various nations concerning a particular task and in looking at changed kinds of undertakings, (for example, mechanical, private, business, and framework projects) in a particular nation. Utilizing the model a few times over a characterized period can likewise encourage checking of danger related with a particular nation as for the full scale, market, and task levels. A plot of danger evaluation information more than quite a while (or periods, that is, t_0 , t_1 , t_2 , and so on) will demonstrate the pattern of danger markers in that nation. This information could likewise be utilized for leading re-enactment studies to decide the patterns of dangers and the connection between the dangers at the large scale, market, and task levels. (13)

APPENDIX B-15

Computer Cost Analysis, Benchmarking, and Risk Management Hybrid Approach (COBRA)

COBRA (Cost assessment, Benchmarking, and Risk Assessment) is a technique for cost assessment that joins parts of algorithmic and experiential methodologies. Current cost assessment methods have various disadvantages. For instance, creating algorithmic models requires broad past undertaking information. Additionally, off-the-rack models have been discovered to be hard to adjust however incorrect without alignment. Casual methodologies dependent on experienced assessors rely upon assessors' accessibility and are not effectively repeatable, just as not being substantially more exact than algorithmic strategies. COBRA philosophy:

Plate B-15.1: Indication of Output Approximation Model

Principles of the Method

As shown in PlateB-15.1, the efficiency evaluation model has two parts. The primary component is a model that offers an overhead calculation of expenses. The subsequent portion is a model of profitability which measures efficiency from this overhead cost. Since the main part is free of any measure of pre-owned venture scale, it may take care of a few profitability models; this enables the use of an exceptional cost overhead model in light of different size estimation, regardless of different types of venture needing distinctive size estimates and despite adjustments in the corporate size estimation software. As the efficiency

model needs less work to develop and sustain, as examined below, this is a solid financial dispute for the use of COBRA.

Overhead Cost

The model of cost overhead estimation takes a bunch of information as data that represents a particular undertaking. The venture knowledge survey collects this information. The model assumes that the overhead cost is due to imperfect circumstances associated with an organisation. The overhead cost is reported as an incremental rate on top of the cost of an enterprise operating under ideal conditions. This is listed as an ostensible undertaking.

Productivity Model

An ostensible venture has the most elevated conceivable profitability. Genuine tasks that veer off from the ostensible will have lower efficiency. It is normal (and shows during the approval) that the cost overhead gauge is firmly identified with efficiency. In particular, the relationship is:

$$1 = b_0 - (b_1 \times CO) \quad (\text{eqn.1})$$

Where the profitability is P, and the operating cost is CO. This is the state of profitability in Plate 1. With the ultimate objective that this relationship is direct, the cost overhead measurement model is defined. The profitability of an ostensible undertaking is the b_0 limit. Between CO and P, the b_1 boundary catches the slant. By and by, as only a bivariate relationship is seen, the two beta borders above can be resolved from a little verifiable knowledge set of undertakings (~10).

Cost of Measuring

Product ventures have been proposed to show economies or diseconomies of scale [2]. Nonetheless, a recent observational investigation provided evidence that this dispute is not upheld and suggests that the relation between effort and size is straightforward [15]. In this way, we agree that the relation between effort and size is direct. This is communicable as:

$$\text{Effort} = \alpha \times \text{Scale/Size} \quad (\text{eqn.2})$$

At eqn. 2, both the value and the scale are variables that for each project are calculated. The value is given by:

1

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{\beta_0 - (\beta_1 \times CO)} \quad (\text{eqn.3})$$

It is necessary to overcome the initiative for the particular undertaking from eqn. 2 using the scale of the system and the overhead cost. The cost overhead increases and therefore the value increases as one digress away from the ostensible venture, indicating that more effort is expended for a comparable framework size (i.e., lower efficiency).

Undertaking Assessment of Cost Risks

The definition of cost threat we use is the possibility of invading the spending plan or any additional rate above it for a provided project. The estimation of an expenditure B transforms into aB and COB estimates in the model introduced above, paying no attention to the methods used. The initial step is to record the probability of having a more prominent CO/a value than COB/aB. At that point, it is appropriate to characterise the most severe passable PM probability that a given undertaking has less efficiency (1/aB) than that expected by the financial plan. Choices should then be rendered as follows with respect to chance assessment: if

$$P(\alpha \geq \alpha) > P_M \quad (4^{\text{th}} \text{ eqn})$$

If completed, the mission would be deemed to be high-risk and precautionary tasks, just as emergency action courses would be mandatory. Compared to different overhead costs, this approach can be applied to various limits. In such a scenario, different degrees of danger and distinctive activity plans relevant to each level of danger can be described.

Benchmarking Undertaking Expense

Comparable expectations are followed by cost benchmarking. The disparity in essence exists in the way in which CO/limit estimates are characterised. In our particular case benchmarking means comparing a new undertaking's CO with verifiable project agent based information. The goal is to determine whether this mission is likely to be entirely more difficult to run than the association's "normal" project and to add more overhead costs. Such an inspection may trigger decisions with regard to the company's personnel or the legally binding agreement with the client. We can also characterise edges related to the CO middle (COT for "common")

or upper quartile (COM for "dominant part") in the association's venture knowledge base for hazard assessment. At that point, the probability of lying better than edges is measured and used to pick the new task's presumed relative level of trouble: above average, above the lion's share.

Assessing Cost Overhead

The secret to our whole approach is that the probability of concocting a cost overhead gauge meets the suspicions of a mission in the 1st equation. This is achieved by a simple model of variables that influence the task costs under investigation within the nearby environment. Cost elements or drivers and interactions with cost overhead or among the variables themselves comprise a fundamental model. The ties show the principle of the effects on overhead costs. Two kinds of relations exist: direct and collaboration. An immediate relationship means that the factor simply raises or decreases overhead costs independently of the projections of different variables. A partnership relationship means that the way a factor affects cost overhead depends on at least one different variable's value(s). In the causal model we develop, we limit the number of variables to a limit of three in cooperation. It is critical that all the variables associated with cost are displayed in a particular way so that they can be interpreted as added substance in order to maximise the demonstration period. This means that each component expands/decreases costs by a certain amount, and that the total effect on spending is the amount of each of the individual elements' impact.

Method's Approval

It is necessary to demonstrate exactly two things in order to approve our methodology. To begin with, the assumption that the basic equation no 1 is legitimate (i.e., that cost overhead is unequivocally associated to profitability). Precise evaluation effort is given by equation no 2. Using the contextual analysis, underlying acceptance of our methodology is presented.

Conclusion

This strategy is revealed as helpful addition with the minimum effort in creation of an association to neighbourhood charge and risk modules, and a huge arrangement of undertaking information is unable to gather or recover. The following rate and risk assessment modules are considered to be operative addition with the revised measure of development at any level or on continuous basis. (14)

APPENDIX C-1

TYPE OF QUESTIONS

Following are some types of questions were asked to the respondents during the survey. The questionnaire includes variety of questions such as

Close Ended Questions: In this type of questions, answers are limited to a fixed set of responses.

∅

Average annual value of work for last 5 years (In million):

Network Questions: Identical Reaction Classes are appointed to Different Inquiries

Risk Identification	Risk Classification					Actual Risk Allocation				Risk Response				
	Risk Impact			Risk Nature	C	U	O	CT	CR	SH	RT	RD	TR	N/A
	Time	Cost	Performance											
Design process delays	1 5	2 5	3 5	4 5	X				X			X		
<p>Scale for Risk Effect: 1=very low, 2=low, 3=medium, 4=high, 5=very high.</p> <p>For Risk Nature: 1. C=Controllable, 2. UC=Uncontrollable.</p> <p>For Actual Allocation: 1. O=Owner 2. CT=Consultant 3. CR=Contractor 4. SH=Shared.</p> <p>For Risk Response: 1. RT=Risk Retention, 2. RD=Risk Reduction, 3. TR=Risk Transfer, 4. N/A=Not Applicable.</p>														

Introduction

This study is being directed as a component of the exploration for my DBA Dissertation:

I am a full-time understudy at the University of the West of Scotland, examining Doctorate of Business Administration. My Dissertation is expected to zero in intensely on Risk, and the Aim is to fundamentally assess hazard the executive's cycle in SMEs.

Your bits of knowledge and your answers, explicitly, may demonstrate very accommodating in outlining a new way to deal with this effective issue. The review is grounded in a bunch of nonexclusive inquiries, each organized as an "open" question to boost your own commitment through your experience to date. Issues of privacy ought not to emerge, however on the off chance that they do, at that point please advise the assessor so that fitting move can be made. The UWS DBA information base isn't accessible to general society.

Personal Information (optional)

Name: _____

Company Name: _____

Total Working Experience: _____

Company Information

Type of Projects (in progress)

Commercial	☐	Residential	☐	Infrastructure	☐
Industrial	☐	Environmental	☐	Others	☐

Yearly Turnover

<1million	☐	1 to 5million	☐	>5million	☐
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Danger Classification	Danger Classification		Actual Danger Allocation				Danger Response				
	Causes	Risk Impact	Risk Nature	O	C	C	S	R	R	T	N
				T				T	D	R	/

	Time	Cost	Performance			R	H				A
				C	UC						
EXAMPLE (Note: scale & abbreviations defined below.)											
Design process delays	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	X			X			X	
DESIGN RELATED RISKS											
Design process delays	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5								
Errors or omissions	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5								
Inadequate specifications	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5								
Loss or delay due to differing site or design changes	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5								
CONSTRUCTION RISKS											
Quality problem	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5								
Site accidents	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5								
Site access	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5								
Equipment failure	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5								
Unavailability of labour	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5								
Unavailability of	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4	1 2 3 4 5								

equipment		5																
FINANCIAL & ECONOMIC RISKS																		
Inadequate cash flow	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5															
Delayed payment on contract	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5															
Underestimation of cost	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5															
Cost overrun due to schedule delays	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5															
Changes in regulation	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5															
Inconsistent application of laws	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5															
Change in trade aptitude	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5															
LEGAL AND REGULATORY RISKS																		
Exchange rate fluctuation	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5															
Inflation	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5															
Price fluctuation	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5															
Complicated/unstable tax structure	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5															
Import restrictions	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5															

Problems with permit and license	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5															
SUB-CONTRACTOR RISKS																		
Untrained workforce	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5															
Improper cash flow	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5															
Lack of expertise	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5															
Improper means of construction	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5															
Sub-contract failure	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5	1 2 3 4 5															

Scale for Risk Effect: 1=very low, 2=low, 3=medium, 4=high, 5=very high.

For Risk Nature: 1. C=Controllable, 2. UC=Uncontrollable.

For Actual Allocation: 1. O=Owner 2. CT=Consultant 3. CR=Contractor 4. SH=Shared.

For Risk Response: 1. RT=Risk Retention, 2. RD=Risk Reduction, 3. TR=Risk Transfer, 4. N/A=Not Applicable.

APPENDIX C-2
QUESTIONNAIRE 1

The interview/survey is between:

Interviewer

Interviewee

Name:

Company Name:

Total Working Experience:

Location:

Date:

This meeting/review is being led as a component of the exploration for my DBA Dissertation:

I am a full-time understudy at the University of the West of Scotland, considering Doctorate of Business Administration. My Dissertation is expected to zero in intensely on Risk, and the Aim is to basically assess hazard the executive's cycle in SMEs.

Your experiences and your answers, explicitly, may demonstrate very accommodating in outlining a new way to deal with this effective issue. The overview is grounded in a bunch of nonexclusive inquiries, each organized as an "open" question to augment your own

commitment through your experience to date. Issues of secrecy ought not to emerge, yet in the event that they do, at that point please inform the assessor so that fitting move can be made. The UWS DBA information base isn't accessible to general society.

There are 21 Questions:	
First category To identify key risk management process and practices in UK construction industry	
1.	Your diagram of danger the board in your association? a) Identify b) analyse c) evaluate d) control e) all of the above
2.	Would you be able to show if there is any stream graph to outline the RMP progressive system? a) Yes (attached) b) No
3.	What are the means and measures you take here for I. risk recognizable proof, II. assessment and III. III. Management? a)RM policy b)Training c)Workshops
4.	A specific danger the board instruments or procedures which are included, nonexclusive, or area explicit? a) Qualitative (intuition, judgement, past project data, experience etc.) b) Quantitative (@Risk, Risk Matrix, Safety Lite, ARM, etc.)
5.	I. Do all [relevant] representatives know the proper Risk definitions as per their jobs and duty? II. How is Risk observing degenerated to workers a)yes b)no c)somewhat a)monitoring b)chasing them c)emailing d)none of the above
Second Category To find out organisation(SME) culture and development level of danger the board in significant activities	
6.	How are your undertaking's risks being: I. monitored II. managed a)collecting information b)risk review c)brain storming d)fire fighting (dealt on spot) d)none of the above
7.	In different words, is Risk Management considered in a group level or an individual premise a)group level(hierarchy based) b)individual
8.	What measures do you take to keep up force and use of all Risk Management standards on your venture? a)keep the registers updated b)dedication of work c)other d)none of the above

9.	How do you guarantee staff responds equally, and emphatically to their jobs/contributions to the Risk Management measure?	a)inquire pleasantly b)risk reporting by individuals c)none of the above
10.	How do you measure the danger culture, Any strategy?	a)awareness quiz b)involvement of leader c)feedback from employees d)none of the above
Third Category To access the effect of danger organization process on general execution of SMEs in the Building industry		
11.	What are the results of helpless risk recognizable proof, evaluation and risk management the board on a task based ID?	a)time delay b)extra cost c)inappropriate performance d)compromised quality e)all of the above
12.	What is the prompt reaction technique, if any vulnerability happens?	a)counter on spot b)leave it for other stakeholder c)insurance claim d)none of the above
13.	How does the helpless risk management influence the funds of the organization/project?	a)change the whole strategy b)demotivate the owner c)reduce the profit margin d)all of the above

APPENDIX D-1

RISK MANAGEMENT TEMPLATE

Project risk management roles and responsibilities

Roles	Responsibilities
Project Managers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Integrate resources and time needed to implement the risk management plan in the project budget and schedule ▪ Develop, communicate and implement risk management plan ▪ Develop and update the risk register with the support of the Project Team and integrate it into the work plan ▪ Ensure proactive response to all risks and opportunities that will impact the successful delivery of the project. ▪ Produce risk management reports for sponsors ▪ Schedule and conduct project risk meetings. ▪ Monitor and update risks. ▪ Ensure quality of the risk data in the risk register. ▪ Track and monitor the effectiveness of risk response actions. ▪ Recommend training on risk management skills for project team as often as required
Project Delivery Team Member	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Identify the risks and describe them (e.g., political, corruption, etc.) ▪ Evaluate the possibility of the risks occurrence & assign descriptive rating (very low, low, medium, high, very high) ▪ Evaluate the consequences of risks on project cost, time, quality, environmental sustainability and stakeholder management & assign descriptive rating as above ▪ Assist to identify risk owner and develop risk response strategies ▪ Document risk response strategies and report to project manager for integration in risk management updates. ▪ Communicate with project manager about newly-identified risks,
	risk analysis, and retirement of risks.
Project Risk Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Support the project manager to develop and update the risk management plan and the risk register ▪ Promote and direct risk management for the project. ▪ Schedule and conduct project risk meetings ▪ Perform risk monitoring and updating ▪ Ensure quality of the risk data in the Risk Register ▪ Document risk response actions ▪ Track and monitor the effectiveness of risk response actions ▪ Track and monitor the effectiveness of risk response actions. ▪ Produce risk management reports for the project manager ▪ Report to the project manager on all matters related to risk management ▪ Compile the lessons learned in the area of risk management

Processes and Procedures

In UK, this clarifies how hazard the executives will be actualized for specific interstate undertaking. This part essentially discloses the plan how to reach, avail and implement exercises with respect to hazard the board for a specific roadway project in UK.

Frequency of Risk Management Meetings and Review of the Project Risks

Gatherings to examine and settling on choices on the undertaking hazard are planned as:

Weekly basis _____ Monthly basis _____ other

The danger/risk the executives ID, examination, reactions, survey and observing cycle will happen all through the entire periods of the venture life cycle. Complete survey and updating of danger record would happen in beginning of every progressive venture's period.

Danger Identification Tools & Techniques to be used

Roadway venture of UK conveyance group as well as undertaking hazard supervisory crew should utilize any blend of: agendas, conceptualizing, and chronicled information, meeting and counselling master to recognize potential danger that may influence the targets of the task at phased advancement.

Danger/Risk Investigation Methods to be Utilized

Subjective danger examination will be utilized to dissect the distinguished danger influencing the presentation of UK development projects

Danger Broadcasting Setup

Represent the yields of danger the executive's cycles will be reported examined and imparted. It clarifies the substance and organization of the danger register just as some other danger reports required. It likewise clarifies hazard correlated reports and organization expected to be received to convey undertaking dangers to the intrigued plan supports with partners. The suggestion is duplicate of danger/risk record layout should be connected to the danger/risk board plan.

Tracking

Report the hazard exercises going to be recorded to serve the present venture just for upcoming necessities addition with s cultured exercise.

Costing

It discloses the way to dispense assets, gauge supports needed for the administration of danger by the undertaking hazard supervisory group.

Risk Categories

The danger class gives a structure that guarantees a thorough methodology of methodical danger distinguishing proof to a reliable degree of subtleties and adds to the proficiency and nature of the recognize hazard measure. A danger arrangement system in type of a straightforward rundown of danger classifications can depict hazard classifications.

Appendix: Template of the Risk Register : continued

Data Entry into the Danger Registry

The data mentioned below provides a guide to the best way to enter data in the section of the example risk register given.

- **Risk ID:** Enter a one-of-a-kind evidence number/code distinction for the danger
- **Category:** Choose one of the hazard classes (Appendix B), e.g., Political, Natural.
- **Descriptions:** Include an assertion or reflection of the occasion and its anticipated effects on the venture should this danger arise, as seen in the example above.
- **Current status:** If fundamental, analyse what is currently being considered about the risk.
- **Rating of the risk event chance:** choose 1-5 as a percentage of the risk importance for reaction activities where 1 = low; 2 = low; 3 = medium; 4 = high and 5 = extremely high;
- **Rating of hazard outcomes:** Pick the outcome rating from 1 to 5 as described above.
- **Consequence score:** Join the outcome of the risk likelihood and its comparative outcome.
- **Strategy:** Join the scheme of sensible hazard reaction. Relief from this scenario
- **Response activities:** Provide a succinct portrayal of the reaction activity in order to minimise the probability of an incident or the result of an unfriendly risk to the mediocre edge of the undertaking.
- **Risk owner:** Write the name of the part of the business hazard supervisory group relegated to the hazard group.
- **Updated:** Enter the date on which the threat was made
- **Date last inspected:** Make any hazard corrections and increments and compose the update date into the last section of the survey date.

APPENDIX D-4

RISK SCALE

Rating	1 (Very low)	2 (Low)	3 (Medium)	4 (High)	5 (Very high)
Cost	Insignificant cost increase	< 5 % cost increase	5 - 10% cost increase	10 - 20% cost increase	> 20% cost increase
Time	Insignificant lapses	< 1 month lapses	1 - 3 month-lapses	3 - 6 month-lapses	> 6 month-lapses
Quality	Insignificant quality deficiency	No safety issues, deficiencies accepted by project team	No safety issues, deficiencies need PM approval	Quality may be accepted through mitigation	Unaccepted quality
Scope	Insignificant scope decrease	Variations in project limits with < 5 % cost increase	Variations in project limits with 5 - 10% cost increase	Sponsor disagreed that scope satisfied purpose & need	Scope does not satisfy purpose & need
Possibility	1 - 9%	10 - 19%	20 - 39%	40 - 59%	60 - 99%

APPENDIX D-5

RISK MATRIX

Risk possibility and Consequence Matrix for highway construction projects in Nigeria						
Possibility Rating	5: Very high	Blue	Yellow	Red	Red	Red
	4: High	Blue	Yellow	Red	Red	Red
	3: Medium	Blue	Blue	Yellow	Red	Red
	2: Low	Blue	Blue	Yellow	Red	Red
	1: Very low	Blue	Blue	Blue	Yellow	Red
		1: Very low	2: Low	3: Medium	4: High	5: Very high
Consequence rating						

Red sector implies top to bottom significance, yellow area shows intermediate significance, bottom line significance is represented by blue. Total number of the chances and results characterize the danger rating. Example: Risk having medium chances with high results is derived as red zone with an outcome of 12.

APPENDIX D-6

Future Extenuation Procedures for Top 10 Risks for SME's in the UK Construction Industry

S.No	Risk Category	Top 10 Risk Factors	Mitigation Measures
1	Subcontractors	Lack of skilled labor	MR1: Train existing labour MR2: Reevaluate recruiting practice MR3: Partner with Recruitment Agencies MR4: Plan your Labour well ahead
2	Subcontractors	Improper means of construction	MR5: Prequalification of Subcontractors MR6: Proper Contractual Terms and Conditions MR7: Arranging a QA/QC Plan MR8: Strong Safety Practices MR9: Minimum Insurance Requests
3	Financial and Economic	Changes in regulation	MR10: Prepare Contingency Funds MR11: Agree Terms and Conditions with Client MR12: Relevant Insurances in Place
4	Legal and Regulatory	Problems with permit and license	MR13: Ensuring Building Control is in Place MR14: Clear Understanding and Information of Regulations MR15: Nominate Responsible Party
5	Construction Risks	Site Accidents	MR16: Engage in Communication MR17: Training and Workshops MR18: Understanding Risks MR19: Proper PPE in Place MR20: Stay Alert and Keep Information Updated

6	Financial and Economic	Cost overrun due to schedule delays	MR21: Ensure Accurate Measures and BOQ MR22: Clear Suitable Plan and Cost, Time Schedule in Place MR23: Clauses of Inflation and Rates in Contracts MR24: Negotiate Fixed Prices of Labour and Material MR25: Reputable Suppliers and Local Labour Adoption MR26: Employe PM team or Consultant
7	Construction Risks	Site Access	MR27: Maintain emergency access to the site MR28: Ensure phased construction maintains access routes MR29: Consider likely space requirements for safe construction MR30: Ensure space and provision for welfare facilities MR31: Signage, Marking for the Vehicles and People
8	Legal and Regulatory	Import Restrictions	MR32: Establish Strong Ties Government Officials MR33: Form JVs with Local Partners if International Project MR34: Get Approval of All Imported Items in Time MR35: Reserve a Budget for Inflation and Restrictions
9	Financial and Economic	Delayed payment on contract	MR36: Ensure sufficient funds before project commences MR37: Develop a clear, suitable plan & visualise contingency fund MR38: Project owner to secure standby financing MR39: Establish independent project monitoring team to control cost and schedule
10	Construction Risks	Equipment failure	MR40: Regular Inspection MR41: Avoid Too Much/Too Less Maintenance MR42: Hire Professional Technicians for Maintenance MR43: Keep Upto Date Insurances

APPENDIX – D 7

Evaluation feedback interview questions

The Framework Validation

If it's not too much trouble find joined herewith 'Risk Management system for SME's in the UK Construction Industry' in Figure 6-1. The rules for the use of the structure are clarified a short time later. As a component of the approval cycle, generously assess the system following the approval measures beneath. Please benevolently remark on the clearness and breadth of the general structure

If it's not too much trouble sympathetically remark on the reasonable importance and appropriateness of the structure to the SME's in the UK Construction Industry.

What is your opinion on each of the basic rules/guidelines for the usage of each cycle of the structure?

The proposed hazard registry (Appendix) for supervising opportunities for SMEs in the UK Construction Industry is valuable or significant.

Do you take into account any of the suggested relief steps (Appendix) for the key nine most fundamental risks that should be removed for SMEs in the UK Construction Industry that are/are not relevant? Would it be ideal for you to comment?

If you don't mind remark if there are any restrictions or shortcomings of the structure.

If it's not too much trouble generously recognize other potential territories where you figure the structure can be utilized.

It would be ideal if you give your overall diagram and any recommendation (assuming any) for development of the structure.

Is it true that you are mindful of any current danger the board system SME's in the UK Construction Industry? In the event that indeed, it would be ideal if you give more subtleties to incorporate any contrast between the current danger the executives structure in UK and the one I have created.
